

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level – root causes, impacts, existing solutions and good practices

Final Report

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Acronyms

DMO	Destination Management Organization
DPSIR	Driving Forces – Pressures – State – Impacts – Responses Framework
ETC	European Travel Commission
FIT	Free Independent Traveller
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ILO	International Labour Organization
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
LAC	Limits of Acceptable Change
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development,
OTA	Online Travel Agency
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
VER	Visiting Friends and Relatives
WTTC	World Travel and Tourism Council

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Abstract

This study investigates the very topical issue of overtourism across Europe and in various types of destinations, in particular before the pandemic but also taking into account the Covid-19 crisis. The root causes, impacts and existing solutions implemented to counteract or mitigate unbalanced tourism growth are thoroughly and critically examined. The study has shown that overtourism is a compound phenomenon, understood and felt differently depending on the destination. Likewise, its assessment requires both a quantitative and qualitative approach and does not correspond to the identification of a maximum threshold beyond which the carrying capacity of a destination is exceeded. Overall, the study identified a need for more refined data, at higher territorial resolution levels. While the economic importance of tourism for destinations shall not be underestimated, overtourism leads to social (e.g. conflicts with local population) and environmental (e.g. pollution) problems. The examined destinations have proactively implemented a wide array of measures to foster off-season tourism, enhance the satisfaction and quality of tourists' experiences and disperse tourism flows territorially.

A key outcome of this study is the development of indicators to support a destination to better manage undesirable tourism developments and identify possible pathways for a more sustainable development of tourism. Likewise, a hands-on compendium designed for tourism professionals has been developed to gather information and solutions addressing overtourism.

Cette étude porte sur la question très actuelle du « surtourisme » en Europe et dans différents types de destinations. Les causes structurelles, les impacts et les solutions existantes mises en œuvre pour contrer ou atténuer la croissance déséquilibrée du tourisme sont examinés de manière approfondie et critique. L'étude a montré que le surtourisme est un phénomène complexe, compris et ressenti différemment selon les destinations. De même, son évaluation nécessite une approche à la fois quantitative et qualitative et ne correspond pas à l'identification d'un seuil maximal au-delà duquel la capacité de charge d'une destination est dépassée. Globalement, l'étude a mis en évidence la nécessité de disposer de données plus spécifiques, à des niveaux de résolution territoriale plus élevés. Si l'importance économique du tourisme pour les destinations ne doit pas être sous-estimée, le surtourisme entraîne des problèmes sociaux (par exemple, des conflits avec la population locale) et environnementaux (par exemple, la pollution). Les destinations examinées ont mis en œuvre de manière proactive un large éventail de mesures pour favoriser le tourisme hors saison, améliorer la satisfaction et la qualité de l'expérience des touristes et disperser les flux touristiques sur leur territoire.

L'un des principaux résultats de cette étude est le développement d'indicateurs pour aider les destinations à mieux gérer les développements touristiques indésirables et identifier les voies possibles pour un développement plus durable du tourisme. De même, un recueil pratique destiné aux professionnels du tourisme, rassemblant des informations et des solutions concernant le surtourisme a été élaboré.

Diese Studie untersucht das aktuelle Thema „Overtourism“ in Europa und entlang von verschiedenen Typen an Reisezielen. Die Ursachen, die Auswirkungen und die bestehenden Lösungen, mit denen unausgewogener Tourismuswachstum entgegengewirkt werden soll, wurden kritisch untersucht. Die Studie zeigt, dass Overtourism ein vielschichtiges Phänomen ist, das je nach Reiseziel unterschiedlich verstanden und empfunden wird. Ebenso erfordert die Analyse von Overtourism sowohl einen quantitativen als auch einen qualitativen Ansatz. Die Bewertung ob ein Reiseziel von Overtourism betroffen ist, kann nicht lediglich entlang eines definierten Schwellenwertes getätigt

werden. Insgesamt wurde in der Studie festgestellt, dass ein Bedarf an regionalen Tourismusdaten besteht. Während die wirtschaftliche Bedeutung des Tourismus für Reiseziele nicht unterschätzt werden darf, führt Overtourism zu sozialen (z. B. Konflikte mit der lokalen Bevölkerung) und ökologischen (z. B. Verschmutzung) Problemen. Die untersuchten Reiseziele haben proaktiv eine breite Palette von Maßnahmen umgesetzt, um den Tourismus in der Nebensaison zu fördern, die Zufriedenheit und Qualität der Touristinnen und Touristen zu verbessern und die Tourismusströme räumlich zu streuen.

Ein wichtiges Ergebnis dieser Studie ist die Entwicklung von Indikatoren, die den Reisezielen helfen sollen, unerwünschte Entwicklungen im Tourismus besser zu bewältigen und mögliche Wege für eine nachhaltigere Entwicklung des Tourismus aufzuzeigen. Ebenso wurde ein praktisches Kompendium für Tourismusfachleute entwickelt, um Informationen und Lösungen zum Thema Overtourism zu sammeln.

Executive Summary

This study consists of five parts: First, an extensive literature analysis was carried out (Task A). This was followed by the elaboration of 15 in-depth cases studies collected from around Europe (Task B). Based on this, an annotated compendium of overtourism literature and case studies has been compiled (Task C). As a result, a key output of the project have been recommendations on how to measure, monitor and manage unbalanced tourism development and its impacts (Task D). Finally, the research results were discussed and, if necessary, amended in a series of six stakeholder workshops (Task E).

Characteristics and occurrence of unbalanced tourism

The most frequently used term for unbalanced tourism is “overtourism”. Throughout the project, both terms have been used interchangeably. It is a complex, multidimensional phenomenon that implies exceeding the physical, ecological, economic, social and/or psychological carrying capacities of a destination through high numbers or densities of tourists.

Overtourism occurs in a variety of destinations, ranging from urban to rural and from mountain to coastal and island destinations. Destinations with important cultural or natural heritage sites or attractive protected areas are prone to be affected as well. The inventory carried out by the project team yielded the identification of a large number of destinations affected by overtourism throughout Europe. Prior to the outbreak of Covid-19 the majority of these destinations were urban and coastal. The pandemic changed this picture drastically, resulting in the occurrence of new overtourism “hotspots” in rural (mountain and coastal) areas caused by domestic tourism and day trips at the expense of urban tourism.

Another important finding is that overtourism rarely occurs in an entire destination or region. Instead, in two thirds of the inventoried cases only certain neighbourhoods, historic town centres, coastal strips or specific attractions were affected. Entire municipalities experience overtourism less frequently, mostly found in rural areas or smaller towns. Furthermore, in many destinations overtourism is a seasonal phenomenon.

Root causes and impacts of overtourism

The root causes of overtourism are as complex and diverse as the phenomenon itself. For a systematic analysis, they can be divided into the following categories:

- **External driving forces** consisting of general global developments as well as tourism-specific developments.
- More **recent tourism trends**, such as the occurrence of new source markets and the proliferation of information and communication technologies in tourism;
- Such external driving forces lead to tangible effects, i.e., increasing **tourism-induced pressure** at destination level.
- **Internal factors** in a destination may exacerbate or mitigate tourism pressure. These factors can be general or tourism specific.

The potential **impacts** of overtourism are likewise diverse, depending on the specific combination of driving forces, pressures and destination characteristics. Impacts can be physical, environmental, (socio-) economic or socio-cultural (including psychological). They can also be differentiated with respect to which stakeholder group is predominantly affected. To this end, there are five main categories of impacts:

- The **degradation of the local infrastructure** – such as roads, port facilities, garbage collection or sewage treatment facilities – usually occurs through high numbers of tourists encountering limited local capacities.
- The **degradation of the natural environment** tends to be more pronounced in rural areas where ecosystems are often fragile and even relatively low visitor

numbers may have negative effects, such as water and air pollution, soil erosion or wildlife disturbance.

- **Imbalances in the local economy** can occur when tourism becomes predominant in certain areas (“touristification”), pushing out traditional stores or professions and leading to rising prices for real estate or everyday consumer goods.
- **Impacts on the social environment** becomes an issue when residents feel psychologically, socially or culturally disturbed by the presence of too many tourists, especially if these tourists behave in an unacceptable way (e.g., by making noise or littering).
- Finally, **tourists** themselves may be negatively affected by the presence of a large number of other visitors in the same area.

The analysis of the 15 case studies and the workshop discussions have shown that unbalanced tourism is a process that evolves uniquely at each destination despite some clear common mega-trends and drivers. International tourism growth is a key driver of unbalanced tourism developments at most destinations. Secondly, the evolution of social media use contributes to overtourism at some specific sites resulting in such sites becoming hotspots without key management organisations in place with rapid and necessary controls. Destination governance was shown to be a decisive factor for the emergence of overtourism. Varying governance levels within a destination can present a challenge and have an impact on the management of tourism.

In terms of impacts, the most visible effects of overtourism include various types of congestion, such as the concentrated number of visitors or vehicles in a limited geographic space, including beaches, parking facilities, queues in front of museums, or ports. The non-visible impacts of unbalanced tourism are more diffuse and include several socio-economic and socio-cultural impacts such as touristification, increased prices and biophysical impacts throughout the year.

Therefore, how destinations experience unbalanced tourism significantly varies and partly relates to the destination type. Nevertheless, many commonalities are observable amongst cities, coasts and islands, rural areas and mountain destinations:

- **Urban destinations** (Florence, Lucerne, Vienna) experience extremely high tourist densities in certain neighbourhoods, but appear to have more flexibility and local alternate tourism attractions and infrastructure available to implement physical dispersion strategies compared to rural destinations.
- **The rural areas** analysed (Plitvice Lakes, Regional Park of Monts d’Ardèche, Cliffs of Moher) demonstrate how regions depend on tourism flows, and that the sudden appearance of large crowds at a few attraction points is not easy to manage. Furthermore, rural areas all seem to be confronted with the contradiction of capturing the economic benefits that tourism may bring, while offering idyllic rural landscapes and unique attractions. This applies particularly to destinations where protected area management goals to conserve ecological integrity do not always easily align with the goals of providing more tourism infrastructure
- **The coastal and island destinations** all show biophysical fragility. This is especially true of beaches, dunes and places of biodiversity value. Collectively, island destinations have limited geographic space and share challenges with respect to further tourism growth. The absence of neighbouring land destinations makes them interesting since any management solution implemented can be set in a very specific scope suitable and adapted to a “closed” destination. As a result, island settings provide advantages in monitoring arrivals from outside, while the local movement and management of crowds remains equally comparable to all other destination types.
- **The mountain destinations** analysed highlight the fragility, both biophysical and socio-cultural, of such areas (Dolomites, Rigi, Bled). The destinations showcase how contemporary visitor masses can easily be channelled even to relatively remotely located places, as more and more visitors seek nature experiences at

“instagrammeable” spots. Similarly to coastal areas, mountain destinations, particularly within protected areas, are suitable for management approaches aiming at stricter regulations and controls.

Indicators to measure overtourism

A large variety of indicators have been proposed in the literature to measure overtourism, or the risk of overtourism. Indicators are widely seen as an important tool to monitor and ultimately prevent or mitigate overtourism. The purpose of developing indicators can be three-fold:

1. to detect risks or “early warning signs” before overtourism actually manifests itself;
2. to manage and counteract impacts that have already occurred;
3. to monitor the effectiveness of mitigation measures.

Overtourism manifests itself through certain impacts that are caused by an unbalanced development of tourism. This may occur either quantitatively through too many tourists or qualitatively, for instance, by tourists behaving inappropriately as perceived by local residents, which adds a subjective component to the issue. The obvious and direct approach to measure overtourism would be to measure its impacts. However, there are two conceptual challenges associated with this method:

- a) Can observed impacts be attributed to tourism?
- b) Negative impacts associated with overtourism typically occur incrementally. Tipping points, where a carrying capacity is exceeded, either do not exist or may be difficult to detect.

Another fundamental weakness of using impact indicators is that they measure negative effects that have already occurred. For this reason, it may be appropriate to also measure driving forces, pressures, and the sensitivity of a destination as a foresighted strategy to counteract overtourism before it manifests. This approach measures the *risk* of overtourism rather than the degree of overtourism itself.

Some authors have proposed concise indicator sets that are to be universally applied while others have pointed out that destinations are too diverse to conceive a “one-size-fits-all” system of indicators. Furthermore, data availability and comparability between destinations are central challenges when striving to measure overtourism. The most frequently proposed indicators in the literature are:

- **Economic importance of tourism** (% of GDP and employment) in a destination.
- **Tourism intensity** (number of overnight tourists in relation to the number of local inhabitants).
- **Tourism density** (number of overnight tourists in relation to the surface of the destination).

The corresponding data, with respect to this list of indicators, is easily available through Eurostat and other sources. The project team has, therefore, mapped these indicators on a European scale. It was decided to compute and depict indicators at NUTS 3 level, where available. These maps were then overlapped with the inventory map of destinations affected by overtourism in order to check the validity of the indicators. Surprisingly, the correlation between the selected indicators alone and the actual occurrence of overtourism was rather weak. There are mainly two possible explanations for this:

- The authors that diagnosed overtourism in a certain destination may have used different criteria or thresholds for overtourism.
- Even the NUTS-3 level may still be too coarse to measure tourism pressure as a predictor for overtourism as it often occurs even below the municipal level, for instance in certain urban neighbourhoods or certain zones of protected areas.

Solution approaches

This report has showcased 15 specific cases across Europe that illustrate how tourism can develop in an unbalanced way in destinations. These 15 cases highlight certain similarities and many differences regarding unbalanced tourism patterns. However, most importantly, they are all cases of good practices and many of the specific initiatives and measures implemented can be applied to other destinations in Europe where tourism may already be, or may become, unbalanced. Although many destinations have implemented a complex and often multidimensional set of solution approaches to overtourism, none represents a case where the issue is “solved for good”.

The solution approaches most frequently applied by the different destinations analysed in this project can be described as follows:

- **Laws, regulations and policies:** Most destinations have implemented some manner of legally binding rules and regulations to address unbalanced tourism development. These include i.e., imposing limits to the construction of new hotels or the numbers of cruise passengers, the regulation of privately rented accommodation as well as imposing capacity limits for heavily visited sites or pollution control measures for cruise ships. Less restrictive policies may create incentives to use public transport instead of an individual automobile.
- Nevertheless, **stakeholder cooperation**, including different interest groups, tourism companies and even the visitors themselves, has been implemented as a precondition to developing appropriate solutions to unbalanced tourism. Participation of residents in policy-making, as well as their consultation were identified as success factors.
- New and expanded **tourism infrastructure**, such as additional parking lots or increased waste collection capacities in the high season are obvious means to accommodate higher visitor numbers in an orderly manner. New infrastructure as well as new tourism offers or simply enhanced information campaigns have also been used to **disperse tourists** to other parts of a destination. Such “de-concentration” strategies and the redirection of visitor streams does not only help to alleviate the burden on areas with “must-see” attractions, but also enable other areas to participate economically.
- **Digital solutions**, particularly the use of big data from mobile technologies and centralised tourism data observatories, seem to be key aspects of successful management of unbalanced tourism as they enable data-driven decision-making. Information provides a common ground for stakeholders of diverging interests and power levels to consider appropriate solutions from their own perspectives. Real-time and up-to-date information provision was highlighted multiple times as solution approaches in the workshops. Nevertheless, there are several challenges to this since datasets need to be purchased from the providers.

However, the systematic monitoring of unbalanced tourism with a key set of indicators is not well advanced among most studied destinations. This contributes to overtourism remaining a subjective phenomenon at some destinations.

Recommendations

Proposed indicator system

An appropriate indicator system for the measurement of overtourism, or the risk of such a development, must fulfil four basic requirements:

1. It must enable the monitoring, prevention and mitigation of overtourism.
2. It must cover the cause-effect relationships leading to unbalanced tourism development, ranging from visitor pressure and actual impacts to the driving forces behind overtourism and characteristics, of a (potentially) affected destination.

3. It must reflect the diversity of individual destinations while also taking into account comparability and replicability as well as the external driving forces behind overtourism, thus combining global with regional and local indicators.
4. It must be feasible, meaning that data availability and the often limited capacities of destination management organisations have to be taken into account.

With this in mind, a **three-tiered indicator system** was developed by the project team:

- Tier 1: Measuring **global trends** that act as driving forces for overtourism. These indicators should be available at global, EU or national level and indicate a *general risk* of overtourism.
- Tier 2: Measuring tourism pressure as well as internal factors (sensitivity) on the **regional level**. This type of indicators can provide insights into whether there is a more *specific risk* of overtourism in a given destination.
- Tier 3: Measuring tourism pressure, actual impacts and internal factors **locally**. A destination – or even site – specific approach is needed to assess the local risk or actual occurrence of overtourism.

Tier 1 indicators are based on mega-trends, or root causes, that are known to have a strong influence on the occurrence of overtourism phenomena around the world. In more detail, the Tier 1 indicators should measure:

- Growth of international tourism in general, with a particular focus on the development of source markets from emerging economies.
- Passenger numbers of low-cost airlines and charter flights. These tend to focus on easily accessible destinations with airports and transport large numbers of tourists in relatively short periods of time.
- Passenger numbers of cruise companies. Even more than charter flights and low-cost airlines, the business model of most cruise companies is geared towards very high volumes of tourists.

The Tier 2 indicators have been derived from the literature and Figure 13 consist of an exposure component (indicators measuring tourism inflows) and a territorial sensitivity component (indicators measuring the regional tourism structures sector). They can also be combined into **bivariate indicators**:

- Importance of tourism for the local or regional economy (% of gross value added (GVA)¹ and % of employment)
- Tourism intensity & density
- Growth in tourist arrivals/nights spent

The Tier 3 indicators (local indicators) are informed by the literature review and the findings of the case studies. They form a “pool” of potential indicators which can be used depending on the destination’s specificities and particular needs. The following key issues need to be taken into account and measured, if possible, in almost every destination affected by overtourism:

- Size of the actual “**tourist**” area in absolute figures and in relation to the overall destination or municipal area. Ideally, tourism density and intensity should then be calculated separately for those highly impacted areas.
- **Seasonality** is a key issue of overtourism. Tourism density and intensity should be measured separately for peak month(s) and the low season.
- **Day visitors** (including cruise ship passengers in coastal or island destinations) are an important driver of overtourism. Therefore, their numbers (in absolute terms and in relation to overnight tourists) should be added when calculating

¹ Eurostat offers GVA and employment data for the NACE sectors G-I and G-J, however, not for the individual sub-sectors. This covers economic activities closely associated with tourism (such as accommodation). Sectors: wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication.

tourism intensity and density. Furthermore, their spatial and temporal visitation patterns as well as their spending in relation to overnight tourists should be measured. However, collecting data on day visitors may be one of the biggest challenges when monitoring overtourism. Using big data instead of, or in addition to, conducting surveys might open up new opportunities.

- The rising share of **private accommodation** offered on platforms such as Airbnb contributes to spreading overtourism into previously unaffected urban neighbourhoods. Their share of the overall accommodation offer and their spatial distribution should therefore be measured.
- The “**sentiments**” of both **residents** and **tourists** as an important impact of overtourism must be taken into account more systematically when managing an affected destination. This can be done either by direct surveys or by using data from online platforms.

Recommendations at EU level

Even though overtourism is largely a regional or local phenomenon that consequently needs to be managed at those levels, external driving forces are better managed, or at least informed about, at EU or national level. In particular, EU institutions could do the following:

- Support destinations potentially affected by overtourism by regularly providing **Tier 1** and particularly **Tier 2 indicators** to help them assess their general risk of unbalanced tourism development.
- Provide guidelines for **multi-level cross-regional cooperation** in order to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism (see following chapter).
- Develop a **common data space for tourism** and fair data sharing.
- **Short-term rentals** (STRs) have been addressed as drivers for overtourism, in particular in urban destinations. The Commission launched the STR initiative, undertaking a public consultation in 2021 to support the development of a framework for STRs as well as to increase transparency and improve the market access for hosts.

Recommendations at national level

The following recommendations are directed at stakeholders in charge of national tourism policies, in particular governments, and national tourism bodies such as industry federations and tourism boards. They may also apply to federal states in countries such as Germany.

- **Multi-level cross-regional cooperation** is necessary to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism. This level of stakeholder cooperation can be difficult and resource-intensive. National or EU guidelines on stakeholder involvement in sustainable tourism development may mitigate this issue.
- National organisations may also provide **country-specific data** for Tier 1 and Tier 2 indicators and inform stakeholders about new trends.
- **Big data solutions** provide accurate monitoring of tourism inflows and hotspots, but are generally expensive and technically complex and DMOs lack capacities or financial resources to implement these systems. As such, national support and provision of these data services can alleviate this gap.
- Where the implementation of **capacity restrictions**, especially at ports and airports, is under the jurisdiction of national governments, care should be taken to consider the needs of regional and local governments and citizen groups.

Recommendations at regional and local levels

The following recommendations are directed at tourism and non-tourism stakeholders in charge of regional and municipal policies, planning and management, in particular

local governments, destination management organisations and local tourism industry associations.

- Destinations need to adopt an **appropriate definition** of overtourism to enable an objective understanding of the phenomenon in their local context.
- Destinations should integrate the risk of overtourism into their **general planning and management framework**.
- Destinations may want to adopt a framework to **oversee overtourism** as a phenomenon beyond classical economic key performance indicators to enable a more data-driven and systematic analysis of the sector in a holistic way.
- In order to achieve this, the **collection and analysis of data** at a relevant scale, frequency and reliability on the economic, social and environmental facets of tourism in a systematic and continuous fashion is recommended.
- Including residents and **stakeholder participation** in policymaking, as well as their consultation (e.g., via surveys) reveals “pain-points” and increases tourism acceptance in the destinations.
- The social dimension needs to be captured to monitor overtourism. This can be done via **resident and visitor surveys**, preferably at the local and regional level.
- **Steering systems** (e.g., awareness campaigns, dynamic pricing and pre-booking) may be used to mitigate the burdens of visitors. This can be done in conjunction with big-data solutions to pin-point tourist hotspots.
- **Visitor management** systems should rely on real-time and up-to-date information provision. They can be exercised in different ways, ranging from crowd monitoring to improving infrastructure in heavily visited areas to **dispersal strategies** by creating additional infrastructure and alternative tourism offers in less visited parts of a destination.
- **De-marketing** may be a solution to discourage certain undesirable tourist groups from visiting a destination.
- Systematic **capacity building** in the context of indicator systems and monitoring is necessary at DMOs to enable the use of comprehensive monitoring systems. In the case of a persisting lack of capacities or low resources, the DMO may wish to implement reduced sets of indicators, focusing on easy-to-collect data.
- Effective planning may have to include various **regulatory provisions** or **taxes** levied on harmful tourist activities. In particular, it is necessary to curtail individual automobile traffic, one of the most noxious sources of negative overtourism impacts, and shift traffic flows more to **public transportation** options.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and objectives of the study

Overall, this study aims to contribute to a sustainable transformation of EU tourism based on the objectives set out by the European Green Deal as well as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. In particular, the assignment will address the overtourism phenomenon which causes imbalances in tourism destinations by analysing the root causes and impacts of overtourism (Task A). Diagnostic models using both quantitative and qualitative indicators will be used to describe the tourism pressure on specific tourism destinations. Based on retrieved best practice solutions (Task B) to mitigate the impacts of overtourism, implementation models will be developed for destinations. These include mitigation and preventive activities to overcome the overtourism phenomenon and lead to balanced and sustainable tourism. To account for the Covid-19 crisis, changes in destination strategies will be considered, not only looking at past tourism hotspots but also at new, emerging overtourism destinations caused by domestic tourism and surging numbers of day trips. Furthermore, the assignment includes the development of an indicator set to measure overtourism at destination level. These outputs will be included in a compendium (Task C) targeted at various stakeholders in destinations affected by overtourism. The compendium categorises, communicates and transfers the existing knowledge on overtourism (see Task A) as well as the assignment findings. Finally, six workshops were organised (Task E) to disseminate the study results on overtourism and foster peer-to-peer learning processes on mitigating strategies between stakeholders of destinations affected by and/or at-risk of overtourism.

Due to the specificities of overtourism and its impacts on destinations tied to geographical, socio-cultural and socio-economic factors, the analysis is structured along five categories of destination types across EU-27 and beyond. These are urban, rural, mountain, coastal, and island destinations, as outlined in the tender specifications.

1.2. The definition of overtourism

Even though overtourism is a very popular research topic and numerous definitions exist that elaborate on the complex concept, it is still a “fuzzy” phenomenon that lacks a universal understanding and definition. When analysing the existing definitions of overtourism put forward by academics, two different approaches can be identified. On the one hand, a qualitative subjective approach can be determined, based on the subjective perception and opinion of residents and tourists. On the other hand, some scholars approach the term by applying a more quantitative objective understanding, which refers to the measurement of the economic, environmental, and partly also socio-cultural pressure of tourism. An example for a qualitative subjective approach is encompassed in the following definition by Milano et al. (2018):

It is described as the excessive growth of visitors leading to overcrowding in areas where residents suffer the consequences of temporary and seasonal tourism peaks, which have caused permanent changes to their lifestyles, denied access to amenities and damaged their general well-being.

Another qualitative subjective definition of overtourism was established by Goodwin (2017):

Overtourism describes destinations where hosts or guests, locals or visitors, feel that there are too many visitors and that the quality of life in the area or the quality of the experience has deteriorated unacceptably. It is the opposite of Responsible Tourism which is about using tourism to make better places to live in and better places to visit. Often both visitors and guests experience the deterioration concurrently and rebel against it. (p. 1)

UNWTO et al. (2018, p. 6) also approaches the phenomenon in a more qualitative and subjective way, describing overtourism as “the impact of tourism on a destination, or

parts thereof, that excessively influences perceived quality of life of citizens and/or quality of visitors experiences in a negative way”.

All three definitions focus on the perspective of destination residents, and the latter two also focus on the perception of tourists. Additionally, Goodwin (2017) contrasts the term with the concept of responsible tourism. However, these subjective and qualitative approaches do not include concrete factors that provide information on how the perceptions of these stakeholders have been influenced (Bauer et al., 2020), making it difficult to derive quantifiable indicators based on these definitions. The subjective perspective of people as an indicator for overtourism naturally leads to difficulties in defining the point at which a destination is actually affected by overtourism. Crowding, for example, can actually enhance the tourist experience up to a certain point. Weber et al. (2017) referred to the different forms of crowding perception in their definition:

(...) every country seems to have so called tourism hot spots with many visitors coming to these sights or places during peak times. Sometimes certain effects of crowding are considered as a positive sign and make visitors conclude that the destination or attraction is worth visiting. Nevertheless, when carrying capacities of the tourism system are reached, too many visitors can lead to serious problems for the destination. This phenomenon seems to have increased in the last years and is sometimes referred to as “overtourism”. (p.198)

Nevertheless, it remains unclear how these problems ultimately manifest themselves at destination level. The definition of Peeters et al. (2018, p. 22), an example of a more quantitative approach, further illustrates this aspect and defines overtourism as **“the situation in which the impact of tourism, at certain times and in certain locations, exceeds physical, ecological, social, economic, psychological, and/or political capacity thresholds”**. This definition not only refers to the different dimensions of tourism impacts, but also clarifies the temporal and spatial limitation of overtourism. Nevertheless, it has also been criticised in the context of the concept of carrying capacity, as regions or cities tend to be seen as static, although they are complex and dynamic systems with a high potential of adaptation (Bauer et al., 2020).

Thus, despite the presence of several attempts and the current popularity in academia, no universal definition has been established yet. Instead, “the term actually can be considered “fuzzy” in that it is ill-defined, lacks clarity, and is highly difficult to operationalize.” (Koens et al., 2018, p. 2).

Based on the review of overtourism definitions, the definition of Peeters et al. (2018) is considered as the most appropriate and used as the basis for further research and analyses in this study.

1.3. Concepts related to overtourism

Apart from overtourism, a variety of other terms related to, or associated with, overtourism have appeared in academic literature and in the media. Since these terms reflect in part different, yet related, concepts, it is important to distinguish each individually.

1.3.1. Mass tourism

Although mass tourism and overtourism are both associated with large numbers of tourists there are some substantial differences between these two concepts. Increasing numbers are one of the root causes of overtourism, but they do not necessarily lead to overtourism (R. W. Butler, 2020). While some destinations are able to cope with large numbers of tourists, other destinations with lower tourism intensity and density are already experiencing strong negative impacts. For this reason, unlike mass tourism, overtourism is not exclusively associated with high numbers of tourists, and is “better understood in relative, rather than absolute, terms”. (R. W. Butler, 2020, p. 27).

Nevertheless, the criticism of mass tourism was quite similar to what is now called overtourism. It first appeared in the 1970s in the German publication *Die Landschaftsfresser* by Krippendorf (1975) and gained prominence in the 1980s. It was a reaction to the massive tourist development of the Alps (and to a certain extent of the Mediterranean coasts) at that time, and was particularly pronounced in Switzerland, Austria and Germany. This criticism focused on the massive tourism-induced construction boom with its associated destruction of natural or rural landscapes, traffic flows, noise and pollution. In addition to the ecological impacts, the socio-cultural effects of mass tourism on formerly traditional rural societies were also discussed ("touristification" of Alpine villages originally marked by small-scale agriculture; former fishing villages in the Mediterranean) as well as a fundamental criticism of the commercialisation of travel (Krippendorf, J. 1986).

However, one difference between overtourism and the criticism of mass tourism is that the areas affected were mostly mountain and coastal destinations (including islands) and not urban destinations. It is also noteworthy that this discussion remained largely within the German-speaking world, with the exception of Krippendorf, whose publications were translated into English and reached a wider audience.

1.3.2. Carrying Capacity

The concept of overtourism is closely linked to the carrying capacity of a destination (Knezevic et al., 2018). In order to avoid overtourism, the carrying capacity of the local tourism system must be well known (Weber et al., 2017). The UNWTO defined the term as **"the maximum number of people that may visit a tourist destination at the same time, without causing destruction of the physical, economic, and socio-cultural environment and an unacceptable decrease in the quality of visitors' satisfaction"** (WTO 1983 in UNWTO *et al.*, 2018, p.14).

The concept of carrying capacity was developed much earlier than the term overtourism and can be seen as "a precursor to current concerns with overtourism, which emphasises that the number of tourists, and their behaviour can overwhelm the places that they visit, damaging both the tourism resources and the lifestyles of those living in destination areas." (Wall, 2020, p. 1). Unlike overtourism, the term was introduced in North America in the context of outdoor recreation management and thus focussed primarily on natural areas with no direct reference to tourism (Wall, 2020). Today, the term is increasingly used in relation to urban destinations. Thus, "the concern with and application of carrying capacity has migrated across continents, from natural to urban settings, and has re-emerged as 'overtourism'" (Wall, 2020, p. 2). However, there are also difficulties in applying the concept in urban settings due to their high complexity (Nilsson, 2020).

Some key questions of the concept of carrying capacity remain, such as how and when to set limits to tourism, as well as finding appropriate management strategies to successfully balance tourism supply and demand. In parallel, there are also new issues and changes that are influencing the tourism industry. Examples are the increasing pressure from cruise ships and the emergence of higher capacity accommodation facilities (Wall, 2020). Peeters et al. (2018, p. 26) summarise that "rapid tourism growth is provoking many discussions on destinations' carrying capacity and their capacity to handle the overwhelming inflow of visitors versus maintaining a balance with residents' numbers." Consequently, carrying capacity is a very topical concept, directly related to the phenomenon of overtourism and its mitigation and prevention.

In their report, Peeters et al. (2018, p. 26) cite the revisited carrying capacity concept presented by Mowforth & Munt (2003, p. 224) which includes five types of carrying capacity and integrates the role of local people:

Ecological-environmental capacity: the level of tourist development or recreational activity beyond which the environment (as previously experienced) is degraded or compromised.

Physical-facility capacity: the level of tourist development or recreational activity beyond which facilities are saturated, or physical deterioration of the environment occurs through overuse by tourists or inadequate infrastructural network.

Social-perceptual capacity: the level reached when groups of residents of an area no longer want tourists because they are destroying the environment, damaging the local culture or crowding residents out of local activities.

Economic carrying capacity: the ability to absorb tourist functions without squeezing out desirable activities. This concept assumes that any limit to capacity can be overcome at a cost – ecological, social, cultural or even political.

Psychological capacity: the individual ability to cope with overcrowding. This capacity is exceeded when a resident and/or tourist is no longer comfortable in the destination area for reasons that may include residents' perceived needs to adapt their habits due to the overwhelming presence of tourists and/or perceived negative attitudes of the locals or other tourists, crowding of the area (traffic jams) or deterioration of the physical environment.

Furthermore, the concept of carrying capacity can be approached similarly to overtourism by using "objective quantitative data on acceptable carrying capacity limits" as well as "subjective qualitative data based on local and tourist perceptions or value judgments on acceptable carrying capacity limits" (Knezevic et al., 2018, p. 24). Social carrying capacity is particularly difficult to measure because it is linked to the psychological characteristics of the tourists or residents of the destination (Weber et al., 2017). At the same time, a balanced socio-psychological perspective is of great importance, as low tolerance towards tourists can negatively affect the visitors' experiences and lead to dissatisfaction. Consequently, managing the social capacity contributes positively to the tourist experience (Weber et al., 2017).

1.3.3. Limits of Acceptable Change (LAC)

As mentioned earlier, the concept of ecological carrying capacity in relation to recreational use was first introduced in the context of protected area management. The original hope was to identify a "magic" number that would allow park managers to know exactly how many visitors could be admitted to a fragile area without degrading its ecosystems. However, the concept of ecological carrying capacity was met with criticism as early as the 1980s. Critics argued along three lines:

- Impacts caused by visitors depend not only on their numbers, but also on their behaviour, spatial and temporal/seasonal distribution, which in turn could be influenced by visitor management.
- It would be extremely difficult to determine thresholds beyond which carrying capacity would be exceeded, unless there are clear tipping points (e.g., oxygen depletion in bodies of water as a consequence of pollution caused by visitors). In reality, however, impacts often occur incrementally making it arbitrary to decide at which point carrying capacity is exceeded.
- The decision whether and to what extent to prevent environmental degradation is largely based on social values rather than on clear scientific facts.

As a consequence, an approach known as Limits of Acceptable Change (LAC) was already conceived in the 1980s (Stankey et al., 1985). LAC is a value-based, iterative approach based primarily on the formulation of conservation goals, which often represent a compromise between the level of access and recreation that should be allowed in a protected area and the ecological quality of its natural resource base, including its biodiversity. The LAC concept still allows for the setting of specific targets that can be measured by quantitative indicators (e.g. population numbers of certain wildlife species), but it would not necessarily set a fixed number of visitors to achieve the defined target. Rather, it would identify and perhaps test several potential management approaches (e.g. allowing access only with trained guides or a zoning concept) that might be suitable to achieve it.

1.3.4. (Over-)Crowding

Rapidly growing visitor numbers have resulted in overcrowding at destination level, which has been increasingly reported in the media, leading to the emergence of the term overtourism (Weber, 2017). However, overcrowding and overtourism are not to be considered synonymous. Instead, excessive crowding can rather be understood as an aspect of overtourism (Ebejer, 2020). Peeters et al. (2018) contextualise the term crowding with their research on overtourism and define it as follows:

Crowding generally refers to a psychological response to density, that is, to feelings of having a lack of privacy, or unwanted interactions (Crothers et al., 1993; Gove & Hughes, 1980; Gray, 2001). Crowding may be associated with over-population as an excess of people in an area, which places pressure on resources or has an impact on broader economic or social goals (Johnston et al., 2005). For instance, "the problems associated with overcrowding can vary, from alienated local residents to overloaded infrastructure. The issues can affect both established and emerging destinations of all kinds. Countries, regions, cities, and individual sites, such as parks, beaches, and museums, may all be affected" (McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017). (p.25)

Furthermore, the concept of crowding has been applied primarily in outdoor recreation studies, while it initially remained a rather neglected topic in cities (Popp, 2012). In terms of outdoor recreation, it was originally developed in the 1980s and related almost exclusively to tourists (or recreationists) visiting natural areas, often located in the areas of North America which typically have no local residents. In this context, visitors are both the causers of crowding and are affected by it. Again, crowding is not just a matter of numbers or density, it is exacerbated by undesirable behaviour (e.g., making noise, littering). As outlined above, crowding is very subjective. It depends on visitors' expectations (e.g. did they expect solitude in a wilderness, or to meet many other people in a picnic area near a car park?). Thus, a sense of crowding can be expected to occur at lower visitor numbers or densities in natural areas, as opposed to in urban areas. There are also strong indications that the perceptions of crowding are also culturally determined. In any case, crowding in rural areas can be seen as a loss of quality of the outdoor recreation or tourism experience. Therefore, protected area managers are keen to monitor and avoid crowding where possible. Monitoring has often been done through visitor surveys measuring their level of satisfaction with the presence of other visitors. Management measures also include zoning (concentration of visitors in certain areas while providing for lower densities in other areas), the presence of different trail systems, etc.

Again, "high tourist densities are not negative *per se*" (Popp, 2012, p. 2), which is why a further differentiation between positive crowding and negative crowding can be made. In conclusion, crowding and its perception are a very complex concept and many variables that influence that perception have been discussed in the literature. For example, for the case of Florence, Popp (2012, 20) identifies "expectations regarding density of use, norms, tourist types and behaviour, length of stay, tourist experience and secondary impacts" as relevant variables contributing to negative or positive crowding. Secondary impacts in this context include the degree of touristification of urban settings and, in case of more rural settings, the degree of environmental degradation.

1.4. Types of destination

Even though overtourism is mainly discussed in academic literature in the context of urban crowding, scholars agree that it is not only a relevant and applicable concept for cities, but also for other destination types such as rural areas (R. W. Butler, 2019; Koens et al., 2018; Postma & Schmuecker, 2017). Peeters et al. (2018, p. 24) also summarise as one of their key findings: "Overtourism is often associated with cities and urban tourism, but is also a common phenomenon in rural, coasts and islands' settings, and at natural and cultural heritage sites and large attractions." Consequently, this report

distinguishes between five different destination types when analysing the underlying root causes, impacts as well as possible solutions for overtourism:

- Urban destinations
- Island destinations
- Coastal destinations
- Rural destinations
- Mountain destinations

Nevertheless, the designation of the type of destination is not always clear-cut (Peeters et al., 2018). Instead, in some cases more than one type may apply. Therefore, in the following analysis, destinations are assigned to more than one category where appropriate. In addition, special attention is paid to protected areas and designated heritage sites, as these are attractive tourist destinations, but at the same time particularly fragile and vulnerable to (over)tourism (Peeters et al., 2018).

In addition, it must be emphasised that there is no “one-size-fits-it-all” solution for dealing with the phenomenon of overtourism (Koens et al., 2018; Milano, Cheer, et al., 2019a; Weber, 2017). Consequently, even when differentiating between geographical settings and types of destinations, the specific conditions of a destination need to be taken into account. Nevertheless, some overarching commonalities can be identified that apply to the same types of destinations. Thus, with a certain generalisation, conclusions can be drawn about several destinations of the same type that have the same specific features. In the following, the special features and conditions of the five destination types are briefly outlined.

1.4.1. Urban destinations

There are five basic aspects of tourism in cities that distinguish them from other types of destinations:

- Cities concentrate a multitude of tourist attractions in a relatively small area.
- These attractions are diverse and thus attract different types of tourists.
- Most urban facilities have not been primarily intended for tourists and this leads to a mutual interaction between different types of urban users (tourists, residents, or workers).
- Different types of economic activities take place in cities and tourism is only one among many.
- Cities are significant regional centres and as such they have a well-developed infrastructure, not only regarding transportation, but also regarding services (e.g. restaurants, cafes, bars, or shops) and accommodation (hotels, pensions, or hostels.). (Dumbrovská & Fialová, 2014, p. 7)

Consequently, the analysis of overtourism in an urban context has to take into account a possibly competing use of infrastructure by tourists and residents. Rural areas often benefit from the additional demand by tourists, as local demand alone is often insufficient to ensure a supply of leisure-related activities (Kagermeier & Erdmenger, 2020, p. 533). In urban areas, on the other hand, the demand of residents alone already leads to a broad offer. In addition, cities often rely on several economic activities. As a result, the tourism sector has less of an influence at the regional level and citizens perceive their economy as less dependent on and less benefiting from tourism (Kagermeier and Erdmenger, 2020; Żemła, 2020).

Cities attract several types of visitors with different interests and motivations for travelling. For example, the German capital Berlin is mainly visited by international and national visitors for its cultural and artistic offerings, but its image, famous night life and a variety of events also attract tourists every year (visitBerlin, 2020). Besides domestic and international leisure tourists, business tourists and people visiting friends and relatives (VFR) also travel to urban spaces (Koens, Postma and Papp, 2018).

Furthermore, it is not only the number of tourist arrivals that has grown during the past years². Urban spaces have also become increasingly popular as places to live and work, resulting in rising numbers of residents and commuters. Consequently, these groups use urban facilities in parallel with the growing number of city tourists (Koens et al., 2018). As many of the activities on offer can be undertaken at any time of year, cities are generally less affected by seasonality, potentially also leading to overcrowding throughout the year. Nevertheless, in some cities overcrowding is more likely to occur in the spring months, while in the summer months many residents are on vacation, leaving more space for tourists (Koens et al., 2018). To counteract seasonality, several destinations, including urban destinations, have attempted to spread tourist arrivals over time, sometimes resulting in year-round dispersion of overcrowding (Koens et al., 2018). Nevertheless, overtourism is mostly limited to certain parts of the city or to certain times, such as during events (Frey, 2021; Koens et al., 2018).

1.4.2. Rural destinations

In rural destinations, the impacts of overtourism can be as severe as in urban destinations (R. W. Butler, 2019), although there are some fundamental differences in terms of (over)tourism development. As mentioned above, some areas are able to cope with a high number of tourist arrivals, while in other destinations even a small increase in tourist numbers can cause large negative impacts. This is especially the case in newly developing tourist areas and in particularly fragile destinations, such as protected areas. Thus, even if the number of tourists is often lower in absolute terms than in urban destinations, they can also lead to negative impacts in a rural context, especially if they have increased over a short period of time (Koens et al., 2018, Butler, 2019, 2020).

In contrast to urban areas, rural areas are more often confronted with seasonality (R. W. Butler, 2019). This can be particularly problematic in villages and smaller towns, as residents are typically more accustomed to a "tranquil and slow pace of life" (R. W. Butler, 2019, p. 199). Consequently, increasing and temporally concentrated visitor numbers may be perceived differently, including feelings of disturbance or even threat (R. W. Butler, 2019).

In addition, the capacity of local infrastructure, including transport services and historic towns and small village centres, is especially limited in rural destinations. Thus, if the local infrastructure is not yet adapted to a rapid increase in visitor numbers, there may be a feeling that residents' spaces are "taken over" by tourists" (R. W. Butler, 2019, p. 199). At the same time, the additional demand may also imply positive impacts, such as the development and expansion of infrastructure and services that also benefit the local population (R. W. Butler, 2019). As in all other destination types, the perception of tourism depends on the behaviour of tourists. Inappropriate behaviour by tourists is associated with negative impacts on the quality of life of the local population and is another concern expressed by residents in rural areas (Butler, 2020). In summary, "tourism and particularly overtourism often create new problems not experienced before, because tourism represents a very different situation and experience to the norm for many residents of rural areas." (R. W. Butler, 2019, p. 209).

1.4.3. Coastal destinations

Regarding the impacts of tourism in coastal areas, spatial occupancy by tourism as well as environmental and social impacts are mentioned in particular (E. Navarro Jurado et al., 2012; Enrique Navarro Jurado et al., 2013). Beaches are an important tourism attraction worldwide. At the same time, coastal areas are subject to fragile natural cycles that make them particularly vulnerable to (over)tourism (E. Navarro Jurado et al., 2012). As Navarro Jurado et al. (2012) illustrated with the example of the Costa del Sol,

² In this context, it is referred to the tourism development until the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus in Europe at beginnings of 2019.

beaches often need to be re-nourished because their natural cycles have been compromised by the massive artificialisation of the area due to tourism. In addition, European coastal areas are often affected by a high seasonality with peak periods in the summer months, which leads to a temporal and spatial concentration of tourism pressure on coasts.

In addition to the typical "beach and sun holiday" tourists, coastal destinations are increasingly visited by cruise passengers. Cruise itineraries start and end at coastal destination and the programme of cruise travels often consists of several day trips. Especially in the latter case, the associated tourism activities are concentrated in sensitive coastal regions and ports (Carić & Mackelworth, 2014).

1.4.4. Island destinations

As island destinations are de facto also coastal destinations, the previously mentioned specificities of coastal destinations also apply to them. However, due to their unique characteristics, islands are particularly prone to experience overtourism (Sarantakou & Terkenli, 2019). Spilanis et al. (2011, p. 34) identified the following four main characteristics that define islands in this regard:

- **Small size:** More often than not, islands are small both in terms of areal size and population compared to the mainland. Their small population results in a limited internal market and constrained local demand for commodities and services, as well as limited workforce. Concurrently, a small surface area means that islands tend to have very limited -if any- land resources for extensive agriculture, whilst they also regularly lack key natural resources, including adequate water supplies, fossil fuels but also non-fuel minerals. In cases where raw materials may have been available in the past, these have now often been exhausted. The environmental balance of islands is frequently endangered and this challenge, in turn, makes environmental management an absolute necessity.
- **Remoteness and isolation** result in high transportation, installation and operating costs for companies, households and the state. There is usually a high dependence on foreign exchange earnings as well as imports, leading to high leakage rates (Peeters et al., 2018).
- **Special experiential identity:** The particularities of the insular space affect perceptions, behaviours and actions. Islands are "objects of the mind" in addition to being physical objects and they are viewed in different ways by visitors – tourists and mainlanders – compared to the long-term local inhabitants. While for the visitor, islands can be places to "escape" from everyday life and live "utopias", local inhabitants may have highly different views.
- **Particularly rich and vulnerable natural and cultural environment:** Due to their small size and their remoteness, many islands have witnessed the evolution of unique endemic species and as a result have valuable terrestrial and marine ecosystems. In addition, due to their strategic location on sea routes, many islands have a rich historical past, highlighted today by monuments, settlements and landscapes; many of them have been classified as national, European, or even World Heritage Sites. This unique natural and cultural capital has so far been used mainly for tourism development – and in the case of most Mediterranean islands – for mass tourism.

1.4.5. Mountain destinations

Brebbia and Pineda (2006) examined Alpine tourism trends and summarised their impacts under three categories. The first category is called "effects of overuse" and stands for the use of land and other natural resources as well as the damage to sensitive high-altitude ecosystems by tourism and related activities. As a second category, the authors name "structural problems" (p. 247) that are directly related to the tourism offer and its character. Examples include a lack of qualitative amenities, a focus on "fair weather tourism" in summer and ski tourism in winter, and a temporal and spatial concentration

of overnights stays. Thirdly, the authors outline a “loss of functions that lie beyond business economics” and mention a general change in the Alpine landscape in this context. In general, summer and winter outdoor leisure activities put pressure on natural ecosystems including impacts such as soil erosion, habitat and biodiversity loss, and noise pollution (Willibald et al., 2019). Skiing is one of the most popular activities in the winter season of mountain destinations. As a result, particularly popular ski resorts can be affected temporally by overtourism. Pikkemaat et al. (2020) investigated the impact of overcrowding on skiers’ experience and concluded that overcrowding at strategic locations of ski resorts (e.g., valley stations, slopes and catering facilities) contributes to an increased overall perception of crowding and negatively affects visitor satisfaction. As a consequence, the authors stressed the importance of improved visitor management in ski resorts in order to reduce site-specific overcrowding effects.

At the same time, while some popular alpine ski destinations experience overtourism, particularly remote valleys partly suffer from a lack or decline of economic activities, as outlined by Barker (1982) already several decades ago.

1.5. Overtourism and Covid-19

Since the start of its outbreak at the beginning of 2020, the Covid-19 virus has severely affected the entire tourism sector. During the preparation of this report, several countries worldwide had still issued travel restrictions and warnings. As a result, international tourism arrivals have declined in every tourism destination. At the start of 2021, the decline of tourist arrivals across Europe was in the order of 85% according to UNWTO (2021).

Due to worldwide travel restrictions and warnings, domestic tourism, including day trips to the nearer surroundings, have become increasingly popular. As a result, some, partly new, destinations were reported by the media to be confronted with overtourism. These developments indicate a relocation of the problem to other areas, some of which have already been popular tourist destinations, but rarely experienced such a rapid increase or accumulation of visitor numbers before. For instance, media reported that in several German Baltic and North Sea destinations as well as in the Bavarian Alps there had been an exceedance of the local capacities and overcrowding during the summer of 2020.

The report *Behavioural changes in tourism in times of Covid-19*, published by the European Union in 2020, predicted several changes concerning tourist behaviour and the choice of destinations due to the Coronavirus crisis. The forecasts mostly proved to be true during the summer holidays of 2020, and over the following months. The authors concluded that there was still a willingness to travel, nonetheless the most important criteria for the selection of the destination were low tourist densities and the health and sanitary conditions in the destination (Marques Santos et al., 2020, p. 23), indicating a higher sensitivity and need for safety during travelling. In addition, a preference for destinations with an offer of outdoor activities and natural landscapes, “away from big cities” (Marques Santos et al., 2020, p. 23), was predicted. The study also indicated that the duration of the holiday would be shorter or divided into several small trips as well as having a lower holiday budget.

Concerning post-Covid travel behaviour, studies point towards two different possible developments. On the one hand, a higher sensitivity and demand for sustainable tourism and a decreased interest in mass tourism has been recorded. For instance, according to a study conducted for the German source market, 15% of the German-speaking population showed a higher interest in sustainable tourism and 21% the urge to travel away from mass tourism (Sonntag, 2020, p. 17). On the other hand, there is evidence of a return to the “old normal” after overcoming the crisis, as another survey undertaken for the German market indicates (Bayerisches Zentrum für Tourismus e.V, 2021). According to this survey, 45% of the respondents who did not travel sustainably before the

Covid-19 outbreak also do not intend to change their behaviour in the future (Bayerisches Zentrum für Tourismus e.V, 2021, p. 38). In either case, overtourism continues to be an important field of research in order to promote a more sustainable tourism development scenario in the future. Moreover, due to an expected higher sensitivity to crowding and heightened health-related security concerns by tourists as well as residents (Koh, 2020; Wen et al., 2020), it is likely that the discourse on overtourism will gain even more relevance in the future.

1.6. EU policy framework for sustainable tourism

The European Commission introduced the [Transition Pathway for Tourism](#)³ initiative in February 2022, as part of the New Industrial Strategy (COM(2021) 350 final). The goal of the Transition Pathway for Tourism initiative is to promote the green and digital transition of the EU tourism ecosystem and build its resilience to future shocks. The Covid-19 pandemic and inevitable climate change impacts highlight the urgency to accelerate this transformation and consequently improve the resilience of the tourism ecosystem. These needs are targeted in the Transition Pathway for Tourism with concrete actions for all tourism stakeholders that were defined in a co-creation process. The Transition Pathway for Tourism includes 70 actions in 27 topic areas. The actions of the initiative can be differentiated into five key areas.

- **Regulation and public governance:** Actions in this theme include regulatory support, such as of short-term rentals, improved accessibility of multimodal transport, improved statistical bases, as well as the development of tourism strategies and the establishment of collaborative governance models.
- **Green transition:** This area includes, among others, actions to improve the circularity of tourism services and the sustainability of transport providers, green certification schemes for tourism providers, as well as pilots and research and innovation transfer projects.
- **Digital transition:** Key actions include support in the uptake of digital tools among tourism stakeholders, improved data sharing and data management, and support for research and innovation (such as for digitised cultural heritage).
- **Skills and resilience:** Key actions are part of the Pact on Skills for tourism, an engagement model which supports the tourism workforce, improves fairness and equality in tourism jobs, information sharing on cross-border traveling in exceptional circumstances, and the facilitation of seamless cross-border traveling.
- **Support for tourism actors** includes awareness raising on sustainability and digitalisation, capacity building for SMEs, best practice collection on the development of tourism strategies, as well as improved visibility of funding, and the establishment of a collaborative platform for tourism stakeholders.

The Commission has started the implementation phase of the transition pathway by gathering concrete commitments and pledges from tourism stakeholders. In June 2022, the Commission [published the results](#) taking stock of the first tranche of collected commitments and pledges as well as [a synthesis report on the published pledges](#).

The [European Green Deal](#) provides the overall framework of the green transition to climate neutrality by 2050 and the decoupling of economic growth from resource use. As part of the European Green Deal, the EU has launched policy frameworks promoting this transition among sectors, and across society. The implementation of the European Green Deal will be achieved through a number of strategies and action plans. Notably, the [Fit for 55](#) package includes a set of legislative proposals to contribute to cutting greenhouse gas emissions by 55% below 1990 levels by 2030. The package contains proposed updates to EU climate, energy and transport legislation. Key aspects relevant to the tourism sector include, for example, the extension of the EU emission trading

³ Please see: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_850

system (EU ETS) to include maritime transport, energy taxation, the promotion of sustainable aviation fuels, and increased energy efficiency targets.

Some strategies developed to achieve the European Green Deal targets are, in particular, relevant in advancing green transition of the tourism ecosystem:

The [Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy](#) (COM(2020) 789 final) provides the overall policy framework for the shift to sustainable transport solutions and is fundamental for tourism. It includes 82 initiatives to promote resilience of the sector, improve innovation and digitalisation, and promote the environmental sustainability of mobility solutions. In the context of the tourism sector, the improvement of multimodal ticketing, zero-emission ports and airports, as well as the uptake of zero-emission vehicles are especially relevant.

The EU [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) (COM(2020) 380 final) is a core part of the European Green Deal. It seeks to promote resilience in light of climate change impacts, forest fires, food insecurity, and disease outbreaks. With nature-based tourism at the core of destinations' attractiveness, particularly in island, mountain, rural, and coastal destinations, this strategy is highly relevant in the context of shifting to more sustainable tourism modes. The strategy seeks to enlarge existing Natura 2000 areas, launch an EU nature restoration plan, as well as to introduce dedicated biodiversity funding and strengthened governance frameworks.

The [Long-term Vision for Rural Areas](#) seeks to promote stronger, more connected, resilient, and prosperous rural areas by 2040. While the demand for nature-based, greener and slow tourism is growing, sustainable tourism has a great potential in offering not only growth and jobs, but also in valorising natural and cultural resources in rural areas. Part of this vision is the promotion of inclusive governance approaches in rural areas, and the introduction of innovative solutions in service provision and digitalisation. Enhanced connectivity, via the promotion of public transportation and improved digitalisation are essential aspects of the vision. Furthermore, the vision promotes overall resilience with respect to economic crises, climate change, and natural hazards. Economic diversification, such as by improving the value of agricultural and agri-food activities, is a key step to enhance rural prosperity. Therefore, a part of the vision is also the Rural Pact, a cooperative framework for rural stakeholders to help fulfil the goals of the vision.

The [new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future](#) (COM(2021) 240 final) seeks to provide policy coherence across the economic sectors of the blue economy, where tourism is an important part. As such, it is particularly relevant for tourism in island and coastal destinations, as the protection of biodiversity and natural heritage, as well as the development of green infrastructure, is at the core of this policy.

2. Task A: Analysis and mapping of the root causes and impacts of overtourism at destination level

2.1. Methodological approach

In order to provide an overall and detailed analysis and mapping of the current state of overtourism at destination level, Task A was divided into four sub-tasks:

The first working step of **Task A.1** provided an introduction to the phenomenon of overtourism, based on an analysis of the recent publications on the subject matter (see introduction sections 1.1 to 1.5). The second part (chapters 1.4 to 1.5) of Task A.1 consisted of the identification and categorisation of destinations facing overtourism prior and due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The analysis of the first inventory was based on a content analysis of recently published reports, scientific articles and case studies highlighting European destinations which have been affected or are at risk of being affected by overtourism. However, it must be stressed that due to the lack of a universal definition of overtourism and the subjectivity of the term, it is partly difficult to assess if a destination is actually beyond its carrying capacity, or if it is rather subjectively perceived as experiencing overtourism. For this reason, the destinations listed in the following inventory are to be considered as destinations *potentially* affected by overtourism. The inventory provides an overview of the state of research and publications on the phenomenon in Europe (state: end of April 2021). The destinations of this inventory were visualised in the form of one overall, and five destination type-specific, maps (see Task A.4).

The methodology of the second inventory of destinations potentially affected by overtourism due to the Covid-19 crisis follows the same procedures as with the first inventory. However, due to the novelty of this issue and since few scientific articles had been published on the implications of the Covid-19 on overtourism at the time of analysis, mostly "grey" literature (newspaper articles, blog articles etc.,) sources were used. In this context it must be underlined that the rise of tourism pressure during the Covid-19 crisis was primarily reported at regional level in local newspaper articles. Consequently, it is difficult to cover all European countries and cases of overtourism during the Covid-19 crisis. Instead, this second inventory must be seen as an exemplary list of destinations which were reported by the media as being "overcrowded" or "overrun". The results of this second part of Task A.1 are presented in two Excel lists in the appendix.

Task A.2 investigates the causes and impacts of overtourism. In the first step of Task A.2, the underlying root causes and recent drivers of overtourism were identified and analysed in a literature review of published reports, scientific articles and case studies. The project team then categorised the identified causes of overtourism according to different aspects that relate to their type (general trends, tourism-specific developments, more recent trends as well as sudden, unpredictable events) and their measurability (quantitative or qualitative). As a result, the project team populated an Excel grid detailing the specificities and characteristics of the causes of overtourism. The Excel grid is presented in the appendix.

The second step of Task A.2 comprises of the identification, analysis and categorisation of the impacts of overtourism. These impacts were grouped by dimension: physical-infrastructure, environmental, socio-cultural and socio-economic. The identified impacts are mostly negative, but also include some positive effects. In this step, the project team also differentiated between the qualitative, often subjective, and the quantitative impacts identified, their permanence (permanent or temporal) and the main stakeholders affected. Similarly to the analysis of the root causes of overtourism described above, the project team created an Excel grid specifying the types of impacts caused by overtourism (see appendix).

The first part of **Task A.3** corresponds to the measurement of key issues, characteristics, root causes and impacts of overtourism that should be monitored (based on Task A.1 and A.2). Following this, within the framework of a literature analysis, the existing measurement approaches and indicator systems were analysed and categorised. The identification of strengths, weaknesses and data gaps of the existing indicator systems led to the creation of an inventory and categorisation of suggested overtourism indicators, as well as the formulation of recommendations and the next research steps.

Task A.4 consists of the mapping of EU destinations (potentially or at risk of being) affected by overtourism, as identified in the inventory of destinations under Task A.1. In addition, the main indicators identified in Task A.3 were mapped at NUTS3 level in a first scoping of the available indicators in order to develop a map of (over)tourism at regional level. This allowed for an assessment of territorial patterns and identification of individual regions as well as more general types of regions which are particularly or potentially affected by overtourism.

2.2. Inventories of destinations facing overtourism

2.2.1. Inventory 1: destinations affected by overtourism prior to the pandemic

The inventory of destinations facing overtourism prior to the outbreak of Covid-19 consists of a total of 144 destinations and provides an overview of the current state of research on the phenomenon.

After identifying the destinations, three major categories were applied:

- Type of destination.
- Protected areas and UNESCO World Heritage Sites located in the destination.
- Spatial level on which overtourism has been diagnosed.

2.2.1.1. Types of destinations identified

As mentioned in the introduction and stated by Peeters et al. (2018), the designation of the type of destination is not always unambiguous. Instead, in some destinations more than one type can apply. Thus, some destinations were assigned to several categories in the inventory. This is for example the case for Palma, Majorca (Spain), which is primarily an urban and coastal destination, but is also located on an island.

Figure 1: Type of destinations (potentially) affected by overtourism prior to the Covid-19 outbreak (Inventory 1)

Source: Project team, 2021

As Figure 1 demonstrates, the clear majority are urban destinations with 78 cases. The second most prevalent type of destination are coastal destinations (64), followed by rural (46 cases), mountain destinations (21 cases), and finally island destinations (20). The individual destinations are mapped in detail in Appendix 1. This reflects one of the

key findings of Peeters et al. (2018), namely the association of overtourism primarily with cities and urban tourism.

At the same time, it highlights a certain underrepresentation of other destination types, particularly of mountainous and island destinations. The reasons for this underrepresentation are not clear. It may be that islands and mountains are less easily accessible than urban areas. Also, as a social phenomenon, overtourism is closely linked to the encountering of tourists and residents.

Another reason might be that non-urban destinations have rather been analysed under other terms related to the concept of overtourism, such as carrying capacity and crowding, or that excessive mass tourism along coasts and in mountains were in the spotlight of academia and the media at an earlier stage (see Chapter 1.3), whereas overtourism in urban destinations is a more recent phenomenon. Thus, the current scientific as well as media coverage of overtourism in urban areas might represent a distorted picture of the situation at hand.

2.2.1.2. Protected areas and heritage sites located in the identified destinations

Due to their fragility and specific management, special attention was given to whether formally proclaimed protected areas or UNESCO World Heritage sites are part of the listed destinations. 75 destinations located (partly) in protected areas were identified, meaning that in more than every second listed destination at least some kind of protected area can be found, such as for example protected landscapes, nature reserves or national parks. Moreover, heritage sites designated by UNESCO are located in more than half (82) of the listed destinations potentially facing overtourism.

This finding underlines the fact that heritage sites as well as protected areas represent major attractions for the tourism sector. While some case studies directly investigated the impacts of the existence of a national park or a heritage site on the increase in overtourism (e.g., Seraphin et al., 2021), others did not mention it at all. Thus, without a more differentiated view of the individual destination, it is difficult to deduce, whether the location of protected areas and particularly UNESCO heritage sites in a destination can be seen as one of the main drivers for (over)tourism. Nevertheless, it stresses the before mentioned ambivalent relationship between tourism and heritage: Being particularly vulnerable to external influences, the impacts of overtourism are potentially severe for these destinations. Consequently, the impacts of overtourism as well as appropriate prevention and mitigation strategies should be further investigated for the site management of protected areas and heritage sites. This finding has been picked up, for example, in the recently published publication *Mediterranean Protected Areas in the Era of Overtourism* (Mandić & Petrić, 2021).

2.2.1.3. Spatial level on which overtourism has been diagnosed

In order to gain further information on the spatial level on which overtourism has been diagnosed in current literature, the identified destinations were classified according to three categories: regional, municipal, and sub-local or attraction level. The lowest level includes those cases in which specific urban districts, neighbourhoods, parts of a rural municipality or attractions have been stated to be affected by overtourism. The municipal level entails destinations which are more broadly affected, without further distinction of specific places or attractions, such as entire villages or small towns. The regional level applies to all other destinations which consist of a region or an accumulation of closely located destinations, such as coastal strips.

Figure 2: Spatial level on which overtourism has been diagnosed prior to the Covid-19 outbreak (Inventory 1)

Source: Project team, 2021

As displayed in Figure 2, in most of the destinations overtourism has been diagnosed at the lowest spatial level, indicating that especially certain places or attractions are affected by overtourism. However, it must be stressed at this point that 60 of the 87 destinations presented at the lowest spatial level are urban destinations. This can be explained by the fact that the phenomenon of overtourism becomes particularly visible in city centres, since these are often the oldest parts of town where most of the attractions are located. This is for example the case in Tallinn (Estonia), where particularly the historic city centre experiences a high concentration of visitors (Peeters *et al.*, 2018). Current literature also includes case studies referring to overtourism in certain attractions and sites outside of urban areas, such as for example certain sites of the Dolomites in Italy (Ruoss & Sormaz, 2020), the Finnich Glen in the United Kingdom (R. W. Butler, 2020) and Trolltunga and Preikestolen in the Geirangerfjord Area, Norway (Peeters *et al.*, 2018).

Based on the inventory, it can be concluded that particularly in urban areas overtourism can be found at a sub-local level, that is in the city centres. Such a differentiated view is *inter alia* important for analysing the causes of overtourism (Namberger *et al.*, 2019), as well as for identifying appropriate solutions (UNWTO *et al.*, 2018). However, this applies not only to urban areas, but also to other types of destinations. Consequently, in future research on the development of overtourism at destination level, a more differentiated spatial view should be aimed for. Instead of examining a destination only in its entirety, an investigation on the parts of the destination most affected by overtourism can lead to new findings relevant for mitigating and preventing overtourism successfully at destination level.

2.2.2. Inventory 2: Destinations affected by overtourism during the Covid-19 crisis

2.2.2.1. Overtourism during the Covid-19 crisis

As described earlier, the onset of the Coronavirus pandemic in early 2020 has led to drastic changes in the global tourism industry and has necessitated an urgent recovery of the sector. In this context, domestic tourism has been seen as “a key driver of recovery in the short to medium term” (OECD, 2020b) and has been expected to recover more quickly from the Covid-19 crisis (ILO, 2020; McKinsey & Company, 2020; OECD, 2020a; UNWTO, 2021; WTTC, 2020).⁴ Apart from travel restrictions and warnings directly limiting international tourism, this is also attributed to a higher need for security and thus, a demand for “the familiar, predictable, and trusted” (WTTC, 2020, p. 9). The

⁴ Also UNWTO (2020) published in September 2020 the briefing note *Understanding Domestic Tourism and Seizing its Opportunities*, providing guidance and stressing the importance of domestic tourism worldwide for the recovery of the tourism sector

fact that the increase in domestic tourism in some European destinations has also contributed to an increase or intensification of tourism pressure is rarely addressed in current reports. Apart from isolated references to exceedances of destinations' capacities (e.g., Kamp, 2020), overtourism has not been presented as existent during the Coronavirus pandemic.⁵ Instead, the terms "overtourism" or "overcrowding" are mentioned mainly in the context of recovery after the Coronavirus pandemic and are seen as a reminder to "re-think the tourism sector" (OECD, 2020a, p. 27).

This second inventory represents a selection of destinations that showed signs of overtourism despite, or precisely because of, the Covid-19 crisis. It includes 29 exemplary cases of destinations where problems of overtourism, often labelled as "overcrowding" or being "overrun", were recorded during the pandemic. Figure 3 shows the different types of the destinations where overcrowding of tourists was reported during the Covid-19 pandemic. As in the first inventory, some destinations were assigned to more than one category. Most destinations were rural (17), followed by mountain (13) and coastal destinations (12), indicating a high demand for nature-based destinations. In contrast to the first inventory, the second inventory contains very few cases of overtourism in urban destinations, and all of these are urban areas located on the coast or, as in the case of two Czech zoos that were temporally overcrowded, attraction points in urban outdoor areas. However, some studies, such as a survey conducted by the European Travel Commission, suggest that urban tourism, as the most popular type of leisure travel, will recover quickly in the post-Covid period (ETC, 2020).

Figure 3: Type of destinations presented as affected by overtourism during the Covid-19 pandemic (inventory 2)

Source: Project team, 2021

Based on the exemplary cases, some conclusions can be drawn about travel behaviour and developments during the pandemic: Firstly, most of the destinations listed in the inventory are nature-based or rural destinations and (with few exceptions) are part of, or are very close to, protected areas. Furthermore, many of these destinations are located close to urban areas. This development is in line with the previously presented forecasts of the European Union (Marques Santos et al., 2020), which predict, among other things, a higher demand for outdoor activities in rural or natural landscapes as an escape from urban areas. In the summer of 2020, this development could be observed particularly well in coastal destinations or destinations near lakes. Examples include several areas near the Baltic Sea and a number of bathing lakes in Bavaria in Germany (tagesschau, 2020).

⁵ State March 2021.

In the winter of 2020/2021, on the other hand, mountainous destinations and ski resorts in particular were confronted with high numbers of domestic tourists, and especially day visitors. These developments were reported for example in Winterberg, Germany (WDR1, 2021), as well as in several ski resorts in Switzerland (SRF, 2021). Nature reserves, especially national parks, were also frequently visited throughout 2020. Examples are the Peak District National Park in England (Halliday, 2020) and the Eifel National Park in Germany (WDR, 2021). The high increase in the numbers of day visitors to protected areas during the Covid-19 pandemic was also reported, in a study by McGinlay *et al.* (2020), in European national parks. The authors linked the increase in day visitors to European protected areas to the increased desire to travel to remote and supposedly safe locations (McGinlay *et al.*, 2020).

In addition to experienced visitors who were already interested in natural landscapes before the Covid-19 pandemic, visitors who normally pursue other leisure activities (e.g., visiting cultural attractions, shopping) also seem to have travelled more to protected areas during the Covid-19 crisis. Their behaviour sometimes led to critical incidents and more rescue operations, such as in the Ore Mountains, Czech Republic, in January 2021 (Idnes.cz, 2021; Lidovky.cz, 2021).

Furthermore, it can be observed that several destinations experienced high tourism pressure due to high numbers of day visitors during public holidays and long weekends. For example, newspaper articles in the UK reported a high increase of domestic tourists to coastal destinations during the bank holidays. Examples include North Yorkshire (BBC, 2020) and Durdle Door (Mulcahey, 2020) (United Kingdom). This development is in line with the prediction that trips will become shorter or split into several smaller visits (Marques Santos *et al.*, 2020). In addition, the relaxation or lifting of regulations during the Covid-19 crisis also sometimes led to temporary overcrowding in popular public places and outdoor attractions. For example, local media reported that two Czech zoos in Prague and Olomouc suffered from overcrowding after movement restrictions were lifted (iRozhlas.cz, 2021; Zajíčková, 2021).

Most of the analysed articles reported complaints from residents about high levels of infrastructure congestion, especially overloaded roads and car parks. This process can be linked to the increasing use of cars rather than public transport and air travel, due to the higher need for safety. Littering was also often cited as a negative impact of tourism in this context. In addition, visitors may be perceived as “transmitters” of the virus” (McGinlay *et al.*, 2020, p. 7), possibly exacerbating already existing conflicts between residents and tourists, such as competition for space and resources.

The observed increase in domestic tourism numbers and fear of contagion has also led to travel warnings pronounced by local authorities, especially before public holidays. In addition, some destinations implemented new visitor management strategies, often incorporating new technologies. For example, coastal destinations such as the Bournemouth and Poole areas in England and some seaside resorts in the German State of Schleswig-Holstein introduced “beach apps” that use a traffic light system to provide information on the level of congestion on beaches.

There is evidence that especially countries with a high population density, which usually have a high share of outbound holiday trips, were affected by tourism pressure during the Covid-19 crisis. In combination with other factors, such as strong seasonality, destinations that were already popular before the pandemic in particular experienced over-tourism at certain times. In addition, the new social distancing rules and strict hygiene regulations limited the space available in these destinations. For example, Germany has a high population density and had a significant share of outbound trips of 72% (German

Travel Association, 2018, p. 11)⁶. German mountain destinations located near lakes as well as coastal destinations experienced a high tourism demand in the summer of 2020.

In contrast, destinations with a high dependence on international tourism, such as Spain, were less affected by these developments due to the sharp decline of international tourists. Furthermore, different movement and travel restrictions applied within the European countries. While in some destinations there was a strict lockdown with movement restrictions in place, such as a limited radius of movement, in other countries some movement of people and thus day trips were still possible. For a more differentiated analysis, the respective safety regulations of the countries must therefore also be taken into account.

Finally, it should be stressed that the safety distance regulations may have also contributed to a higher sensitivity to crowding. Consequently, it is partly difficult to assess whether all destinations presented actually experienced a real increase in visitor numbers during the Covid-19 crisis, or whether it was *perceived* as such due to the higher awareness and safety regulations enacted.

2.3. Causes and impacts of overtourism

The causes and impacts of overtourism are complex, interrelated and result from a combination of factors. Various causes and impacts of overtourism have been identified and analysed in the current literature (e.g., Dodds & Butler, 2019b; Goodwin, 2017; Peeters et al., 2018; Volo, 2020). However, in order to understand and present the underlying processes of this complex phenomenon in more detail, it is essential to distinguish between different dimensions and categories of overtourism causes and impacts. Dodds and Butler (2019b, p. 6), for example, have listed ten enablers of overtourism. Apart from general developments and characteristics of the tourism sector such as a "dominance of the growth-focused mindset" and the fact that "travel has become more affordable", they list other enablers such as "competition for space, amenities and services" and the "lack of destination control over tourist numbers". Of course, these are all factors that encourage overtourism. But while the dominance of growth orientation and travel affordability describe more general aspects of the tourism sector, the latter relate to the destination level.

Thus, when examining the causes of overtourism, different dimensions and categories can be identified. Weber et al. (2017, p. 188) point out this issue and distinguish between "external and internal factors". Another important aspect is that some factors favouring overtourism have existed for several years, while "many other influences have increased the issue to a tipping point" (Dodds & Butler, 2019c, p. 2). Examples of long-standing developments that promote overtourism include socio-economic factors such as fewer travel restrictions worldwide, higher living standards and generally lower travel costs (Dodds & Butler, 2019b; Goodwin, 2017). Generally, the accessibility of travel has increased, including improved road infrastructure as well as new train and especially flight connections to many destinations, making short breaks to foreign destinations feasible and affordable. Additional influences that have developed, particularly in recent years, include the rise of low-cost airlines, peer-to-peer platforms and new emerging source markets (Goodwin, 2017).

The extensive literature review has led to the conclusion that the causes of overtourism can be divided into the following main categories:

- The **root causes of overtourism** are the underlying developments that have enabled the emergence of overtourism in the first place, consisting of general non-tourism-specific developments, as well as general tourism-specific characteristics and developments.

⁶ This figure includes holiday trips from 5 days onwards in 2017.

- Additionally, **new trends** have emerged in recent years that have profoundly affected the tourism sector, such as the proliferation of social media, the prioritisation of travel and leisure experiences, and new types of tourism.
- In addition, **sudden, unpredictable events** that are not necessarily tourism-specific, have a direct impact by causing a shift of demand.
- These first-mentioned categories lead to a variety of **resulting effects** that become visible at destination level.
- Depending on **intensifying factors** at destination level, which include the general characteristics of the destination as well as the conditions of the local tourism sector, these developments can be enhanced or weakened.
- Finally, these processes result in a variety of **impacts of overtourism** at the destination level.

Based on the literature review, these impacts can in turn be assigned to five main categories, related to the four dimensions physical-infrastructure, environmental, socio-cultural and socio-economic:

- **Degradation of the local infrastructure**
- **Degradation of the environment**
- **Imbalances in the local economy**
- **Disturbance of the social environment**
- **Decreased quality of the visitor experience**

Figure 4: Framework of overtourism causes and impacts

Source: Project team, 2022 based on sources indicated in bibliography

The Driving Forces – Pressures – State – Impacts – Responses (DPSIR) framework used by the European Environment Agency for the development of environmental indicators can also be applied to this framework. The DPSIR framework has originally been used to describe and analyse the relationships between the causes and consequences of environmental problems, their dynamics and their linkages. It can also be used to illustrate the relationship between the different types and levels of causes and the resulting impacts of overtourism. As shown in Figure 4, the categories referred to as *root causes*, *new trends* and *sudden, unpredictable events* correspond to the *driving forces*. The *resulting developments* are what is referred to as *pressure* in the DPSIR model. The *intensifying factors* at destination level are the *state* of the affected system or destination, while the same terminology is used for the *impacts*. The *response* corresponds to the

measures that can be implemented at different levels to mitigate and prevent the occurrence of overtourism, which is part of the research undertaken in Task B.

As Peeters et al. (2018, p. 29) stated “often, various trends work in tandem and contribute to the overtourism phenomenon”. In other words: “Overtourism has resulted from a combination of a number of factors, which together have created a ‘perfect storm’ of visitors to specific sites.” (Dodds & Butler, 2019c, p. 2). Like all models, this framework reduces to some extent the complexity of the underlying processes of tourism pressure at destination level. However, by categorising and linking the different factors, the framework provides an overall view of the underlying processes that ultimately lead to overtourism. Thus, it helps to analyse the phenomenon and its causes and impacts in more detail.

2.3.1. Analysis of the causes of overtourism

Figure 5 provides an overview of the causes presented in more detail below. The root causes, emerging trends and sudden unpredictable events apply to all five types of destinations, as they are general developments that do not take place at destination level. However, the resulting trends and intensifying factors at destination level differ from destination to destination. They must therefore be examined specifically for the respective destination, taking into account the outlined characteristics of the destination types (see section 0).

Figure 5: Overview of the causes of overtourism

Source: Project team, 2022 based on sources indicated in bibliography

2.3.1.1. Root causes: Long-term external factors

There are several external factors that have influenced the development of tourism in general, and eventually enabled the development of high tourism pressure in certain destinations. In particular, the following non-tourism-specific developments are relevant in this context:

- **Demographic changes** including the Millennial generation with new travel behaviour and longer life expectancies (McKinsey & Company and World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017, 14),

- overall **economic growth and higher living standards** (Nilsson, 2020), especially in emerging economies,
- an **increased number of (paid) holidays** (Goodwin, 2017) and
- **technological advances**, combined with **wider access to media and information** (Dodds & Butler, 2019b), as well as
- **increased transport connectivity** through a denser route network and higher frequencies (Goodwin, 2017).

In the past decades, trains, planes and cruise ships in particular have increased their passenger capacities and frequencies, making a variety of destinations more easily accessible. Additionally, international and even national transport facilities are usually outside the control of local authorities or destination organisations (Dodds & Butler, 2019b). For example, airports and ports are often managed by national governments or private companies (Dodds & Butler, 2019b). Similarly, highways and roads are usually under the control of the federal or national government rather than municipalities, which in turn makes it difficult to control or limit the number of arrivals (Dodds & Butler, 2019b). As Dodds and Butler (2019b, p. 15) point out, “many of the cities, islands, ski resorts and other destinations that are facing overtourism issues have tourists arriving via multiple transportation modes. This can cause major issues in terms of managing the flow of people.”

2.3.1.2. *Tourism-specific conditions and developments*

Up until the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, the developments outlined in the previous chapter have contributed to the “**the falling cost of travel**” (Goodwin, 2017, p. 5) this, along with **fewer travel restrictions worldwide**, has been making travel generally more affordable and accessible (Dodds & Butler, 2019b; Goodwin, 2017). In this context, one new type of service in particular has revolutionised the nature of travel over the last decade: low-cost carriers (LCC). According to several authors, LCCs have been instrumental in the growth of weekend, city or short-break tourism. In doing so, they contributed to a radical expansion of potential destinations, not only making already well-established destinations more accessible, but also encouraging the growth of tourist arrivals in lesser-known places (Olipra, 2012). By targeting a range of markets that had not been satisfied with the offering available through “traditional airlines”, low-cost carriers created a new demand for air travel (Olipra, 2012). Examples include cultural, residential, party and VFR tourism. Rončák (2019) for example analysed the impacts of low-cost airlines on the tourism and the general development of Prague. He concluded that the entry of low-cost companies into the Czech market has led to an increase of tourist arrivals and, among other things, an increase in “stag and hen trips”.

Even though of course not all passengers on LCC flights are holiday tourists, several destination case studies have shown that the rise the low-cost airlines can be a factor contributing to overcrowding, and eventually overtourism: LCCs represent **the rise of new competitors in the global tourism market**, which contributes to “new dynamics and competition in the world tourism market” (Weber et al., 2017, p. 189) and leads to a competitive atmosphere characterised by strong price pressure.

Another key feature of the global tourism sector that encourages overtourism is its “**growth-focused mindset**” (Dodds & Butler, 2019b, p. 10) and the associated **inappropriate performance measurement** of Destination Marketing Organisations (DMOs) (Goodwin, 2017, p. 10). Instead of equally considering socio-economic, social and environmental indicators, their focus remains on economic metrics such as international arrivals and number of bed-nights. Due to these measures of success, DMOs often prefer to **market already internationally established destinations**, which is more cost-effective and more likely to lead to success (Goodwin, 2017, p. 6). Successfully marketed and internationally well-established destinations in turn attract even more visitors. In addition, decision-makers usually have a **short-term focus**, which leads to

a lack of long-term planning and consideration of the negative impacts of tourism (Dodds & Butler, 2019b, p. 11).

Moreover, tourist products and attractions are often **public goods** that may be subject to overuse due to their uniqueness and scarcity (Camatti et al., 2021). While several services and products consumed by tourists are free, maintenance and repair costs are mainly paid by local taxpayers (Goodwin, 2017).

2.3.1.3. *New trends*

Long-term external factors and tourism-specific conditions and developments have contributed to a number of more recent trends that have a high impact on global tourism development. Developments in ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) and especially the internet have had a deep impact on the entire tourism industry and are transforming the tourism value chain as a whole. Nilsson (2020) cites the **rise of peer-to-peer platforms** such as *Airbnb* and **the recent proliferation of social media use**, including information platforms such as *TripAdvisor*, as key shaping factors for the tourism sector.

In particular, social media and information platforms such as *TripAdvisor* have become one of the key drivers of consumer awareness and inspiration for travel. As Gretzel (2019) outlines, social media platforms have a number of functions that influence various aspects of travel and tourism. One such factor is that they are used as sources of travel information, which leads, among other things, to travel decisions and also planning during the trip being made at an increasingly later point in time. Moreover, they not only contain up-to-date information, but also provide access to current ratings and reviews of destinations and specific attractions, especially on rating platforms. Consequently, social media platforms have a high influence on the decision-making process of (potential) visitors (Gretzel, 2019).

Social media platforms are also increasingly used by DMOs or online travel agencies (OTAs) as information channels to promote destination attributes, influence destination image, capture additional market segments and ultimately increase the number of tourists (Alonso-Almeida et al., 2019). For example, Spain's National Tourism Organisation has opened *WeChat* and *Weibo* accounts in order to target potential Chinese visitors (Alonso-Almeida et al., 2019).

By sharing their photographs on social media platforms such as Instagram, tourists themselves also actively promote the establishment of "must-see" destinations and thus influence the image of a particular destination (Gretzel, 2019). This ultimately contributes to an "apparently insatiable desire amongst social media participants to visit and be seen in such places" (Dodds & Butler, 2019c, p. 4). Through mentions by popular influencers, previously lesser-known destinations can gain popularity in very unpredictable ways. Therefore, social media can lead to a sudden boost in the popularity of certain areas or sites, contributing to overcrowding and negative destination-level impacts. For example, Russo Krauss (2019) illustrated that many tourists travel to Capri because of the opportunity to meet celebrities and have their holidays at the same time. As a result, social media platforms have contributed to a change in the cultural landscape of the island, as well as to the processes of touristification and gentrification. The promotion of places via social media is particularly problematic if the respective destination lacks the necessary infrastructure or if tourists are spread throughout the destination, outside the established hotspots (Benner, 2020). This is especially true for destinations with little experience in tourism that face a sudden increase of tourist numbers, such as rural areas and small heritage sites. Ruoss & Sormaz (2020), for example, studied the impacts of promoting heritage sites on social media and concluded that "especially in small heritage sites with insufficient or no tourism infrastructure and business, the booming visitor flow results in overtourism and consequently in impacts to natural and cultural

heritage, local economy and population.” (p. 247) They added that particularly the combination of promotion through visual media, such as television, movies and music clips, and social media can lead to periodic or seasonal increases in visitor numbers to small or previously unknown sites.

Furthermore, looking for the best picture to share on social media networks can also encourage unsustainable and careless behaviour (Gretzel, 2019) and even lead to an underestimation of risks (Heslinga et al., 2019). To this effect, Heslinga et al. (2019) presented the example of the Preikestolen cliff in Norway. Tourists often put themselves in very dangerous positions to take “the perfect ‘Instagrammable’ picture” (Heslinga et al., 2019, p. 3). In addition, social media can contribute to the emergence of other new trends that may lead to an increase in tourism in certain destinations. One example is the so-called “last chance tourism” (Gretzel, 2019, p. 69), tourism motivated by the last chance to see something that might disappear in the future (e.g., glacier fields due to climate change). Another important aspect is that social media platforms “represent a complex, networked conversation space, which supports diverse types of affiliations and exchanges, and enables feelings of belonging and community” (Gretzel, 2019, p. 67), detached from time and space. This aspect is not only relevant for the communication behaviour of tourists, but also influences other tourism stakeholders such as the local population. Social media platforms also have a certain political power and “make activism more accessible” (Gretzel, 2019, p. 68). For example, in a study of social movements in the Spanish cities of Marbella and Málaga, Romero Padilla et al. (2019) show that social movements see the creation of social networks and the internet as a turning point in their organisation, as they facilitate communication and expand the possibilities for action against overtourism. As a result, social media can also amplify other socio-cultural impacts, such as the pronouncement of a certain level of dissatisfaction by residents (see section 2.3.2).

However, high social media use is not the only or the most important cause of overtourism, but rather a *contributing* factor to overcrowding and negative tourism impacts. Gretzel (2019, p. 70) summarises: “While social media use is not the only, and likely not the most important, reason for overtourism, it certainly encourages behaviours that lead to crowding and it perpetuates images that influence others to travel to certain places and, once there, behave in certain ways.”

Apart from facilitating overtourism, social media can also be used to mitigate or prevent the phenomenon and its negative impacts. For example, social media platforms can be used to encourage sustainable tourism behaviour, influence and manage tourism flows to mitigate overcrowding, and educate about the causes and impacts of overtourism. Furthermore, as “networked conversation spaces” (Gretzel, 2019, p. 67) they can help in establishing forums of tourism stakeholders. In addition, they can serve as a source of information on current data for tourism decision-makers, and thus as a basis for early-warning-systems (Gretzel, 2019). Ruoss & Sormaz (2020) predict that media and ICT applications will play an important role in new governance and management models and help to balance over- and undertourism in the future, both in time and space. An example of using social media data as a tool for visitor management strategies is presented by Ruoss & Sormaz (2020). By analysing the number of hashtags, posts and reviews on *Instagram* and *Tripadvisor* they visualised over- and undertourism in destinations and short-time visitor flows. They concluded that the analysis of posts and hashtags “can be considered as fast and cost effective and therefore ideal to monitor and forecast tourism developments” (Ruoss & Sormaz, 2020, p. 263). This aspect becomes even more important when considering that Millennials⁷ are more likely to use social media and technology than the previous generations (McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017). Consequently, social media must not only be taken into account when researching the causes of overtourism, but also in its capacity

⁷ Under the term “Millennials” it is referred to the generation born between the early 1980s and the end of the 1990s.

to successfully analyse, and implement possible solutions to, the phenomenon in combination with other measures (Gretzel, 2019).

The rapid development of ICTs has also led to the rise of the **"sharing" economy**. In particular **peer-to-peer accommodation platforms** with *Airbnb* as the most popular provider. These platforms have had a strong impact on the tourism sector and have been analysed by various scholars. They are often cited as one of the driving forces contributing to tourism growth, especially in cities (Nilsson, 2020). Although private home rentals are not a new concept in themselves, the rise of internet providers has led to an extreme increase in these accommodation offers (Koens et al., 2018). There are numerous case studies analysing the negative impact of Airbnb in a variety of destinations, such as several Italian cities (Celata & Romano, 2020), Barcelona (Martín-Martín et al., 2020), Madrid (Gil & Sequera, 2018) and Athens, Lisbon and Milan (Amore et al., 2020).

As Nilsson (2020, p. 6) notes, recent literature has focused on two processes in particular: "the quantitative expansion of peer-to-peer accommodation with consequences for the housing market and the role of peer-to-peer accommodation in the tourist penetration of residential areas outside traditional tourist districts." Another major problem is that while peer-to-peer platforms and (urban) tourism development generate economic benefits, these are often unequally distributed. A significant part of the revenue goes to external owners and residents often do not benefit further from these activities (Żemła, 2020). In addition to other socio-economic disadvantages such as the associated increase in rental prices and less accessible housing, peer-to-peer accommodation platforms also contribute to a range of environmental and socio-cultural impacts, such as increased noise and "a more general sense of insecurity" (Koens et al., 2018, p. 6) (see section 2.3.2). Therefore, the impact of peer-to-peer accommodation platforms can be seen as a "new and slightly different form of touristification" (Koens et al., 2018, p. 6), affecting neighbourhoods across the city, but especially concentrated in the most popular parts of a city such as central neighbourhoods.

In the context of ICT effects, and as briefly stated earlier, different types of destinations are also gaining popularity through their **promotion in films and on television** (Dodds & Butler, 2019c). An example is the city of Dubrovnik, Croatia, which served as a filming location for the *Game of Thrones* series. Although the influence of the appearance of destinations in films is not itself a new aspect, there are currently even more types of media that promote the popularity of destinations (music videos, social media etc.). In addition, some destinations have recently been presented by the so-called "prosumers", tourists who produce and promote their own films and videos, which can lead to a sudden hype. This development is also particularly problematic when the increase is very rapid and occurs in destination types that are particularly vulnerable to high and concentrated visitor numbers, such as rural areas or small historic city centres.

Finally, there has been a rise in **new source markets and tourist groups** travelling both internationally and domestically (Dodds & Butler, 2019b; Goodwin, 2017). In particular, Asian countries are a new, fast-growing source market for important European destinations and are increasing pressure on the already existing "intra-European visitor pressure" (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 33). There has also been a certain **transition from "3S tourism"** ("sea, sun and sand") **to "3E tourism"** ("education, entertainment and experience, or excitement, or emotions") (Żemła, 2020), leading to **new demands, segments and types of tourists**. For example, urban, coastal and island destinations are particularly affected by the growth of cruise tourism and the associated visits of large, concentrated groups (Jordan et al., 2018; Koens et al., 2018; Peeters et al., 2018). An increase in **"bucket-list" tourism** – the desire to "tick-off" certain destinations and attractions" (HOSTREC, 2018, p. 2), has put additional pressure on popular destinations.

Another, quite different, example is the “new urban tourism” – tourists striving to temporarily live like locals in “hip” neighbourhoods – which has influenced the tourism development of cities such as Budapest (Smith et al., 2018) and Berlin (Füller & Michel, 2014).

2.3.1.4. *Sudden, unpredictable events*

In addition to the root causes and new trends, sudden, unpredictable events often have a direct impact on the attractiveness and accessibility of a destination and thus on the tourism demand. Camatti et al. (2020, p. 887) refer to these events as “external factors that cannot be controlled or predicted and which limit the mobility of people”. In contrast to tourism-specific and general long-term developments, they occur abruptly, sometimes repeatedly, but irregularly and are therefore difficult to predict and control. Normally, such events lead to a sudden disruption or decline of tourism in the affected destination, but may cause demand to shift to alternative destinations with similar conditions and cause overtourism there.

A typical example of such events are **terrorist attacks**. A study published by Seabra et al. (2020) concluded that they have a strong impact on tourist arrivals. Due to the high-risk perception of destinations affected by terrorist attacks, often combined with a generalisation of the perceived image to an entire country or region, tourism spillovers can occur. The authors cite inter alia a study by Ahlfeldt et al. (2015), which analysed the reactions of German tourists to several terrorist attacks in Tunisia in 2002 and Morocco in 2003. The study concluded that “those shocks heavily affected Islamic countries and provided a temporary substitution effect in favour of (Southern) European countries” with substantially increased tourist numbers (Seabra et al., 2020, p. 5). **Political disruption** can have similar effects. One example are the conflicts in Turkey in 2016, which contributed to a shift of tourism flows (Koyuncu, 2020).

Other uncontrollable external factors mentioned by Camatti et al. (2020, p. 887) are natural disasters, such as earthquakes and tsunamis, as well as **extreme weather events** which will continue to occur ever more frequently due to climate change. Similar to political instability and safety issues, they could contribute to a temporary or permanent shift in demand to other, often already popular, destinations increasing tourism pressure at these locations.

Of course, the Covid-19 crisis is another example of a sudden, unpredictable event that has been unprecedented in its scope and implications. In contrast to the more isolated disasters described above, it has been unique in that it has affected both tourism source markets and destinations and that its impacts have been felt around the world. Thus, shifts of tourism flows were typically in the form of sudden overtourism events caused by domestic tourism and day trips, as outlined in section 1.5 and 2.2.3.

2.3.1.5. *Resulting effects or pressures*

Key aspects potentially leading to overtourism are the **greater number of tourists as well as rapid growth** (Dodds & Butler, 2019b; Jordan et al., 2018; McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017). Before the Covid-19 outbreak, tourist numbers in the affected destinations were growing both rapidly and steadily. As Peeters et al. (2018, p. 28) note, “on the most fundamental level, overtourism is directly linked to growth in tourist arrivals”.

Closely related to tourism growth is the **temporal and spatial concentration of visitors**. In particular, the promotion of destinations on social media channels and the arrival of new groups of travellers have led to a high tourism density in some destinations. At the same time, the phenomenon of overtourism is often spatially and temporally limited. This is particularly the case with large-scale events, which can also be considered as (temporary) drivers of overtourism due to the pressure they exert on the

local environment, infrastructure and community (Moisescu et al., 2019). Especially when these events are poorly planned or not adapted to the local resources and infrastructure, the pressure increases. The aforementioned developments can also contribute to **undesired visitor behaviour** as well as intercultural misunderstandings, which, together with high visitor numbers, can reinforce the perception of overcrowding (Weber et al., 2017, p. 193). Of course, this aspect is highly dependent on the type of tourists as well as individual behaviour. For example, one of the main problems identified in Lucerne, Switzerland, is that large group tours, primarily from Asian source markets, often remain only for a short time without interacting with the local population (Weber, Egli, Ohnmacht, et al., 2019).

Particularly due to the decline in travel costs and increasing flight connections, less frequented places are also increasingly visited, which leads in parallel to a **distribution of tourism to new places** (Dodds & Butler, 2019b). However, this development is not only observed in the choice of the destination itself, but also at destination level. Due to other factors and trends such as new city tourists and peer-to-peer accommodation platforms, tourists are increasingly visiting residential areas instead of "touristy" places. In turn, the distribution of tourists to new locations is particularly problematic in destinations with very sensitive environments, such as rural, mountainous and coastal areas, and especially in UNESCO World Heritage Sites and protected areas. In these destinations a slight increase in visitation beyond established hotspots can have even more severe negative environmental impacts (Milano, Cheer, et al., 2019a; Weber et al., 2017).

Especially during peak periods, there can be **"imbalances in the number of visitors and residents sharing the same space"** (Milano, Cheer, et al., 2019a, p. 24). These imbalances can in turn lead to a range of negative impacts, particularly on the social environment of the destination (see section 2.3.2). Moreover, visitors increasingly have a **short-term focus in both organising and undertaking trips**, leading them to "travelling at short notice to a wide range of destinations" (Dodds & Butler, 2019c, p. 2). Developments such as shorter stays in turn reinforce a spatial concentration of visitors, as visitors want to see the main attraction points of a destination in a shorter period of time. Other effects include increased traffic, a higher frequentation of easily accessible destinations and a more "condensed" tourist experience (Gössling et al., 2018).

2.3.1.6. *Destination factors intensifying overtourism (state or sensitivity)*

Depending on a variety of conditions and developments at destination level, destinations are more or less susceptible to the negative impacts of overtourism. As a result, the previously outlined resulting effects can either be intensified or weakened. In this context, the general (not tourism-specific) characteristics of the destination and the local tourism sector need to be examined. Weber (2017, p. 1) refers to this category as "contextual factors contributing to negative developments in overcrowded tourism destinations" and lists a number of general and tourism-specific characteristics at destination level. Depending on the characteristics of the destination type, such as geographical and environmental parameters (see part section 0), these characteristics manifest themselves differently in each destination. In addition, the legal and political framework conditions or economic, social and environmental aspects also have a high influence in the respective destination (Weber, 2017).

General destination characteristics influencing local tourism development

Current literature identifies the following possible general characteristics that directly or indirectly influence local tourism development:

- The **lack (or low quality) of facilities** such as public transport, parking, public water etc., leading to infrastructural congestion and capacity problems (Weber et al., 2017, p. 191).

- The **(improved) accessibility of a destination** (Weber et al., 2017, p. 189), e.g., through an expansion of the local port or airport capacities as well as an increase in low-cost airlines connections, as outlined by Rončák (2019) in the case of Prague.
- Additional **pressures exerted through other sectors**, leading to an exacerbation of the impacts of overtourism, such as air pollution, noise, traffic, and possibly an intensification of rivalry between sectors (Weber, 2017).
- A **diversity of stakeholders**, which usually involves a complex interaction of different stakeholders with different interests (Weber, 2017), potentially in turn leading to “disagreement on priorities from the stakeholders side” (Volo, 2020, p. 15).
- **Poor governance** at destination level, for example in the form of a lack of an overall strategic approach, control measures and penalty systems, or insufficient coordination among the diverse stakeholders (Weber, 2017).
- An unequal distribution or **concentration of benefits and capital** can reinforce negative developments. For example, Weber et al. (2017, p. 192) state that “In many destinations where there is a monopolistic economy and a high concentration of capital, often with an accumulation of foreign-owned businesses, there are problems of financial leakages, unilateral benefits and few executive-level jobs for locals.”
- This factor can also contribute to **social disparity** in the form of social or cultural conflicts, generally low income levels and high unemployment, which in turn can also exacerbate the impacts of tourism pressure (Weber, 2017).

Coupled with poor destination governance, **general and tourism-specific laws and regulations** can introduce or amplify the negative impacts on the destination level. Hospers (2020) gives the example of the Mouraria district in Lisbon: in order to promote tourism as a remedy to the financial crisis, real estate laws and tenant protection mechanisms were relaxed. As a result, the older city districts experienced a wave of renovations, which led to rising housing prices and the displacement of local residents.

2.3.1.7. *Characteristics of the local tourism sector*

The current literature presents in particular the following tourism-specific factors which may contribute to overtourism at destination level:

A generally **high dependency on tourism** (Weber, 2017), often combined with a lack of diversification, can intensify the impacts of overtourism and influence the reaction of local stakeholders to it. Furthermore, a **lack of awareness of overtourism and the importance of sustainable tourism development** contributes to a lack of prioritisation and implementation of sustainable tourism management among relevant stakeholders such as policy-makers and local industry players. This problem is identified, for example, by Çakar and Uzut (2020, p. 926) in the case of Istanbul, stating that “awareness of overtourism amongst stakeholders is very limited, and they are therefore unable to develop the necessary policy responses to the problem.”

Furthermore, local communities are often **insufficiently involved in tourism development** and therefore miss the opportunity to actively participate (Weber et al., 2017), which reinforces an “imbalance of power between stakeholders” (Dodds & Butler, 2019b, p. 15). However, this **imbalance of power and responsibility** manifests itself not only at local level, but also beyond. As mentioned in relation to the growth of transport infrastructure, it is not uncommon to find an imbalance of decision-making power at local, municipality and national levels, as well as between public and private companies. This leads in part to the following issue outlined by Wall (2019) in relation environmental issues and overtourism: “Thus, while it is difficult to decide what to do, it may be even more difficult to get agreement on how to do it. This is partly because neither the tourism department nor the environmental department is among the most powerful of gov-

ernmental agencies, and the issues relating to tourism span departmental responsibilities and jurisdictions. Furthermore, the issues must be addressed through administrative structures that vary from place to place. This is a highly significant challenge.” (Wall, 2019, p.40)

Furthermore, the response of policy-makers to (potential) overtourism greatly influences the way in which tourism impacts manifest themselves. This leads to another potential tourism-specific factor: **inadequate implementation of tourism strategies**. As Weber et al. (2017, p. 193) point out: “Where tourism strategies and master-plans are missing or inadequately applied and measures are not implemented, tourism is prevented from developing properly. Poor tourism management can even affect businesses with good performances and be a challenge for the whole destination.” In other words, poor or non-existent tourism management is another promoter of overtourism. Of course, this factor is also closely linked to poor management at destination level in general.

Yet, DMOs often do not have sufficient **access to up-to-date tourism statistics and other tourism-related data**, resulting in a limited scope of preventive measures to limit overflows (Volo, 2020). As Volo (2020, p. 14) points out: “Destinations’ organizations should make better use of historical data and industry data and develop new tools to correct existing statistics (Volo 2018) in order to better estimate the flows, the seasonal peaks and related overcrowding periods.”

Furthermore, the success and quality of a **destination’s branding strategy** plays a significant role as it encourages a first or repeat visit to a destination (Sraphin et al., 2019). Therefore, another important task for DMOs is to rethink the destination’s branding strategy and align it with its core values.

2.3.1.8. *Influence of destination management on overtourism*

As already shown, the conditions and general developments at the local level have a significant influence on the development of (over)tourism. This once again underlines the importance of efficient and sustainable destination management. As pointed out by Weber et al. (2017, p. 191): “The way tourism is managed has a direct impact on carrying capacity and the resilience to overtourism.” In 2017, UNWTO published an opinion article by Taleb Rifai (2017), entitled *Tourism: growth is not the enemy; it’s how we manage it that counts*. The UNWTO Secretary-General emphasised tourism growth as a positive development and necessity, and instead blamed poor management for the problematics that arise in destinations facing exponential tourism growth by stating that “It’s the failure of management, not of the sector as such.” Some scholars also agree that poor destination management and governance can be considered as one of the main causes of overtourism. akar, K. and Uzut, . (2020, p. 926), for example, stated in their case study on overtourism in Istanbul that “the problem of overtourism can be understood as being caused by governance that neglects social and active dialogue, coordination, integrity and unity, communication, collaboration, and participation.” They saw the main problem in the top-down management approach in Istanbul, where the Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism is dependent on the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, represented by the DMOs (akar & Uzut, 2020).

However, “many of the factors leading to a higher vulnerability of tourism cannot be managed by tourism destination management organisations alone. A constant dialogue between industry representatives and public authorities is needed to cope with the challenges of overtourism.” (Weber et al., 2017, p. 6). UNWTO (2018, p. 18) also emphasises, with regard to the power of tourism policy-makers and DMOs in urban destinations, that “their ability to implement management strategies and/or attempt to influence the development and reputation of a city is relatively limited, therefore they cannot be solely responsible for tourism development.” Moreover, tourism development must fit into the overall context of the destination and be embedded in the broader policy framework (UNWTO et al., 2018).

2.3.2. Analysis of the impacts of overtourism

In terms of categorising impacts, the current literature agrees that the impacts of (over)tourism can be roughly divided into three main dimensions: environmental, economic and socio-cultural⁸. The authors decided to add a fourth dimension, the physical-infrastructure dimension, which is sometimes placed under economic impacts, but represents a different, more material type of impact. Furthermore, economic impacts often have social implications and are therefore referred to as socio-economic impacts. As outlined by Martín-Martín et al. (2018, p. 4), socio-economic impacts include “aspects that are related to employment quality and wages, the standard of living, increasing property values, the home tenancy status, and even changes in the job market and the economic system itself”. Impacts on the residents’ quality of life and on the quality of the tourists’ experience are referred to as socio-cultural impacts. Since they are based on the perception of people who are confronted with overtourism, these impacts have a rather subjective, psychological nature. Based on these considerations and depending on the affected stakeholders, the following five general categories of impacts have been identified:

- Degradation of local infrastructure
- Degradation of the natural environment
- Imbalances in the local economy
- Disturbance of the social environment
- Decreased quality of the visitor experience.

Potentially, these categories apply to all types of destinations analysed, although, as with the causes of overtourism, how the identified main impacts manifest themselves at destination level depends on the respective destination type and its specific characteristics. Furthermore, it must be emphasised that the identified impacts are very complex, closely interlinked and partly overlapping. Consequently, they also need to be considered in a broader context. Peeters et al. (2018, p. 22) also highlighted: “Social, economic and environmental impacts should not be assessed independently, but rather interdependently, in a more systemic way.” Consequently, the impacts of overtourism do not always occur in parallel and rarely independently. Instead, they interact and sometimes even occur sequentially.

2.3.2.1. Degradation of local infrastructure

Overcrowding, overloading or overuse of the local infrastructure, more specifically public spaces and facilities, is presented as one of the main challenges related to overtourism (Jordan et al., 2018; Koens et al., 2018; McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017; Peeters et al., 2018; Weber et al., 2017). This impact is highly associated with the aforementioned increase in tourist numbers, a spatial and temporal concentration of visitors to certain areas, and is particularly reinforced when the respective destination suffers from a lack of facilities to accommodate these developments. Particularly in urban areas, however, these effects are often not exclusively caused by high tourism demand. Rather, the pressure can also arise from a general increase in the use of local infrastructure, for example due to an increase of commuters and residents and other parallel developments in society (Koens et al., 2018). Furthermore, the spaces that become particularly crowded vary depending on the type of destination. For example, in island and coastal destinations, beaches suffer most from overcrowding, while in urban spaces, historic city centres are often affected.

Closely related, but considered as a separate impact in this report due to its importance, is the **congestion of local transport infrastructure**. Several case studies report problems with traffic congestion, overloaded roads and public transport systems, and insufficient parking facilities as major impacts of overtourism. Examples include case

⁸ E.g., Atzori, 2020; Peeters et al., 2018; Postma et al., 2018; Wall, 2019; Weber, Egli, Ohnmacht, et al., 2019.

studies in Besalú, Spain and Lucerne, Switzerland (UNWTO et al., 2019) as well as in Giethoorn, the Netherlands and Santorini, and in Greece (Peeters et al., 2018).

In addition to a destination's general infrastructure, physical overcrowding can particularly affect attractions, including culture and heritage sites, thus also leading to socio-cultural impacts (Frey, 2021; Jordan et al., 2018; McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017; Peeters et al., 2018). Peeters et al. (2018, p. 88) identified "**overcrowding at attractions, including natural, historical, and architectural sites**" as a key impact associated with overall "**damage to natural, historical and architectural sites**". These developments can also contribute to a **visual (aesthetic) pollution** "related to the aesthetics of the tourism infrastructure, facilities and activities" (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 88).

Another potential impact on physical infrastructural by tourism, overlapping with socio-economic impacts, is the **loss of investments in infrastructure needed by residents** and the wider destination community due to tourism-generated investments in tourism-specific infrastructure (Peeters et al., 2018).

2.3.2.2. *Degradation of the natural environment*

Due to the growth and concentration of tourist numbers, especially in destinations with a high seasonality, destinations experience **increased use and impairment of natural resources**. This includes a high consumption of water and energy as well as increased land, which may lead to peaks and bottlenecks. This is especially observed in insular destinations with limited resources, where this aspect represents a major challenge (Coccossis et al., 2002). For example, the island of Majorca often suffers from water scarcity (Peeters et al., 2018). Increased resource use may lead to local depletion and imports of natural resources as well as rising maintenance costs for local infrastructure, thus overlapping with physical infrastructural impacts.

Associated with increased resource consumption is the **pollution and degradation of natural resources**. This includes the following possible negative environmental impacts:

- **Air pollution**, often associated with increased traffic. Coastal destinations are particularly affected by the (often temporally concentrated) arrival of cruise ships. One example is the popular cruise ship destination Dubrovnik in Croatia (UNWTO et al., 2019).
- **Noise pollution**, resulting from traffic and tourist activities. In particular, noise at night, caused by the circulation of tourists to residential neighbourhoods with a different daily routine, or by the emergence of party districts, often leads to conflicts. In Budapest, Hungary, for example, noise is one of the main issues causing residents to complain (Pinke-Sziva et al., 2019). Due to its effects on well-being, this impact could also be considered as a socio-cultural impact (Koens et al., 2018).
- **Soil erosion** (in all types of destination, including parks in urban spaces), **coastal erosion** (in coastal and island destination) and **urbanisation of land** (in all types of destination) (Coccossis et al., 2002).
- **Water pollution** caused by an increase in sewage and traffic. In addition to freshwater pollution, this includes marine pollution in coastal and island destinations from boat and cruise ship traffic. In conjunction with unsustainable abstraction of freshwater, salinisation problems can also occur, including saline wastewater produced by desalination plants. Coastal destinations are particularly affected by these developments (Coccossis et al., 2002). Another example is Plitvice Lakes National Park in Croatia, which is affected by a lack of wastewater treatment facilities (Peeters et al., 2018).
- High production of solid **waste** may lead to (temporal) problems in waste disposal and consequent terrestrial and marine pollution (Coccossis et al., 2002).

Overtourism also potentially contributes to the **degradation of natural ecosystems**. As outlined by Coccossis et al. (2002, p. 18), destinations can experience a “loss of biodiversity and impacts on ecological equilibrium due to intense pressure from tourist development in some overbuilt destinations”. Intensive building and outdoor activities potentially affect all types of destinations. However, the ecosystems affected vary greatly depending on the type of destination. Urban areas, for example, may be affected by urban sprawl and the associated **loss of green space**. This development is observed, for example, in Málaga and Marbella, Spain (Romero Padilla et al., 2019). Coastal and island destinations, on the other hand, often face **destruction or alteration of sand dunes or coastal wetlands** due to the removal of vegetation, uncontrolled development or high tourist pressures on beaches (Coccossis et al., 2002, p. 19). Mountain, rural and some coastal destinations are particularly affected by **deforestation or forest clearance** (Coccossis et al., 2002). Examples are the Plitvice Lakes and the Turkish Riviera (Peeters et al., 2018).

2.3.2.3. *Imbalances in the local economy*

Although tourism is often primarily associated with positive economic impacts, there is also a number of negative socio-economic impacts that affect destinations facing overtourism. Current literature presents the following (socio-) economic impacts that contribute to an imbalance in the local economy:

As a result of infrastructural congestion and the pollution of natural resources the “reduction of the quality and **increase in the maintenance cost** for infrastructure, facilities and (commercial) activities specifically directed at inhabitants” may occur (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 39). Even if resource use increases only at certain peak times, related infrastructure generally requires adaptation, resulting in higher maintenance costs throughout the year. Residents are the most affected by these impacts, as local taxpayers are primarily responsible for financing the increased maintenance costs. In addition, these developments contribute to a **“reduced accessibility of infrastructure, sites and facilities for both residents and visitors”** inhibiting regular activities, such as reaching shops or working in their daily local travel” (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 39).

Another major socio-economic impact, especially in urban contexts, is the **inflation of prices**, as outlined by UNWTO et al. (2018, p. 23) focusing on urban destinations. These include:

- rising **housing and rental prices**, particularly in city centres and often linked to the rise of new tourism platform services in the accommodation sector such as *Airbnb*,
- increased price level of **everyday goods**, such as general prices in shops and prices in restaurants and cafés,
- increased price level of **everyday services** such as taxis and public transport (*ibidem*), which is partly related to the often higher purchasing power of foreign tourists (see below), and
- increased price levels of **leisure facilities**.

Nevertheless, tourism is not necessarily the only cause of a price increase; other factors such as the broader real-estate market and the increase in commuters and resident numbers also influence this development (UNWTO et al., 2018).

Price inflation contributes to an overall increase in the cost of living (Jordan et al., 2018; Postma et al., 2018) and may result in a general “reduction of the availability of certain goods, services, and factors of production aimed at inhabitants and for other sectors and functions (industry, agriculture, housing, etc.)” (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 39). In urban areas, such as Berlin (Füller & Michel, 2014), the increasing conversion of rental housing into holiday homes is leading to a loss of available living space. The increasing privatisation of public spaces and community resources is another related process that limits access to formerly shared resources (Milano, 2017; Milano, Cheer, et al., 2019a;

Novy & Colomb, 2019). In combination with these socio-economic processes and different income levels and lifestyles of tourists and residents, there is a **“loss of residents’ purchasing power”** (Milano, 2017, p. 5), which potentially contributes to **“rising inequality among local residents”** (Jordan et al., 2018, p. 5).

These developments in turn lead to a **“degradation of commercial infrastructure and activities specifically directed at residents”** (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 88), and potentially also to **commercial gentrification**. As described in detail by Blázquez-Salom et al. (2019) using the example of the Majorcan capital of Palma, this impact implies the replacement of small shops focused on the needs of local consumers with those focused on tourist demand. Similar developments have also been reported in Amsterdam, Netherlands (UNWTO et al., 2019).

In addition, overtourism can also foster a further dependency on tourism-induced income (Peeters et al., 2018; UNWTO et al., 2018). As a result, destinations may face economic distress in the low seasons and are highly vulnerable to unexpected events (UNWTO et al., 2018). This issue is drastically illustrated by the Covid-19 crisis. Linked to this is a potential **“degradation of other sectors and types of employment”** (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 39). On the one hand, tourism may indirectly contribute to the abandonment of traditional activities such as agriculture and fishing (Coccosis et al., 2002). On the other hand, it reinforces economic monostructures. In this context, the deterioration of the generally rather **low quality of tourism employment** should also be mentioned (Milano, Cheer, et al., 2019a; Walmsley, 2017; Weber et al., 2017). Even though increased tourism may bring higher incomes and less physically demanding jobs than in other sectors, overtourism potentially contributes to a deterioration of already precarious employment conditions (Walmsley, 2017). Possible consequences include unbalanced working hours and an increase of physically, emotionally and mentally demanding work, which ultimately affects workers’ mental and physical health.

2.3.2.4. *Disturbance of the social environment*

The previously described effects contribute to a number of socio-cultural impacts that primarily affect the local residents living in the destinations and their living environment. These processes ultimately contribute to a **touristification** of the destination (Nilsson, 2020; Peeters et al., 2018), which describes the changing character of former residential areas that are becoming less and less suitable for residents and instead more and more adapted to tourists. As a result, popular destinations are becoming increasingly similar, a process also referred to as “McDisneyisation” (HOSTREC, 2018, p. 2).

In particular, congestion of (transport) infrastructure, increased spatial dispersion of tourists into residential neighbourhoods and an imbalance between visitors and residents lead to a degree of **competition for social space, amenities and services between residents and tourists** (Dodds & Butler, 2019b; Volo, 2020). García-Hernández, De la Calle-Vaquero and Yubero (2017, p. 15) illustrate this with the example of San Sebastián, Spain in which the “intensive use of historic spaces by visitors brings with it an increase in competition for central spaces with displacements and changes of use. Different processes can be seen that affect retail trade, hospitality, accommodation and the residential function.” In the most extreme cases, the local population experiences **displacement and marginalisation** (Peeters et al., 2018; Żemła, 2020), resulting in an “excessively high number of tourists per resident” (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 89). Out-migration of residents can be both temporary (e.g., in form of an escape during the peak travel times) and permanent (when residents permanently move out of their previous living space). Especially in urban areas, permanent out-migration leads to a higher number of daily commuters, which in turn increases the pressure on local infrastructure (Koens et al., 2018).

Although in the current literature competition for space and the gentrification of destinations are mainly associated with urban areas, similar processes can be experienced

in other types of destinations, including rural areas (Gascón & Cañada, 2016). Competition for space between different users and residents has also been mentioned in protected areas (McGinlay *et al.*, 2020). However, it is difficult to generalise whether processes of touristification and gentrification are primarily caused by high tourism demand and growth or by other factors such as socio-demographic and cultural changes (Milano, Cheer, *et al.*, 2019a; Nilsson, 2020). Smith *et al.* (2018, p. 2), for example, concluded: "In the post-socialist countries, the process of gentrification depends primarily on the inflow of foreign capital, the extent of state subsidies, the regulations adopted, the development of the real estate market and the preferences of the population on the housing market."

Furthermore, tourism pressures can also cause structural and behavioural changes in the resident population, including changes in family relationships and value systems (Peeters *et al.*, 2018; Postma *et al.*, 2018), and potentially lead to a **"loss of community spirit and pride and a loss of cultural identity"** (Peeters *et al.*, 2018, p. 40). Particularly in cultural and heritage sites, overtourism is seen as contributing to cultural appropriation, loss of traditions and adaptation of social norms (Hugo, 2020). Inappropriate behaviour by tourists can exacerbate these processes (Żemła, 2020). For instance, violation of residents' privacy and personal safety may also increase (Postma *et al.*, 2018; UNWTO *et al.*, 2018), associated with a **feeling of strangeness or insecurity** among local people (Koens *et al.*, 2018; Postma & Schmuecker, 2017). For example, as residents do not always know who occupies the rental properties in their neighbourhoods, the increased use of peer-to-peer accommodation in residential areas contributes to a "a general sense of insecurity" (Koens *et al.*, 2018, p. 6). All in all, these impacts ultimately lead to a **reduced quality of life of residents** (HOSTREC, 2018; Weber *et al.*, 2017).

However, it must be stressed that local residents are not necessarily a homogenous group, particularly in urban areas. Interests within the same stakeholder group are often different, sometimes even contradictory (Gómez & Alfonso, 2019). As Weber *et al.* (2017, p. 182) stated "who the beneficiaries and sufferers in the different cases are, depends a lot on the specific situation". Recent studies on residents' perceptions of (over)tourism point to an influence of economic dependence on residents' attitudes.⁹ Thus, locals who are economically involved in tourism, be it as entrepreneurs or as employees, may have entirely different interests and perceptions than residents who are not.

Furthermore, several recent studies have found out that the perception of the same impact may differ between individuals in the same area. Depending on the exact location where the case study was conducted, they differ considerably in their research results. For example, some studies show a high dependence on the place of residence or even the location of the house (Gerritsma & Vork, 2017; Gómez & Alfonso, 2019), the length of residence (Almeida-García *et al.*, 2016), and socio-demographic factors such as age, place of birth, level of education (Almeida-García *et al.*, 2016) or income level (Martín-Martín *et al.*, 2018).

2.3.2.5. *Degradation of the visitor experience*

Finally, the tourists themselves can be affected by the impacts of overtourism. For example, Frey (2021, p. 26) outlines that most tourists actually seek a certain atmosphere and authenticity in cultural places above all else, which ironically are diminished or even lost through the processes of overtourism. Instead, tourists encounter destinations with a "lack of an 'ordinary neighborhood [sic]'" (Żemła, 2020, p. 9). In addition, "a general

⁹ E.g., Almeida-García *et al.*, 2016; Martín-Martín, Guaita Martínez and Salinas Fernández, 2018; Gómez and Alfonso, 2019; Szromek, Kruczek and Walas, 2020.

sense of overcrowding” can arise, as well as feelings of disruption due to long waiting times and increased prices (UNWTO et al., 2018).

In addition, as a result of the multiple negative impacts of overtourism, as well as possible misunderstandings, some **alienation of the local community** towards tourism may arise (McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017; Peeters et al., 2018; UNWTO et al., 2018). The level of hostility and the way in which residents’ discontent manifests itself varies from passive conflict, social movements and “backlash” (Jordan et al., 2018, p. 5) to active protests against tourism.

Furthermore, the impacts outlined earlier can also lead to increased crime (Frey, 2021, p. 28; Weber et al., 2017, p. 193) and ultimately to a **general deterioration in the perception of safety** among residents and visitors (Peeters et al., 2018, p. 40). In addition, an increase in gambling, alcohol consumption or drug use can reinforce **uncivilized behaviour among visitors** (Frey, 2021, p. 28; Jordan et al., 2018, p. 5), which in turn intensifies the negative impacts and dissatisfaction of residents and tourists alike.

All in all, visitors may experience a **deterioration of their experience**, which in turn translates into an increase in negative reviews and feedback on websites and social media platforms such as *Tripadvisor*, potentially leading to **“online reputation change”** (Oklevik et al., 2019, p. 1807). Finally, the sum of these processes can lead to a **deterioration of the destination image** (McKinsey & Company & World Travel & Tourism Council, 2017; Peeters et al., 2018; UNWTO et al., 2018), which not only affects the tourists themselves, but also local and global industry stakeholders, as well as tourism policy makers and DMOs.

2.3.2.6. *Excursus: Positive impacts related to mass tourism*

As pointed out in the introductory chapters, there is a fine line between mass tourism and overtourism. While the latter is by definition associated with negative impacts, the former term is more neutral and may entail positive impacts as well. Furthermore, both negative and positive impacts of large tourist numbers may simultaneously occur in the same destination. Consequently, some reports and case studies dealing with (over) tourism also point to a number of potential positive impacts. In particular the studies published by Postma et al. (2018) and UNWTO et al. (2018) outline such positive impacts. These positive effects are primarily socio-economic impacts, but also include some positive socio-cultural, physical-infrastructure as well as environmental impacts. Additionally, as emphasised earlier, the manifestation of tourism impacts at destination level is highly dependent on the destination, including the way tourism is planned, developed and managed (see section 2.3.1.8) as well as the general context, the type of visitor and their activities (Martín-Martín et al., 2018). Thus, some destinations may experience rather positive tourism impacts that in other destinations can manifest in an opposite or negative manner. Furthermore, the perception of overtourism and its impacts depends heavily on the perspective, interest and level of involvement of the respective stakeholder groups (see section 2.3.2.6). For example, the results of a survey of residents conducted by UNWTO et al. (2018, p. 23) in eight European cities show that local residents perceive “spatial, social and personal effects slightly more positive than the economic ones”.

Positive socio-economic impacts consist of **higher living standards, income from tourism** and tourism-related activities, **higher employment rates** and **increased tax revenues** (Postma et al., 2018; UNWTO et al., 2018). Positive impacts on the local economy may also benefit **other sectors**, such as local agriculture, and the **improvement of business networks** (Martín-Martín et al., 2018, p. 4).

Other potential positive impacts of (over)tourism relate to local infrastructure. These include the **restoration and maintenance of built heritage** (Postma et al., 2018;

UNWTO et al., 2018) and **the creation and maintenance of infrastructure and services** in general, including public services such as cultural institutions, public transport offers and gastronomy (Postma & Schmuecker, 2017, p. 147). Together these impacts contribute to **higher quality and improved infrastructure** (Postma et al., 2018; UNWTO et al., 2018).

In addition, the literature identifies a number of positive impacts that contribute to improving the social environment of destinations, including **social and cultural exchanges** as well as “a general stimulation and a social enrichment and liveliness” (Postma & Schmuecker, 2017, p. 147). Other positive socio-cultural impacts include the **creation of tourism-related entertainment facilities that are also used by local residents** and **the safeguarding of cultural heritage**. Furthermore, **higher levels of education** (including for example improved language skills, social etiquette and behaviour towards others) and an **improvement of living conditions** are mentioned (Postma et al., 2018; UNWTO et al., 2018).

2.4. Definition and selection of core impact indicators

2.4.1. Basic considerations

The first question that needs to be answered before delving into a discussion on the measurement of overtourism and the selection of appropriate indicators is for which purposes, and on what policy or management levels, are the indicators to be used. As will be shown in the following sections, the task to manage and mitigate overtourism accrues mostly to the local or regional levels. However, some of the broader driving forces that increase the risk of overtourism arise on the national or supranational levels. Examples are the planning and management of large-scale transport infrastructure (e.g. airports, motorways or ports) or strategic decisions taken by large tourism corporations, such as airlines, hotel chains or cruise companies. Global trends in tourism demand have an influence as well, for instance increasing tourism flows from emerging economies (see section 2.3). Therefore, indicators are needed to guide planning and management from the local all the way up to the global levels.

The purpose of developing indicators can be three-fold:

- to detect risks or “early warning signs” before overtourism actually manifests itself, or is in its initial stages;
- to manage and counteract impacts that have already occurred (but may not be plainly visible, e.g. biodiversity loss);
- to monitor the effectiveness of mitigation measures.

The second question is *what* is being measured. Overtourism manifests itself through certain impacts that are caused by an unbalanced development of tourism. This may occur either quantitatively through too many tourists (and the infrastructure and supporting activities that are needed to make tourism happen) or qualitatively, for instance by tourists behaving inappropriately (see annex A.2). Thus, the obvious and direct approach to measure overtourism would be to measure its impacts. However, a conceptual challenge of this method is whether the observed impacts can, completely or partially, be attributed to tourism. For instance, water pollution in a coastal city may be caused by other economic activities or by the residents themselves. A second weakness of using impact indicators is that they measure negative effects that have already occurred.

Therefore, a second approach is to measure overtourism, or the risk of overtourism, indirectly or pre-emptively, that is by:

- assessing the root causes behind overtourism that may affect a given destination, and by
- analysing the territorial context or state of that destination that would make it more or less vulnerable to overtourism and its impacts.

In order to categorise the cause-and-effect relationships that lead to overtourism, the DPSIR (Drivers – Pressures – State – Impact – Responses) framework, originally developed by the European Environment Agency, has been used.

Figure 6: The DPSIR Framework

Source: European Environment Agency 1999

When relating this concept to the spatial levels where overtourism originates and manifests itself, and where it can be managed accordingly, the following observations apply:

- Driving forces (tourism trends, policies) usually originate outside of the destination on the national, supra-national (e.g. the European Union) or even global levels. When this is the case, appropriate policy responses also need to be allocated to these levels.
- Driving forces generate pressures (tourism flows) that manifest themselves on the local levels, but also in transit zones (airports, motorways).
- The category of "state" reflects the local context, or the characteristics of a destination that is affected by these pressures. The interaction between pressures and state then leads to certain impacts which, in turn, require local responses.

The third fundamental question with respect to measuring overtourism is that of a *threshold* at which mass tourism becomes overtourism. By definition, overtourism occurs when the environmental or social carrying capacity is exceeded or, in other words, when impacts become intolerable (see section 2.2). However, as the following graph demonstrates, impacts arise in different ways:

- Type A: Under certain circumstances, low visitor numbers can already have a significantly large negative impact on an area. Examples are animal species that are extremely sensitive to human disturbance during breeding season ("state"), or highly inappropriate visitor behaviour in rural communities. In these cases, the threshold to overtourism is very low and an appropriate management response might be the prohibition or strict regulation of tourist activities.
- Inversely, Type C depicts a situation where negative impacts remain low with increasing visitor numbers, but suddenly rise steeply once the carrying capacity of the affected system has been exceeded. One examples includes the increasing pollution of water which eventually leads to a sudden depletion of oxygen. In this case a threshold or tipping point does exist (marked as CC for "carrying capacity" in Figure 7), but it may be difficult to determine beforehand (for instance, through a specific indicator value) when it will be reached. In spite of their differences, Types A and C have in common that an actual threshold exists between tolerable and intolerable impacts.
- This not the case with Type B where a gradual increase of impacts as a direct function of visitor numbers can be observed. Even though this situation may be more "comfortable" for destination managers as it does not produce overtourism suddenly, it makes it arbitrary to impose any concrete limits (indicator values) beyond which tourism would be labelled as overtourism. It is plausible to assume that most undesirable tourism developments occur in such a way. Under this

scenario it would be adequate to measure overtourism on a sliding scale of increasing or decreasing severity or risk.

Figure 7: Development of impacts as a function of visitor pressure

Source: Eagles/McCool 2002

Source: Eagles & McCool 2002

2.4.2. Literature analysis: Measurement approaches and indicator systems

Several of the authors cited in sections A.1 and A.2 have already proposed measurement systems and indicators for overtourism. Therefore, in this section four meta-studies which have developed their own more or less comprehensive methodologies for measuring overtourism will be analysed. These are the following:

- McKinsey & Company, World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC): Coping with Success – Managing Overcrowding in Tourism Destination. December (2017)
- Peeters, P. Gössling, S., Klijs, J. et al.: Research for TRAN Committee – Overtourism: Impact and possible policy responses. October 2018
- Weber, F., Stettler, J., Cramer, U. et al.: Measuring overtourism – Indicators for overtourism: Challenges and opportunities. Hochschule Luzern, December 2019
- Schuh, B., Derszniak-Noirjean, M., Gaugitsch, R. et al.: Carrying capacity methodology for tourism. Interim report. ESPON, September 2020

In addition, the European Tourism Indicator System – ETIS toolkit for sustainable destination management (European Commission, March 2016) was analysed.

2.4.2.1. McKinsey & WTTC: Coping with Success (2017)

The purpose of this study was to develop a globally applicable indicator system for cities that are (potentially) affected by overtourism. The system was tested in 68 cities around the world. The selection of the indicators was guided by the following principles:

- Simplicity, meaning that the system should be easy to handle by destination managers.
- The indicators should be tourism-specific, so as to avoid measuring pressures or impacts caused by other factors.
- The data for the indicators should be widely available, ideally on a global scale, but at least in Europe.
- The data should also be regularly available, thus allowing for comparisons over time.

The results of this study are listed in Table 1. The approach taken in the study design was to look at the physical, social and environmental systems in the destination that are potentially impacted by overtourism as well as at the general tourism context, and following this to allocate nine core indicators to them. An emphasis was put on infrastructure and on social issues, and less so on the environment. Indicators were retrieved mostly from classical tourism statistics and from big data (TripAdvisor). Actual impacts

were only measured by two indicators (tourist satisfaction and air pollution). Rather, the focus was more on identifying pressures and on driving forces.

Table 1: Overview of indicators selected for measuring overtourism in cities

Context/ Impacted system	Criterion	Indicator	Data source	DPSIR category
Tourism economy	Importance of tourism	Direct share of GDP and employment (%)	Classic tourism statistics	State
Tourism economy	Arrivals growth	% CAGR 2011 to 2016 (paid accommodation)	Classic tourism statistics	Driving force
Local residents	Tourism density	No. of visitors per km ²	Classic tourism statistics	Pressure
Local residents	Tourism intensity	No. of visitors per resident	Classic tourism statistics	Pressure
Tourist experience	Negative reviews	TripAdvisor for Top 10 attractions	Big data	Impact
Overloaded infrastructure	Seasonality of arrivals	Ratio arriving flight-seats highest & lowest month	Traffic statistics	Driving force
Overloaded infrastructure	Attraction concentration	TripAdvisor: Share of reviews of Top 5 attractions	Big data	Pressure
Damage to local environment	Air pollution	Annual mean particulate matter concentration	Environmental statistics	Impact
Culture and heritage	Historic site prevalence	TripAdvisor: Share of Top 20 attractions	Big data	Pressure

Source: McKinsey & WTTC 2017, Exhibit 4, p. 21

The values for each indicator were then calculated for each of the 68 cities in the sample. The resulting values were segmented into quintiles, with the top quintile meaning the highest risk of overtourism (see Figure 8 for the example of Barcelona). The representation of risk is relative, in that the assessment of a given destination with respect to overtourism is relative to the other destinations in the sample. By applying this methodology, the authors have explicitly refrained from defining thresholds for overtourism, rather they have created a sliding scale with an increasing or decreasing *risk* of overtourism.

The strength of the methodology developed by McKinsey & WTTC lies in its simplicity and the potential of its application around the world. A major limitation is that it is specifically applicable to urban destinations and may be less suitable for use in other destinations affected by overtourism, especially for natural areas where environmental impacts are probably more prevalent. There are also some other shortcomings (see also Peeters et al. 2018):

- The results are relative, meaning that they depend on the size and selection of the sample which may or may not be representative.
- The tourism statistics are "classical" in the sense that they do not include day visitors or informal accommodation (such as many Airbnb listings), both of which are recognised as important drivers of overtourism.
- Local air pollution is a criterion that is particularly relevant for destinations affected by automobile traffic and cruise tourism, but it is very difficult to disaggregate it from non-tourism sources.
- Data gained from internet platforms such as TripAdvisor may not be reliable as they are influenced by default settings and specific algorithms (see Weber et al. 2019).

Figure 8: The calculated risk of overtourism for Barcelona based on quintiles

Source: McKinsey & WTTC 2017, Exhibit 6, p. 24

2.4.2.2. Peeters et al.: Overtourism – Impact and possible policy responses (2018)

Similarly to the previous report, this study undertaken on behalf of the European Parliament also developed a set of core indicators to measure overtourism and further tested these through various statistical methods against a number of European “destinations in a state of overtourism” that had been retrieved from the literature on overtourism. This had been achieved by calculating the values of potential indicators on the NUTS-2 level throughout the European Union. Just as in the McKinsey/WTTC study, the resulting values were then divided into quintiles and compared with the existence or non-existence of overtourism destinations within those regions. In theory, the correlation would be found to be strong if a region that contained one or several destinations in a state of overtourism was also in the top quintile for the respective indicator value.

A further 41 cases were analysed in greater depth, some located outside of Europe. In contrast to the McKinsey/WTTC study, the analysis was not confined to cities, but also included rural and coastal destinations (including islands) as well as heritage sites and single attractions.

As a result, the authors developed a set of eight core indicators for which they had found an, albeit not very strong, correlation with the occurrence of overtourism (see Table 2). The indicators are mostly classical tourism statistics, complemented with air traffic data, data from Airbnb and geographic data. The DPSIR categories covered are drivers, pressures and state. There are no impact indicators, meaning that overtourism is measured indirectly. Consequently, just as in the McKinsey & WTTC (2017) study, the intention was not to measure overtourism per se, but rather the risk of overtourism.

Table 2: Overtourism indicators selected by Peeters et al. (2018)

Criterion	Indicator	Data source	DPSIR category
Tourism intensity (Tourism Penetration Rate) ¹	Bed-nights per resident (number of visitors per 100 inhabitants)	Tourism statistics (Eurostat)	Pressure
Tourism density (Tourism Density Rate) ¹	Bed-nights per km ² (annual number of visitors per km ²)	Tourism statistics (Eurostat)	Pressure
Air travel intensity	Arrivals by air per number of bed-nights	Traffic statistics (openflights.org, Eurostat)	Driving force
Share of Airbnb bed capacity	Share of the combined Airbnb and booking.com bed capacity	Big data	Driving force
Significance of tourism in regional economy	Share of regional GDP (%)	Tourism statistics (Eurostat)	State
Proximity to cruise port	Km (< 15 km as a tentative threshold)	Geodata (cruise companies)	State
Proximity to airport	Km (< 30 km as a tentative threshold)	Geodata (openflights.org)	State
Proximity to UNESCO World Heritage Site	Km (< 20 km as a tentative threshold)	Geodata (UNESCO)	State

¹ Includes day visitors | Source: Adapted from Peeters et al. (2018)

Nevertheless, in the study's abstract, the authors come to the conclusion that "a common set of indicators cannot be defined because of the complex causes and effects of overtourism." Therefore, the suggested indicators on NUTS-2 level can only serve as an orientation for determining the risk of overtourism for destinations within the respective region. The results of this extensive analysis are shown in Figure 9. The map combines the average values of all (equally weighted) core indicators, whereas the red and orange colours symbolise a relatively high risk of overtourism.

Figure 9: NUTS-2 regions displaying various levels of overtourism risks

Source: Peeters et al.(2018). Map 12, p. 76

The methodology has some other shortcomings that were identified by the authors themselves:

- The validity of the indicators was checked against “destinations in a state of overtourism” that were identified as such by other authors who may have used different definitions and metrics for overtourism. As Figure 9 shows, many overtourism destinations are not located in high-risk areas for overtourism.
- The NUTS-2 level constitutes in itself a problem insofar as it is too coarse for identifying overtourism which tends to occur in much smaller areas (see annex A.2).

- On the other hand, data availability in finer granulation varies from destination to destination which complicates the possibility of comparing indicators across the EU territory.
- The proposed set of indicators does not measure any impacts (for instance, residents' or tourists' sentiments towards tourism) caused by overtourism.
- The potential of big data for measuring overtourism was hardly explored by the authors.

Consequently, and almost as an "afterthought", Peeters et al. recommended the use of an additional checklist of qualitative questions to assess the risk of overtourism in a given destination. These questions are very much related to local context ("state") and to management responses to overtourism, or rather the lack thereof. They include, for instance, whether a destination management organisation pursues growth-oriented tourism policies or favours participatory planning.

2.4.2.3. *Weber et al.: Measuring Overtourism – Indicators for overtourism: Challenges and opportunities (2019)*

Whereas the previously analysed studies focused on comparability (cities around the world, EU regions), Weber et al. (2019) recommended the use of site- and problem-specific indicators in addition to more general ones. For them, overtourism is largely a local phenomenon, with very specific manifestations, which requires local solutions, including the use of locally developed indicators for monitoring purposes. However, the authors acknowledge that collecting data for "custom-made" indicators may require too much effort. Their guiding principle therefore is to conceive a system of locally relevant indicators that are easy to manage.

In order to identify and test such indicators, the authors conducted nine in-depth comparative case studies throughout the world. This was performed in addition to eleven case studies that had been carried out by some of the authors two years earlier. Most examined destinations were urban, but the samples also encompassed coastal destinations (including islands) and a mountain destination. While the number of case studies was lower in comparison to McKinsey & WTTC (2017) and Peeters et al. (2018), the number of indicators that were tested was much higher. As a first step 20 "classical" tourism and destination indicators were applied (see Table 3). All of these indicators were quantitative and represented predominantly driving forces, pressures and states in the DPSIR typology. This first set of indicators was supplemented with eleven so-called "experimental" indicators (including visitor concentration, number of tourism-specific offers, differing price levels, TripAdvisor reviews and Airbnb listings – mostly a mixture of pressures and impacts), the indicators developed by McKinsey & WTTC and some case-specific indicators that presented themselves while conducting the case studies.

Table 3: Quantitative core indicators tested by Weber et al. (2019)

Metric	Definition (Description of Indicator)
Destination area	Area of destination (km ²)
Area of tourist centre	Area of tourist centre (city centre) (km ²)
Inhabitants in destination	Number of inhabitants in destination
Inhabitants in tourist centre	Number of inhabitants in tourist centre
Population development	Increase or decrease in local population from 2012-2017
Hotels	Number of Hotels
Hotel rooms	Number of Hotel rooms
Hotel beds	Number of Hotel beds
Tourist arrivals	Absolute value of the number of tourist arrivals in destination (2017)

Metric	Definition (Description of Indicator)
Arrivals growth	Growth in tourist arrivals (%) from 2012 to 2017
International and domestic arrivals	Share of international tourist arrivals
Overnights 2017	Total overnights per year
Development of overnight stays	Development of overnight stays from 2012-2017
Overnights in low season	Overnights in low season
Overnights in peak month	Overnights in peak month
Overnights in lowest month	Overnights in lowest month
Overnight visitor high season	Number of months in 2017 with overnight visitor number above average
International and domestic overnights	Share of international overnights
Day visitors 2017	Total day visitors per year (estimated)
Employment in Destination	Tourism share of employment (%) in destination (as percent of total)

Source: Weber et al. (2019), Table 1

The authors encountered a number of challenges when analysing the validity and usefulness of overtourism indicators:

- Heterogeneity in how overtourism manifests itself in different destinations
- Highly aggregated data does not allow for the necessary spatial and seasonal differentiation
- Single indicators, or overly simplified indicator systems, may not be sufficiently valid to reflect the complexity of overtourism.
- Customised data may be desirable but is often not available, outdated or difficult to collect.
- Data retrieved from social media or peer-to-peer platforms may not be reliable due to certain default settings and algorithms.
- Monitoring systems and the required input data must be dynamic in order to respond to newly emerging trends. This data must also allow for comparative observations over longer periods of time.
- The spectrum of what is measured in tourism needs to be broadened in a way that also considers domestic tourism and in particular day tourists.
- The opinions and sentiments of local residents must be measured and taken into account more thoroughly.

In turn, the identification of these challenges led Weber et al. to the recommendations listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Challenges and recommendations regarding the measurement of overtourism according to Weber et al. (2019)

Challenge	Recommendation
Heterogeneity	Identify key problems
Aggregation	Choose the right set of indicators
Validity of single indicators	
Data availability	Work with what you have
	Make use of new tools and data sources
Data reliability	Choose data sources carefully
Dynamic	Take a dynamic approach
Spectrum	Extend the spectrum
Non-consideration of residents	Focus on the residents perspective

Source: Weber et al. (2019), Table 16

Figure 10: Indicator framework for monitoring overtourism according to Weber et al. (2019)

Source: Weber et al. (2019), Figure 46

In summary, the authors refrain from recommending any concrete indicators. Instead, they propose a framework of potential indicators that is similar to the DPSIR methodology; the differences being that "Supply" corresponds partially to "State" (but is limited to tourism offers and infrastructure, disregarding, for instance, social structure or ecological fragility) and that "Demand" corresponds mostly to "Pressure". In contrast to the two previously analysed studies, Weber et al. (2019) also propose the use of "response" indicators (see Figure 10).

2.4.2.4. Schuh et al.: Carrying capacity methodology for tourism (2020)

Even though this study does not directly deal with overtourism, it discusses the measurability of carrying capacity in tourism, a concept that is key to the understanding of overtourism. As outlined in section 3.1, overtourism occurs when a certain threshold or the carrying capacity of a given social or natural system has been exceeded.

As with all of the previously analysed studies, Schuh et al. (2020) started out with a literature analysis in order to identify methodologies for the measurement of carrying capacity. An overview of the results is provided in Table 5. The authors further "extracted" a set of 20 most commonly suggested indicators. These rely mainly on classical tourism statistics and on environmental indicators (mostly driving forces and pressure indicators).

Table 5: Suggested tourism indicators for measuring carrying capacity

Study	Strengths	Weaknesses	Potential degree of applicability	Suggested indicators ¹⁰
Jurado et al. (2012)	Carrying capacity assessment : 24 indicators (9 physical, 9 socioeconomic, 6 social)	– Focus on the coastal area – Data availability/collection effort	Medium	1. bednights (absolute value and percentage change)
UNWTO (2014)	Density (explicitly labeled as carrying capacity in this report), CO ₂ emissions, water consumption, solid waste generation, visitor load (number of tourists per day per 100 residents), resident satisfaction, congestion and intrusion, use of essential services	– Focus on cities – Data availability/collection effort	Medium	2. arrivals (absolute value and percentage change)
Gössling et al. (2015)	Travel distance and estimation of CO ₂ emissions	Focus on countries, no focus on modal split, source-market weighting, number of destinations visited	Low	3. average length of stay
European Union (2016); European Commission (n.d.)	– 43 core indicators – Supplementary indicators for specific types of destinations – Slovenia as one of the case studies	Data availability/collection effort	High	4. tourism revenues
González-Guerrero, Robles, Pérez, Ibarra, and Martínez (2016)	– Overview of the carrying capacity studies – Evaluation of visitor management models	NA	Low	5. share of tourism contribution to GDP
Green Destinations (2017)	– 6 main themes – 100 criteria	Data availability/collection effort	Medium	6. occupancy rate
McKinsey & Company and World Travel & Tourism Council (2017)	– 9 metrics for a diagnostic development – 5 tactics with specific sets of actions	Focus on cities	High	7. number of bedspaces available in commercial accommodation establishments (absolute value and percentage change)
Önder, Wöber and Zekan (2017)	An overview of potential objectives and indicators for destinations and their policy-makers (classified as economic, social, and/or environmental)	Focus on cities	High	8. share of Airbnb bedspaces
University of St. Gallen (2017)	– 6 steps for understanding visitor flows	NA	High	9. distribution of bedspaces
Lenzen et al. (2018)	– Bilateral embodied CO ₂ emissions – Breakdown of the tourism carbon footprint into purchased commodities and emitting industries	– Focus on countries – Analytical complexity	Low	10. distribution of demand (seasonality)
Peeters et al. (2018)	– 6 indicators of overtourism – Applicable to various types of destinations – Bled as one of the case studies	NA	High	11. tourism density
				12. tourism intensity
				13. percentage of same day visitors to total number of visitors
				14. CO ₂ emissions (during traveling to/from and at the destination)
				15. waste production per tourist night compared to general population waste production per person (kg)
				16. water consumption per tourist night compared to general population water consumption per resident night
				17. energy consumption per tourist night compared to general population energy consumption per resident night
				18. closeness to airports, cruise ports and World Heritage Sites

¹⁰ This list of indicators is based on the literature review on carrying capacity of tourism destinations. The listed methodologies are all using their own often very comprehensive indicator lists. Since one of the most identified weaknesses is the data availability and data collection effort the suggested list of indicators is focusing on from the expert perspective most relevant indicators encompassing the three dimension of sustainability.

Study	Strengths	Weaknesses	Potential degree of applicability	Suggested indicators ¹⁰
Roland Berger (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Quality versus quantity – proactive measures (short term, mid term, long term) – 3 reactive measures 	Focus on cities	Medium	19. negative TripAdvisor reviews 20. overall satisfaction of visitors and residents with tourism
UNWTO (2018, 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 11 strategies – 68 measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Focus on cities – Data availability/collection effort 	Medium	
Gunter and Wöber (2019)	Travel distance, modal split, source-market weighting, number of destinations visited, and estimation of CO ₂ emissions	Focus on cities	High	
Önder and Zekan (2019)	Recommendations	Focus on cities	Medium	
WEF (2019)	Variables from the pillars on environmental sustainability and natural resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Focus on countries – Data availability/collection effort 	Medium	

Source: Schuh et al. (2020), p. 6/7

Schuh et al. (2020) then proceeded to integrate the selected indicators into a broader framework of destination management which was tested in several tourism destinations in Slovenia (urban and non-urban). Similarly to Weber et al. (2019), the authors emphasise the practicalities of indicator use, that is the availability of corresponding data and the efforts required to collect them. Secondly, the eventual selection of indicators is highly participatory, involving local workshops and stakeholder interviews at Steps 1, 2 and 5 (see Figure 11). The selection process of indicators is incremental, starting with a broad range of indicators (the 20 most commonly used indicators having been listed in Table 5) and then narrowed down or expanded according to local issues and needs. This participatory process even applies to the identification of limits beyond which carrying capacity is exceeded. Instead of determining thresholds as fixed points, the authors advocate for limits of impacts or, adversely, target corridors which are to be defined by local needs and development goals. In this sense, this approach is similar to the Limits of Acceptable Change framework that was developed for visitor management in North American protected natural areas, with the exception that the latter are typically uninhabited and decisions on visitor carrying capacity are taken by protected area managers (see annex A.1).

Figure 11: Participatory methodology to determine tourism carrying capacity in destinations

Source: Schuh et al. (2020), p. 11

2.4.2.5. The European Tourism Indicator System (ETIS)

The aim of ETIS has been to provide a framework and an indicator system for European destinations who wish to take steps towards sustainability. Avoiding overtourism is implicit in the framework, but is only one of several issues. Similarly to what was proposed by Schuh et al. (2020), ETIS has been conceived as part of a participatory destination management process. The original intention had been to provide a fixed indicator set, for reasons of comparability. However, due to widespread criticism regarding the diversity of destinations and the feasibility of data collection, the system can now be used more flexibly, leaving out indicators that are not deemed important and adding others that are relevant to a particular destination. The process of using ETIS indicators as a monitoring tool is outlined in Figure 12.

After a revision, ETIS now includes 18 sustainability criteria, measured through 43 core indicators, plus a list of optional supplementary indicators that may be applied to special destinations (maritime & coastal tourism; transnational cultural routes) or to measure specific issues. The criteria/indicators are divided into the four dimensions of sustainability:

- Destination management: A.1 Sustainable tourism public policy (response), A.2 Customer satisfaction (impact)
- Economic value: B.2 Tourism flow (driving force, pressure, state), B.2 Tourism enterprise performance, B.3 Quantity and quality of employment, B.4 Tourism value chain
- Social and cultural impact: C.1 Community/social impact (impact, pressure), C.2 Health and safety, C.3 Gender equality, C.4 Inclusion/accessibility, C.5 Protecting and enhancing cultural heritage, local identity and assets (impact)
- Environmental impact: D.1 Reducing transport impact (driving force), D.2 Climate change, D.3 Solid waste management (impact, response), D.4 Sewage treatment (response), D.5 Water management (impact, response), D.6 Energy usage (impact, response), D.7 Landscape and biodiversity protection (response)

Figure 12: Steps to develop the ETIS planning and monitoring process

Source: European Commission 2016

Eleven of the 18 criteria are applicable to the measurement of overtourism (highlighted in bold above). Those criteria and their corresponding indicators cover the entire spectrum of the DPSIR typology, but with a focus on impacts, which makes them, in principle, particularly suitable for measuring the environmental and socio-cultural effects of overtourism. Accompanying documents explain to users how to collect data and how to conduct surveys (of tourists, tourism companies and residents). Many indicators can only be collected through special surveys, especially the ones that are impact-related (European Commission 2016).

According to Font (2019), only about one third of the ETIS data can be retrieved from official statistics. Of the 200 destinations that had originally expressed interest in participating in the two ETIS test phases, less than 40% actually did. Of these, 65% were satisfied with the methodology. However, in his survey, Font found that only a minority of the involved destinations actually used the collected data to initiate and monitor progress towards sustainability (ibid.).

In summary, the ETIS framework faces similar challenges as do the methodologies that have been suggested to measure overtourism. Data availability and the effort to collect data that is not readily available appear to be major barriers to implementing the system. Furthermore, ETIS does not claim to define thresholds beyond which tourism becomes sustainable tourism in a destination¹¹ – another similarity to the other studies in the overtourism discussion.

2.4.3. Summary findings

There is an evolution that can be observed from the first to the fourth study analysed in the previous section. Whereas McKinsey & WTTC (2017) strove to create a simplified system for cities on a global scale (with classical quantitative tourism statistics and TripAdvisor reviews), Peeters et al. (2018) have created a quantitative indicator system based on regional statistics covering a broader range of destinations and the entire EU which was qualified as only partially adequate by the authors themselves. Almost as an afterthought they added a qualitative (not well-founded) checklist for destination managers to determine their local risk of overtourism. Finally, Weber et al. (2019) and Schuh et al. (2020) – also covering different destination types – have shied away from recommending generalised overtourism indicators altogether. Instead, they emphasised the necessity of managing overtourism locally with the help of site- and problem-specific data, a stronger consideration of residents and, in the case of Schuh et al., a participatory process in the affected destinations. This more flexible approach is also reflected by the European Commission's recommendations on how to use the European Tourism Indicator System (ETIS). Originally a fixed set of indicators, it has now been acknowledged that it might be better to adapt ETIS to local conditions, at least to a certain degree.

The downside of a flexible approach, however, is that destinations striving to mitigate overtourism or to become sustainable are no longer comparable. Furthermore, this precludes to a certain degree the possibility of managing overtourism on a national or supra-national level, for instance by striving to influence broader driving forces within or beyond the tourism industry on the national or international levels that might create overtourism problems throughout the territory in question.

Neither of the first two studies (McKinsey/WTTC 2017 and Peeters et al. 2018) pretend to measure overtourism itself. Rather, they speak of an increased or decreased *risk* of overtourism, both recognising that there is no defined threshold between mass tourism and overtourism. Instead, McKinsey & WTTC developed a sliding scale of core indicator values derived from a sample of cities that might be affected by overtourism. Peeters et al. did the same for EU regions, but they also included indicator values of regions *not* labelled as overtourism destinations for comparison. Both studies divided the resulting indicator values into quintiles in which the top quintile represents the highest risk of overtourism. Apart from the difficulty of defining a certain threshold between two states, the concept of overtourism in these two approaches is also, therefore, *relative* to other destinations in a given sample. Schuh et al. (2020) circumnavigated the problem of defining objective thresholds by conceiving them as subjective limits or, inversely, as target corridors of desirable indicator values to be determined in a participatory process.

Consequently, all of the five analysed approaches tend to measure mostly driving forces and pressures exerted by tourism rather than actual impacts. State indicators measuring the sensitivity of a destination towards overtourism are even more underrepresented. ETIS is the only framework that explicitly strives to measure response indicators, with a strong focus on environmental issues (see Table 6). Weber et al. (2019) listed a broad range of potential overtourism indicators, including state, impacts and responses, but did not recommend any core indicators.

¹¹ For a more in-depth discussion on the question of thresholds between sustainable and unsustainable tourism, see Balaš, M. & Strasdas, W.: Nachhaltigkeit im Tourismus – Entwicklungen, Ansätze und Begriffsklärung. Umweltbundesamt Texte 22/2019, Oktober 2018

Table 6: Inventory and categorisation of suggested overtourism indicators

Metric	McKinsey	Peeters	Schuh	ETIS	DPSIR type
Tourism spending/revenue			x	x	Driver
Importance of tourism (% GDP, employment)	x	x	x	x	Driver
No. of bed-spaces/resident			(x)	x	Driver
Spatial distribution of bed-spaces			x		Driver
Arrivals growth (%)	x		x		Driver
Bed-nights growth (%)			x	x	Driver
Length of stay			x	x	Driver
Occupancy rate			x	x	Driver
Share of Airbnb bed-spaces		x	x		Driver
Share of second homes/residents				x	Driver
Seasonality: Distribution of demand	x (air arrivals)		x		Driver
Air travel intensity		x			Driver
% of same-day visitors			x	x	Driver
Means of transportation, distances covered by tourists				x	Driver
Proximity to airport, cruise port, UNESCO WHS		x	x		State
Tourism intensity	x	x (+ TPR)	x	x	Pressure
Tourism density	x	x (+ TDR)	x		Pressure
Attraction concentration (based on visitor reviews)	x				Pressure
Historic site prevalence (based on visitor reviews)	x				Pressure
CO ₂ emissions from tourist transportation			x	x	Pressure
Energy use per tourist			x	x	Pressure
Waste production per tourist			x	x	Pressure
Water consumption per tourist					Pressure
Air pollution	x				Impact
Residents' satisfaction; identity			x	x	Impact
Visitor satisfaction: Negative reviews, complaints	x		x	x	Impact
Waste management by tourism enterprises				x	Response
Sewage treatment				x	Response
Water management by tourism enterprises				x	Response
Energy efficiency and renewable energy use				x	Response
Biodiversity conservation by tourism enterprises				x	Response

Source: Compiled by the consortium

2.5. Mapping EU destinations under pressure

The literature analysis under Task A has led to the identification of rural, urban, mountain, island, and coastal destinations which are under pressure by overtourism. Map 1 illustrates the distribution of these identified destinations. Highlighted NUTS 3 regions correspond to regions with at least one identified destination affected by overtourism. The distribution according to type of destination (urban, rural, coastal, island, or mountain) is provided in separate maps in Appendix 1.

Map 1: Destinations affected by overtourism

Source: Project team, 2022

A scoping of available data has led the project team to preliminarily identify four indicators to measure overtourism. The following indicators were populated and mapped for this report:

- Importance of tourism for the local or regional economy (% of gross value added (GVA) in Map 2 and % of employment in Map 3)¹²
- Tourism intensity (number of bed-nights per number of inhabitants) in Map 4
- Tourism density (number of bed-nights per km²) in Map 5

This selection is preliminary and is expanded and refined under Task D. The project team opted to select indicators at NUTS 3 level, where available. If data was not available at NUTS 3 level, the NUTS 3 data was approximated or *regionalised* from available NUTS 2 data¹³. In addition, regions with identified overtourism destinations are highlighted.

Indicators on the regional (i.e. NUTS2 or NUTS3) economic importance of tourism activities are not available from uniform datasets at EU level. Eurostat carries an indicator which also captures other economic sectors in addition to tourism activities (wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication), which are connected to tourism activities.

The gross value added of the sectors of wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication is represented as percentage of the total gross value added, on a NUTS3 (2016) level, for the year 2018.

Although the sectors included here extend beyond the scope of tourism alone, the data presents a uniform picture across Europe, from which some findings become visible namely that populous cities, mountainous regions and coastal regions tend to have a higher percentage. However, NUTS-3 regions with overtourism destinations are not necessarily to be found in the top ranks, but rather in the 20-30% range.

¹² Eurostat offers GVA and employment data for the NACE sectors G-I and G-J, however, not for the individual sub-sectors. This covers economic activities closely associated with tourism (such as accommodation). Sectors: wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication.

¹³ Regionalisation was undertaken by multiplying the NUTS 2 value of the indicator by the number of inhabitants living in the NUTS 3 region relative to the overall population of the NUTS 2 region.

Map 2: Gross value added from tourism activities as a share of total gross value added

Source: Project team, 2022

Map 3: Employment from tourism activities as a share of total employment

Source: Project team, 2022

The employment of the sectors of wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication is represented as percentage of the total employment, on a NUTS3 (2016) level, for the year 2018.

Coastal as well as mountainous regions present a higher percentage, as do urban regions with higher populations. Island regions in Greece, Spain and Croatia have particularly high values, whereas more rural regions of eastern and central Europe are at the opposite end of the scale. The importance of tourism employment seems to be a slightly better indicator for the existence or risk of overtourism than the percentage of GVA since most overtourism destinations are to be found in the 20 to 40% range.

Map 4: Tourism density (2018)

Source: Project team, 2022

This map shows the total number of bed-nights (stays) spent at tourist accommodation establishments per square kilometre, on a NUTS3 (2016) level. The data was regionalised from NUTS2 to NUTS3 level by using the share of population of the NUTS3 relative to the NUTS2 regions. The data shows nights spent by both national as well as international guests. Of note, there are data gaps for non-EU states.

The map illustrates a concentration of higher density regions in western European, particularly from the Netherlands, Belgium and Germany in the north that span until the northern parts of Italy in the south. In addition to this, most populous urban regions also have a high density, as do several island and coastal regions of Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia and Greece. Surprisingly, there appears to be a rather weak overlap between high tourism density on NUTS-3 level and the existence of overtourism destinations. This overlap is more pronounced in the Mediterranean than in other parts of Europe.

Map 5: Tourism intensity (2018)

Source: Project team, 2022

This map shows the total number of bed-nights (overnight stays) spent at tourist accommodation establishments per 10,000 inhabitants, on a NUTS3 (2016) level. The data was regionalised from NUTS2 to NUTS3 level, by using the share of population of the NUTS3 relative to the NUTS2 regions. The data shows nights spent by both national as well as international guests. There are data gaps for non-EU states.

One interesting conclusion which can be drawn from this figure is that populous city regions have particularly low values, even though they might have a high number of nights spent. The higher values are clearly present in regions with a small population and a proportionally high number of tourists, such as some Greek island regions, the Croatian coast, and mountainous regions in multiple countries along the Alps.

Again, most overtourism destinations derived from the literature are not located in regions of high tourism intensity. This might be due to the fact that incidences of urban overtourism are often limited to certain neighbourhoods and thus relatively insignificant for urban areas as a whole.

3. Task B: Identifying best practice solutions, successfully applied by tourism destinations in the EU and globally

3.1. Methodological approach

Based on the overview developed in Task A.1, extensive desk research was carried out to gain a comprehensive list of possible case studies. An inventory of potential case studies for the different geographical areas (urban, rural, mountain, coastal, island) was developed based on findings from existing studies such as by the UNWTO et al. (2018), Dodds & Butler (2019), Weber et al. (2017), Peeters et al. (2018) as well as journal publications, white papers and media reports. This task was closely linked to Task A.1 and therefore the same assessment grid was applied for the inventory. Therefore, the project team has developed a joint assessment grid for Task A.1 and Task B.1 as indicated below. In addition to the European cases (Task A.1), some prominent global examples have also been included in the inventory.

Table 7: Assessment grid for the inventory

Destination/ Country/ Region	NUTS 3 Level	Type of destination	Protected Areas and Heritage Sites		Spatial level overtourism arises			Key facts tourism situation and de- velop- ment	Solution Approa- ches (Measures taken)	Case Study availa- ble	General sources and fur- ther in- for- mation
			Protec- ted Ar- eas	UNESCO World Heritage Site	Regio- nal	Municipal- ity	District/ Attrac- tion				
		Urban/ Rural/ Coastal/ Island/ Mountain									

Source: Consortium

Even though the aim of the case study analysis is to look at exemplary cases, a balanced representation of different aspects in regard of geographical distribution, root causes, impacts and solution approaches, amongst others, has also been at the forefront.

A comprehensive set of criteria for the selection of the cases to be analysed was developed. The most important criteria were the existence of successful solution approaches, as well as a balanced representation of the five destination types and geographical distribution within Europe. In addition, data availability, the diversity of root causes and impacts, and the informative value of the cases were integrated as important aspects considered.

The selected case studies were analysed using a case study framework. This finalised framework has been based on the insights of Task A and has been discussed and adapted with feedback from the project team. The framework contains quantitative as well as qualitative criteria that not only allow for the development of a comprehensive picture of the specific situation at the destination level, but also a cross comparison of the different cases. The finalised analysis framework serves as a structure for the cross-comparison of all case studies as well as an interview guideline for the researchers working on each of the cases. The framework includes general categories that are of research interest as well as specific case study items for each category and guiding questions.

The methodological design for the case studies was based predominantly on secondary data compilation from published academic and industry reports. The case studies were compiled using a template, which provided a basic structure for each case. Published information on each case was reviewed and complemented with interviews from tourism stakeholders from each destination. In some cases, one or more person provided information about unbalanced tourism at a given destination. All interview partners were at senior management level representing organisations closely involved with destination management. Their input is acknowledged in the bibliography of each case. This approach therefore contributed the completion of case study analysis and validated some

of the information compiled from secondary sources. However, as the method for recruiting interview partners was organisation based, the views expressed may not represent multi-stakeholder views from each destination. Therefore, it may be that some of the opinions expressed for a given case may also contain some bias.

3.2. Selection of best practice cases

The goal of this task is to select the final set of best practice case studies for further analysis. Data according to the developed selection criteria was collected by desk research and based on the preliminary work for the inventory. Thus, the data gathered in the assessment grid of the inventory serves as a basis for the selection process. Based on the selection criteria defined, possible case studies were gathered in a comprehensive list. The cases were then researched again in more detail, especially regarding the existing solution approaches as these best practice solution approaches are the key focus in Task B. Based on these insights, three cases per destination type (urban, rural, mountain, coastal, island) were defined and the final selection was then discussed in the project team.

Furthermore, as some destinations are already more prominently covered in various overtourism studies (e.g. Barcelona, Dubrovnik, Amsterdam, Prague etc.), the focus was placed on cases that are equally interesting and allow for some new knowledge creation in overtourism literature. These comparably less researched cases can deliver an added value, especially considering the diversity and transferability of the solution approaches taken.

All European regions are represented with some cases and it is only the eastern region of Europe where the topic seems to be less relevant (except for in selected cities). Overall, with the present selection, a good balance could be achieved in terms of geographical distribution as well as in terms of assessing different root causes and impacts. Table 8 shows the selection of the cases for the analysis.

Table 8: Argumentation for Case Study Selection

Case Study Name	Country	Type of Destination	Geographical Distribution	Root Causes	Impact	Solution approach (innovative, transferable, feasible)	Information availability	Covid-19 context	Social Media	Protected area	Heritage site
Lucerne	Switzerland	urban	Western Europe	group tourism, tourism growth in source markets	alienated local residents, traffic/parking situation, coaches	Political process → participatory tourism development	good				
Vienna	Austria	urban	Central Europe	generally growing visitor numbers, river cruises, bus tourism	seasonal peaks (for ex. Christmas markets), tourist hotspots (for ex. Schönbrunn), negative perceptions of river cruise and bus tourists (day visitors), parking and traffic	ICT based visitor management, continuous resident surveys, stakeholder participation through expert hearings	good				X
Florence	Italy	urban	Southern Europe	Airbnb, short term rentals, attractions	overcrowding, price development, alienated residents	Spatial and temporal strategies	medium				X
Geirangerfjord Area	Norway	coastal	Northern Europe	cruise tourism, social media	overcrowding, traffic, environmental issues	Promoting off-season, price management	low		X		
Baltic sea (Lübecker Bucht, St. Peter Ording)	Germany	coastal	Central Europe	Overcrowding, Covid19	overcrowding, traffic, parking problems	Digital crowd management (app)	medium	X			
Palma de Mallorca	Spain	coastal	Southwestern Europe	tourism growth	alienated residents, environmental issues	Eco tax, campaign "Better in Winter", regulations and bans	good				
Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche	France	rural	Western Europe	tourism growth	environmental issues	Visitor management plan, visitor flow management, EU-founded LIFE programme	medium			X	
Burren and Cliffs of Moher	Ireland	rural	Western Europe	tourism growth	environmental issues, tourist experience	Best-practice example for community collaboration (Burren Ecotourism Network). Extended opening hours, Advance booking and intelligent management, Price based incentives for trade operators, "Come later in the day" FIT messaging, Operational closure of admissions	medium				

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level

Case Study Name	Country	Type of Destination	Geographical Distribution	Root Causes	Impact	Solution approach (innovative, transferable, feasible)	Information availability	Covid-19 context	Social Media	Protected area	Heritage site
Plitvice Lake	Croatia	rural	Southeastern Europe	tourism growth	lack of sewage system and waste-water treatment, lack of capacity, environmental issues	Zero-Waster Strategy, New Management Plan, electric vehicles are used, products from local family farms are used, and they received the green light from UNESCO, which has just monitored all protection processes and even threatened to remove Plitvice Lakes from the UNESCO list.	good		X	X	
Bled	Slowenia	mountain	Central Europe	increase in foreign markets	overcrowding, parking	New targeted segments (upmarket), special law prohibits new construction on the immediate banks of the lake, regulations for swimming and boats, parking,	medium				
Rigi	Switzerland	mountain	Western Europe	group tourism	overcrowding, alienated residents	Masterplan Rigi, new schedules, adaptation of infrastructure, information, round table with different stakeholders, sustainability charter	good				
Dolomites/Lake Braies	Italy	mountain	Southern Europe	Italian TV series, strong marketing campaign, social media	overcrowding, environmental impact	Visitor guidance system, carfree from 10am to 3pm Visitor limitations	medium				X
Malta	Malta	island	Southern Europe	tourism growth	touristification, prices, public facilities	Off-peak tourism concept, zoning systems (increase of pedestrian areas etc.), environmental contribution	good				X
Mallorca	Spain	island	Southwestern Europe	tourism growth, cheap flights	anti-tourism protests, Environmental issues, Real estate speculation	Seasonal dispersal	good				
Reykjavik/Iceland	Iceland	island	Northern Europe	cruise, cheap flights, Airbnb	gentrification, environmental issues, real estate speculation	Education (Iceland Academy, responsible tourist pledge)	good		X		

Source: Project team, 2022

3.3. Observed Tourism Characteristics and Development

The aim of this section is to compare 15 selected tourism cases from Europe (Table 1), where the tourism growth in recent years has led to unbalanced and or overtourism developments. The case studies are provided in Appendix 8. These cases were preselected from nearly 200 destinations and considered for detailed analysis in Part A of the research since they individually each represent good case examples, particularly in how they address various types and stages of overtourism. As defined in chapter 1.2 this research is based on a definition that describes a "situation in which the impact of tourism, at certain times and in certain locations, exceeds physical, ecological, social, economic, psychological, and/or political capacity thresholds" (Peeters et al, 2018, p. 22). This section details selected case examples with vastly different characteristics in terms of geography, socio-political, and tourism history which are described separately in the summaries below. In this context, the stage and development of overtourism is also vastly different amongst the 15 cases. As the detailed cases highlight, all of the destinations are experiencing some form of overtourism, which can be better described as a form of "unbalance" due to the nature of specific drivers, impacts and management solutions implemented.

The 15 cases can be broadly classified as coastal, island, mountain, rural and urban tourism destinations, which allows for a basic categorical analysis in a tourism context. This section illustrates the characteristics of unbalanced tourism development with a focus on the period from 2010 to 2020. It provides insight into the physical and temporal nature of tourism issues, the drivers for tourism intensification and the contemporary solutions which are currently being implemented by key stakeholders to address unbalanced tourism development.

Each case study is a unique illustration of unbalanced tourism over the past years, which have brought to light the following key insights with respect to good practice solution approaches.

Florence, Italy demonstrates how mass visitors can be absorbed by a destination year round and supported by a careful orchestration of management initiatives spanning across various subsectors of tourism combined with digital communication solutions to nudge crowds to steer away from specific hotspots.

Lucerne, Switzerland highlights how a destination strives to achieve consensus by participative democracy amongst stakeholders' groups with otherwise diverging interests. This destination aims to balance very high numbers of day and group visitors from Asian countries arriving on coach buses, while maintaining a historic city setting that meets local resident expectations as far as cultural identity and the level of touristification are concerned.

Vienna, Austria provides insight into how a destination engages with the tourism sector to address the subjective perception of unbalanced tourism that only occurs to some degree and is often spatially concentrated at key tourism attractions. The city is a good case to explore on how tourism stakeholders strive to attract visitor segments in a manner that matches resident values.

The Bay of Lübeck, Germany is a valuable case that illustrates unbalanced tourism predominantly involving domestic and day visitors while employing a variety of innovative digital strategies to manage beaches that temporarily suffer from congestion and related issues.

Geiranger Fjord, Norway is an illustrative case of how independent scientific findings on air quality impacts can help to enforce solution measures, such as the recent set of national regulations regarding zero-emission cruise ships entering heritage fjords starting in 2026.

Palma is a coastal city destination that highlights how unbalanced tourism can be mitigated with efforts in the field of digitalisation that can help to manage and control visitor flows combined with a variety of other management solutions, including the restriction of further accommodation expansion and the arrival of cruise ships.

Mallorca demonstrates how tourism can quickly develop to become unbalanced, requiring stricter control and management of stakeholders involved. It is a relevant case as Mallorca has established a Sustainable Tourism Observatory to monitor environmental, social and economic tourism impacts, and thus to facilitate tourism decision-making. Furthermore, a wide variety of measures such as a Sustainable Tourism have also been employed.

Iceland as a country and an island showcases how events such as the global financial crisis, a volcano eruption, increased accessibility via flights and cruises and viral media coverage of the destination can exponentially increase international visitor arrivals over the course of just one decade. It highlights numerous management solutions to disperse visitors spatially and temporally, and to nudge more sustainable behaviour, e.g., by requesting visitors to sign a responsible visitor pledge.

Malta is a country and island destination that demonstrates a case where tourism stakeholders do not appear to perceive unbalances from the recent development of the sector despite the presence of some issues of crowding at several locations on the island.

The **Burren and Cliffs of Moher, Ireland** is a classic nature-based destination where mostly day visitors place significant pressure on the iconic landscape and environs, without significantly financially contributing to the management of the area. The case offers a combination of solution approaches how to prolong stays in the area and how to regulate the tour operating sector to conform to park management guidelines.

The **Parc Régional de Monts Ardèche, France** is an insightful case where multi-level stakeholders with somewhat overlapping geographic boundaries strive to manage crowds that place pressure on a few iconic sites in the area. The application of digital technologies used to collect big data on visitors appears to offer solutions for stakeholders in terms of informed decision making, which would otherwise be difficult due to their different spatial management boundaries.

Plitvice Lakes, Croatia demonstrates how coach bus management flow can be dispersed from one single site by using a range of measures related to accommodation infrastructure regulation combined with the arrival of visitor buses at the park's gate.

Bled, Slovenia provides insights about how repositioning a destination to be greener and more sustainable involving a variety of stakeholders including the local authorities can enable for quick and effective management implementation to control unbalanced tourism.

The **Dolomites Mountain, Italy** destination is another case illustrating the power of using data driven analysis about impacts to enforce solution approaches. Their study on carrying capacity using mobile device data from visitors gives a more concrete understanding of the present unbalances and creates further legitimacy for regulatory measures.

Mount Rigi, Switzerland showcases how a classic mountain destination can develop unbalances perceived as a cultural conflict amongst local stakeholders. It also highlights how collaborative and strategic tourism planning can provide new pathways to resolve perceptions of "overtourism". The "2030 Rigi Charta" is a process and tool that enables data collection and data driven discussion amongst stakeholder of different interests and powers of influence.

Table 9: An overview of cases and their main tourism attractions

Destination Category	Destination Cases	Key hotspots contributing to visible crowding
Urban	Florence, Italy	Historic city centre, museums, cultural events
	Lucerne, Switzerland	Historic city centre, Lion Monument, Alpine Views over lake shore, watch shops
	Vienna, Austria	Schönbrunn Palace Area, Zoos, historic city centre, Christmas markets,
Coastal	Lübeck Bay, Germany	Sun, sea, sand: narrow coastal zone along bay area along 2-4 km of Baltic Coast, Hansapark (theme park),
	Geirangerfjord, Norway	Dramatic coastal fjord scenery with mountains
	Palma, Spain	Historic city centre, Cathedral, Royal Palace, Port of Palma
Island	Mallorca, Spain	Beaches, scenic coastal areas, mountainous villages
	Iceland, Iceland	Reykjavík city, pristine landscapes, geological and geomorphological attractions, particularly those located in the capital region (Blue Lagoon and the Golden Circle route) and in the South of Iceland
	Malta, Malta	Historic centre and churches, archaeological sites, beaches and coastal areas
Rural	Burren and Cliffs of Moher, Ireland	Dramatic coastal cliff landscapes, caves
	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche, France	Scenic mountains and valley views, waterfalls
	Plitvice Lakes, Croatia	A scenic lake area in a mountain area
Mountain	Bled, Slovenia	Panoramic lake area in a mountain setting, iconic castle on an island, Vintgar Gorge, Triglav National Park, Julian Alpine Scenery
	Dolomites, Val Pusteria, Italy	Dramatic Three Peaks, Lake Braies
	Rigi, Switzerland	Cable car, summit peak, various built areas near summit

Source: Project team, 2021

3.3.1. Tourism development and organisations

Tourism arrival numbers and overnight stays have steadily increased at all case study destinations over the past decade, and many have represented classic tourism areas for more than several decades. Some destinations for example Mount Rigi have a long history of debates in the tourism sector regarding *how much tourism is too much*. However, some destinations have only recently had to deal with unbalanced tourism due to the extensive growth of international tourism in the last decade. This increase in tourist arrivals has in certain cases led to a rapid development or revision of existing tourism organisational structures (e.g., Iceland, the Burren and Cliffs of Moher).

The case destinations currently all have a highly organised and structured tourism management system in place with various organisations taking leading roles in tourism marketing and promotion amongst other classic coordination responsibilities commonly assigned to a Destination Management Organisation (DMO). Furthermore, most destinations have numerous municipalities within their geographic or political spatial boundaries (e.g., Geirangerfjord, Dolomites) representing complex structures that demand extra coordination. At some rural destinations, particularly around natural parks, such as Monts Ardèche, the Burren and Cliffs of Moher and Plitvice Lakes, the indirect issues of tourism coordination between park management authorities and local authorities are also highlighted.

Since several of the case destinations have United Nations World Heritage listed attractions within their territories adding them to the list of “iconic places” to visit, UNESCO is also a key stakeholder in tourism management at these sites. For example, in the Geirangerfjord area the UNESCO foundation has even taken over some of the classical non-profit tasks that the DMOs would normally carry out and thus, has also become a key stakeholder regarding development. Despite a seemingly well organised tourism industry at the destinations, they all highlight ways in which unbalanced tourism occurs.

3.3.2. Recent Tourism Growth Patterns

One of the first points to note, among the 15 cases, is a significant double to even triple digit tourism arrival and overnight stay growth over the past ten years before the Covid-19 pandemic began affecting tourism flows (Table 10). However, this growth range is highly variable at the destinations, as are the causes and impacts of unbalanced tourism. For the past ten years, all 15 case destinations show higher than average international arrival statistics compared to the UNWTO, which reports a global 3.6% average annual growth rate from 2009 to 2019. Notable deviations from the “average” include Iceland (+308%), Bled (+149%) and Malta (+107%). Other well established tourist destinations such as Mallorca (+36%), Florence (+26%) or the Dolomites (+39%), show lower growth rates (Table 10). However, when comparing the base rates of tourist arrivals, the destinations with comparably lower growth rates in the last years have been welcoming well above 1 million visitors per year in previous decades. Thus, absolute numbers and significant growth increases must be considered in this context.

The numbers represented in Table 10 are mostly based on the official statistical records of the respective countries. This means that only official accommodation statistics go into these figures and there is some uncertainty regarding the number of visitors staying in private accommodation, or day visitors, as they are often not completely represented in these official statistics. The urban and island destinations of Palma in Mallorca are noteworthy, where in addition to 66% growth rates for hotel overnight stays in the city centre of Palma, cruise passengers also grew 182% for the same period. In Iceland, besides the high growth rates of arrivals and overnight stays, cruise ship passengers arriving at the port of Reykjavík also grew significantly, namely by 136% in the same period. Furthermore, in the Geirangerfjord, the growth of cruise passengers is a substantial driver of unbalanced tourism especially in small villages like Geiranger.

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level

Table 10: Average growth rates from 2009 to 2019 (pre-pandemic)

		Arrivals			Overnights			Other relevant growth statistics
Destination		2009	2019	Growth (%)	2009	2019	Growth (%)	
Urban	Florence	4,248,818 (2010)	5,372,412	+26%	11,418,183	15,840,756	+39%	
	Lucerne	679,642	945,903	+39%	1,194,793	1,628,319	+36%	
	Vienna	4,385,529	7,926,768	+81%	9,842,827	17,604,573	+79%	
Coastal	Lübeck Bay	416,220 (2015)	603,704	+45%	1,740,000	2,626,514	+51%	
	Geirangerfjord	n/a	n/a	-	n/a	n/a	-	Cruise passengers at Geiranger port 2009: 218,038 2019: 402,335 → 84% growth
	Palma	564,420	907,083	+61%	1,595,930	2,642,229	+66%	Cruise passengers 2009: 785,509 2019: 2,217,496 → 182.3% growth
Island	Mallorca	8,718,788	11,874,835	+36%	42,417,320	50,825,632	+20%	
	Iceland	493,940	2,013,190	+308 %	3,004,629	8,406,291	+180 %	Cruise passengers at the port of Reykjavik: 2009: ca. 69,000 2019: 162,476 →135.5% growth
	Malta	1,330,000	2,771,888	+107 %	352,312	474,950	+38%	Overnights: Nights spent at tourist accommodation es- tablishments
Rural	Burren and Cliffs of Moher	n/a	n/a	-	n/a	n/a	-	Visitors Cliffs of Moher 2015: 1,251,574 2019: 1,605,131 → 28% growth
	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche	n/a	n/a	-	n/a	7,807,000	-	
	Plitvice Lakes	-	345,625	+51%	-	485,699	+58%	
Mountain	Bled	204,837	509,247	+149 %	503,724	1,132,574	+125 %	
	Dolomites (Val Pusteria)	1,620,584	2,247,110	+39%	8,761,045	10,431,438	+19%	
	Rigi	n/a	n/a	-	n/a	n/a	-	in railway travel frequencies 2009: 1.11 M. 2019: 1.87 M. → 68% growth

Source: Project team, 2022; Note: For detailed references and statistics please refer to the respective case study file.

3.3.3. Temporal and spatial aspects

Unbalanced tourism is mostly linked to peak European holiday seasons at all destinations (cf. Table 11). This means that visitor arrivals are the highest and most concentrated between the months of May and September. The mountain destination Dolomites also reports increased visitor numbers during winter season where typical winter outdoor activities like skiing, snowboarding or cross-country skiing can be performed. Some destinations such as the Bay of Lübeck also report crowding issues over long weekends, whereas Vienna reports the same during special events such as the Christmas markets in December. While on the other hand, several destinations have high visitor numbers all year round, particularly Malta and Florence.

In Iceland for example, tourism seasonality in the past years has considerably decreased (in contrast to the 50% observed seasonal arrival in 2010, in 2019, 34% of all visitors arrived at the island's main airport between the months of June and August). However, even within the destination, crowding patterns can have different seasonal distributions.

Although rural areas have relatively large open spaces to absorb visitors to the broader region, the attractions that visitors seek out are often located at very specific sites with limited parking facilities to tolerate mass expansions. Further, even these open spaces available are sometimes restricted for conservatory purposes (i.e. in the Burren and Cliffs of Moher where around 60% of the park is designated as a special area of conservation with restricted access). However, even in these cases, there exists the potential to better distribute visitors as spatial distribution is often concentrated at iconic sites, to the detriment of less iconic locations (e.g. at the Cliffs of Moher visitors could be absorbed by other sites that have not reached full capacity (for example the Aillwee Cave)).

Table 11: Temporal Aspects of Unbalanced Tourism

Destination Category	Destination Cases	Crowding across seasons				Special peak times
		Winter November to February	Spring March to May	Summer June to August	Autumn September to November	
Urban	Florence	x	x	x	x	Tourism balanced all year
	Lucerne		x	x		
	Vienna					
Coastal	Lübeck Bay			x		Sunny weekends
	Geirangerfjord			x		
	Palma		x	x	(x)	
Island	Iceland			x		
	Mallorca			x		
	Malta	x	x	x	x	
Rural	Burren and Cliffs of Moher			x		
	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche			x		Long weekends
	Plitvice Lakes			x		
Mountain	Bled			x		
	Dolomites (Val Pusteria)	x		x		
	Rigi		x	x		

Source: Project team, 2021

3.3.4. Tourism intensities and densities

In the analysed destinations tourism intensity (tourist nights per inhabitants) varies between 16 and 144 and tourism density (tourist nights per km²) varies between 82 and 132,327 tourist nights per km². However, due to the nature of the vastly different geographic characteristics of the 15 cases and the lack of consistent available statistics, particularly for day visitors and overnight stays that are not recorded in official statistics (e.g., Airbnb, unregistered private accommodation) it is challenging to meaningfully calculate and compare these indicators. These numbers often account for an entire municipality or even tourism region due to the corresponding statistical surveys. Therefore, particularly in urban destinations tourism density and intensity are even higher, since most of the tourists are concentrated in the historical centre and even the wider city is often also popular among day tourists.

Furthermore, the day visitors, which in many analysed destinations play a crucial role regarding unbalanced tourism, are also not adequately accounted for in these indicators. For the rural areas Geirangerfjord, the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, Plitvice Lakes and Mount Rigi the data used to calculate the tourism intensity and density is not available. These destinations do not have a clearly defined boundary for the tourism areas, and often the destination is broadly defined compared to the actual sites where unbalanced tourism exists or could be measures. Thus, these numbers show how broad the spectrum can be and how difficult it is to adequately put a quantitative measure on the complex issues of unbalanced tourism.

Table 12: Destination tourism intensity and tourism density

Destination	Tourism Intensity (overnights/inhabitants)	Tourism Density (overnights/km ² for the administrative tourism area)
Florence (Province of Florence)	16	4,508
Lucerne	20	55,937
Vienna	10	42,434
Lübeck Bay (Scharbeutz)	144	132,327
Iceland	24	82
Palma	22	43,799
Mallorca	57	13,980
Malta	94	1,503
Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche	93	3,424
Bled	144	15,730
Dolomites (Pustertal)	125	5,037

Source: Case studies in this report, Project team, 2021

3.3.5. Visitor Segments

Based on the 15 cases analysed, international tourism growth appears to drive unbalanced tourism at all destinations. Clearly, both domestic tourists and day excursionist also contribute to the unbalanced tourism developments observed in recent years. However, it appears that international tourism growth drives the recorded tourism expansions markedly at all destinations (see section on specific drivers). Exceptions to this is the Bay of Lübeck in Germany, where international overnight statistics have remained around 5% over the past decade and the Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche where international tourists represent around 22% of visitors. At all other destinations, the proportion of international visitors has grown and currently represents around 50% or more of all visitors. For example, in County Clare where the Burren and Cliffs of Moher are situated, international tourists represent 59% of visitors, in Florence this is 70%, in

Iceland this is 87% and in Bled 95% of overnighting visitors are international tourists. At some destinations, a strong shift has been observed, such as at the mountain tourism destination Rigi in Switzerland, which historically has had about 20-30% international tourism, while in recent years, this has increased to around 60%.

3.3.6. Capacities and Bottlenecks

Unbalanced tourism across the 15 cases is caused principally by the arrival of a large number of people concentrated over a short period, typically during the summer months (Table 10) in popular areas of the destination. This arrival mode often illustrates a classical bottleneck situation of people crowding and can be observed in practically all cases, independent of the type of destination.

In mountains and rural areas like Bled, the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, Dolomites, Bay of Lübeck or Monts d'Ardèche, most visitors arrive on their own or in rented cars, contributing to traffic jams and exceeding the carrying capacities of parking facilities. In Bled, the lack of suitable road and parking infrastructure is an important challenge that is being addressed by different infrastructure projects to relieve the streets around Bled and the lake. Similarly in the Dolomites the arrival mode by private car presents challenges (around 86% of incoming tourists enter the region by means of private transport and more than half also continue to use private transport during their vacation). This leads to a high amount of pressure on the local road infrastructure capacities, which are often overstretched during peak summer days and weeks with negative consequences resulting not only for tourists (e.g. waiting time) but also presenting considerable challenges for the local community (e.g. getting to work on time due to traffic jams, access for ambulances in medical emergencies). The measures addressing such issues range from the introduction of shuttle buses and advanced reservation systems for car parking, to closing off roads during the high season to address the traffic situation in the valleys.

Although high arrival volumes in private or rented cars is a challenge at most destinations, in some, the problems are compounded by the arrival of visitors on coach buses, further exacerbating the crowding effect of people and large vehicles (e.g., the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, Plitvice Lakes). The visibility and number of coaches and tour buses have been amplifying crowding situations.

On islands like Mallorca and Iceland, visitors tend to arrive first by plane, or on cruise ships, where visitors are concentrated heavily at airports and ports before they disperse to other areas on the islands. However, in these cases as well, the arrival by coach and bus (e.g. from the cruise port to the city centre as is the case in Palma) has to be considered in solution measures. The high influx of visitors by cruise ships is also becoming an issue in city destinations like Vienna, where the Danube River connection from Amsterdam to the Danube Delta has continued to increase (pre-pandemic) and can lead to not only spatial but also a temporal concentration (most of the city tours take place between 8:30 and 11.30 am) and thus to potential crowding along these routes, or at chosen attractions.

However, it is not only in rural destinations, but also in urban destinations that the arrival of visitors to specific attractions, including old historic centres, by means of their own vehicle and on coach buses, is presenting an issue. In Lucerne, annual day visitors are estimated to be 8 million, much of which are attributed to coach buses bringing group tourists to this scenic and historic city. These groups of 30-60 visitors passing through the streets are noticeable. This is coupled with the corresponding number of coach buses that park in the heart or in the close periphery of the historic centre. If these group tourists were Free Independent Travellers (FITs), their presence could be more easily absorbed by the city's size and would not lead to the cultural issues currently observed (Table 13 and Table 14).

3.4. Drivers and impacts of unbalanced tourism

3.4.1. Drivers

Increased population growth, better and expanded personal mobility options, digitisation, and wealth changes in emerging economies are some of the megatrends that explain general tourism growth at some of the destinations analysed. However, there are other factors at individual destinations which play an important role in driving unbalanced tourism, and particularly tourism growth in recent years. Some of the notable factors include the higher accessibility of travel including the expansion of low-cost airline routes across Europe, the growing popularity of cruise travel, and proliferation of privately rented accommodation options (such as Airbnb). However, also seemingly opposing developments like the pandemic have contributed to unbalanced tourism changes such as could be observed in the Bay of Lübeck (more Germans than usual have travelled domestically, and overcrowding has also presented a heightened infection risk and thus created a new urgency to find solutions to overcrowding).

Other noteworthy drivers are:

- High accessibility and favourable geographic location (e.g., its central location in the north-south route through Europe and the proximity to mountains make Lucerne a popular destination for bus tours focused on Asian tourists).
- Increased tourism activity due to a film or television show that has been shot in the destination (e.g., popular Italian TV Series *Un passo dal cielo* at Lake Braies in the Dolomites, "Frozen-effect" in Geirangerfjord whose fictional setting, Arendelle, is closely modelled on Norway, *Game of Thrones* in Iceland) but also the influence of social media in presenting the destinations as "must-see" (e.g., iconic Lake Bled on social media).

Table 13 summarises the key driving forces behind the 15 cases and highlights a complex situation at all destinations. The overall contribution or weight of each factor is variable at all destinations. Nonetheless, all identified factors play a part in contributing to unbalanced tourism developments.

3.4.2. Impacts

Similar to the drivers mentioned, there are some general impacts that can be observed in a majority of the cases explored. These include, for example, increased crowding of people (mostly in specific temporal and spatial factors) and infrastructure that reaches capacity limits (e.g., road and parking infrastructure, waste management) leading to challenges with traffic jams and also highly affecting local populations. Additionally, there are more specific impacts that vary between the destination, these also depend on the type of drivers of unbalanced tourism. Table 14 presents an overview of the greatest identified impacts in the examined destinations which are described in more detail in the individual case studies.

- Environmental issues like decreased air quality in the Geirangerfjord area due to intensive cruise tourism.
- Economic impacts in city centres such as an increase in commercial development geared towards the needs of tourists (e.g., cheap souvenir shops, disappearance of smaller and local stores, emergence of big chains). Further, the development of easily accessible sharing economy rentals such as Airbnb has led to a reduction of local long-term rental apartments leading to local populations getting pushed backed from historical centres, destroying those social structures and creating areas more and more resembling open-air museums (e.g., Florence, Palma, Lucerne).
- Social impacts such as undesirable visitor behaviours can be observed in Mallorca, Palma and Iceland, and in the case of group tourism, in the city of Lucerne and the mountain cables ways of Mount Rigi. The affected stakeholders also vary

between the different cases. However, local residents are almost always impacted in some way by the development of unbalanced tourism (e.g., loss of identity and sense of place, gentrification processes, exodus of residents, reduced quality of life, etc.). Furthermore, tourists experience the negative impacts through a reduced quality and authenticity that comes from overcrowded hotspots (e.g., waiting in lines, administrative effort of pre-bookings). However, the quality for visitors seems to be less impacted than the perceived experience of residents. The visitor experience quality is often reported to be slightly or not at all compromised by such tourism developments at destinations. This might also have to do with the expectations that visitors have when visiting popular tourist destinations. A certain tolerance for waiting in lines, traffic jams or experiencing crowded places can be observed. Studies, such as those in the Dolomites linking overcapacities to TripAdvisor reviews could find a negative correlation of visitor satisfaction and an overcrowding event.

It is noteworthy as an outcome of the interview process within this study, that in some destinations the phenomenon of overtourism as defined by academia is not always congruent with how local stakeholders perceive the situation to be. Mostly DMOs appear to be distanced from the term "overtourism", due to its strong and negative connotations with the destination as reported by the media. Thus, DMO representatives are somewhat hesitant to be brought into association with overtourism challenges.

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level

Table 13: Overview of driving factors contributing to unbalanced tourism development

Strong Drivers/ Root Causes	Urban			Coastal			Island			Rural			Mountain		
	Flor- ence	Lu- cerne	Vienna	Lübeck Bay	Gei- ranger- fjord	Palma	Iceland	Mallorca	Malta	Burren and Cliffs of Moher	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ar- dèche	Plitvice Lake	Bled	Dolo- mites (Three Peaks, Lake Braies)	Rigi
Low-cost flights			x			x	x	x	x	x					
Favourable geographical location (in terms of accessibility)	x	x		x		x				x			x		x
Bus tours/Coaches		x				x				x					
Airbnb & private accommodation				x		x	x	x	x						
Film/Series setting					x		x			x				x	
Social Media					x		x		x	x					
Seasonal attractions/events			x	x				x							
Cruise ships	x		x		x	x	x	x	x						
Must-See/Iconic Attractions/Rankings	x		x			x	x			x			x	x	x
Classic tourism area since decades	x	x	x	x		x		x	x		x				x
Others	Very short stays, lack of knowledge about variety of cultural offer		Insufficient management of Danube cruise ports	Narrow beach spaces, seasonality		Foreign real estate investments	Various media reports, devaluation of national currency, volcanic eruption	Increase of residential tourism	Foreign investment, gaming, cultural and educational attraction	UNESCO Geopark	Use of several labels known at least from domestic tourists (Village de caractère, Regional Natural Park, Geopark...)				Expansion Chinese day visitors

Source: Project team, 2022

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level

Table 14: Overview of main impacts of unbalanced tourism development

Impacts	Urban			Coastal			Island			Rural			Mountain		
	Florence	Lucerne	Vienna	Lübeck Bay	Geiranger-fjord	Palma	Iceland	Mallorca	Malta	Burren and Cliffs of Moher	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ar-dèche	Plitvice Lake	Bled	Dolomites (Three Peaks, Lake Braies)	Rigi
Socio-economic															
Increased cost of living		x				x		x	x					x	
Increased real estate prices	x		x			x	x (in the capital)	x	x						
Concentration of tourist shops/"touristification"	x	x		x		x	x	x							x
Physical-infrastructure															
Infrastructure overcapacity		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
People Crowding	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	
Traffic jams		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Pressure to build more tourism infrastructures			x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x			
Partial resentment local population towards tourism	x	x			x	x		x		x	x	x			x
Socio-cultural															
Undesirable Visitor behaviour (noise etc)		x				x	x	x			x			x	x
Reduced visitor experience quality	x	x				x	x	x	x	x		x	x		x
Reduced quality of life for locals/exodus of local residents	x	x	x			x		x					x	x	
Changing neighbourhood structures	x					x	x	x							

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level

Impacts	Urban			Coastal			Island			Rural			Mountain		
	Florence	Lucerne	Vienna	Lübeck Bay	Geirangerfjord	Palma	Iceland	Mallorca	Malta	Burren and Cliffs of Moher	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ar-dèche	Plitvice Lake	Bled	Dolomites (Three Peaks, Lake Braies)	Rigi
Environmental															
Air quality (pollution)					x	x		x							
Noise pollution						x									
Excessive Water resource use/water pollution						x		x	x		x	x	x		
Waste Management issues	x				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Other	Loss of authenticity (souvenirs), normal services and residents in historic centre	Coach busses	Aggressive tourism selling (e.g., Mozart Concerts)	Illegal parking, camping vans		Privatization and commodification of public space for tourist usage; loss of identity and sense of place among residents	Off-road driving, wild recreation uses,	Coastal beach-dune system degradations	No new space available	Biophysical degradation	Biophysical degradation	Biophysical degradations of National Park	Aquatic biodiversity issues	Limited tourism job opportunities in shoulder season	

Source: Project team, 2022

3.4.3. Recent impact of the Covid-19 pandemic

The pandemic has had different impacts on the examined destinations. In general, it can be stated that city destinations have experienced a greater decrease in visitor numbers (e.g., the decrease in visitor numbers reached 90% considering only the City of Florence and 78% in the whole Florentine area, and furthermore 90% of hotels remained closed in 2020).

The contrast between urban and rural tourism development during the pandemic can be illustrated through the case of Florence. While Florence has been experiencing a great loss in visitor numbers, the coastline in Italy has experienced a small increase and could overall profit from domestic travel. Other rural destinations (e.g., Dolomites, Mount Rigi) could also profit from the demand for nature and space during the pandemic and have reported relatively smaller losses than other destinations during COVID-19. Monts d'Ardèche for example experienced only a small loss of visitors (approx. -14% compared to 2019) and the reduction of the number of international visitors was compensated by domestic tourists. However, it could be noted that peaks and lows in terms of frequencies were accentuated.

The strong increase of interest in outdoor activities has also led to pressure in natural areas located close to urban areas, as could be observed for example in Iceland. Some of these areas have been downgraded in the environmental assessment by the Icelandic Environmental Agency due to a lack of preparation for the rapid changes due to Covid-19. On the contrary, in traditionally popular sites further away from the capital, partly less pressure and thus improved conditions were reported due to the decrease of international tourism. Furthermore, some other rural destinations that are more secluded and dependant on international tourists (e.g., cruise tourists to Geirangerfjord) were also strongly hit by the pandemic.

The above-described impacts (e.g., tourist oriented commercial development) became even more evident with the pandemic. The shops in the centres (mostly souvenir shops) which are not catering to residents have experienced closures in many cases. However, the trend towards more balanced tourism development could still profit from the current situation and remains promising as the pandemic has made these negative impacts painfully noticeable.

The pandemic has also impacted the tourism workforce. For example, in Malta, despite employment support measures provided by the government, immigrant populations working in the tourism industry have left the country. Therefore, a temporary workforce shortage may be expected when tourism activities resume.

The high uncertainty of future tourism development (e.g., travel restrictions, regulations, visitor behaviours) remains a major challenge for all analysed destinations. In many destinations however plans for more sustainable development have been reinforced rather than impeded.

3.5. Solutions Approaches to Unbalanced Tourism

Although none of the cases analysed have a "perfect solution approach" to address unbalanced tourism, individually and collectively they offer lessons that are transferable to other destinations. All of the 15 destinations have a clear tourism management system in place with key stakeholders, such as DMOs and local authorities involved in various roles and responsibilities, which enables a good foundation for discourse and concrete management strategies to address unbalanced tourism. Additionally, the key tourism stakeholders of the 15 case destinations all envision actively continuing their work together to address unbalanced tourism. In this context, of the destinations analysed all have a 2030 development strategy, or something similar, implemented. Such strat-

egies and their corresponding action plans mostly aim to achieve balanced tourism development with clear objectives in place to manage the impacts of recent tourism issues (Table 14). However, how each destination specifically addresses this varies.

Table 15: Common approaches to address unbalanced tourism at destinations

	Destination	Laws and Policies	Key stakeholders cooperate	New Tourism Infrastructure Developments	Capacity Limits at some sites	Dispersion Strategies	Digital Solutions	Others
Urban	Florence	x	x			x	x	Enhanced reservation system to attractions
	Lucerne	x	x	x		x	x	
	Vienna	x	x	x	x	x		
Coastal	Bay of Lübeck	x	x	x	x	x	x	Create more space for pedestrians instead of cars
	Geirangerfjord	x	x			x	x	Green Shipping Programme, VR Experience of the area
	Palma	x	x	x	x	x	x	Online marketplace for tourism businesses, temporary prohibition of alcohol sale and consumption in public places
Island	Iceland	x	x	x	x	x	x	Iceland Academy and Pledge, Tourism start-up accelerator, Tourism Fund
	Mallorca	x	x	x	x	x	x	Sustainable Tourism Tax, Better Winter Strategy
	Malta		x					Malta Tourism Observatory planned, rebranding, focus towards different categories of tourists
Rural	Burren and Cliffs of Moher		x	x	x	x	x	Pricing strategies, encouraging longer stays
	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche		x		x	x	x	"Flux Vision Tourism" Data gathering
	Plitvice Lake	x	x		x	x		Pricing strategies
Mountain	Bled	x	x	x				Encouraging longer stays
	Dolomites, Val Pusteria		x		x		x	Scientific assessment of flows
	Rigi		x	x				

Source: Project team, 2022

At all destinations, stakeholders strive to clearly cooperate to achieve positive and harmonious co-existence between residents and visitors via diverse governance mechanisms and the halting of exponential touristification of the destination. An interesting case is Vienna, where efforts are currently undertaken applying targeted marketing to match the city's DNA and tourism offers. Destinations are gearing towards increased data driven tourism monitoring to enable effective management of visitors as well as products. This still seems difficult for the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, and may be because the monitoring solutions were only recently implemented at this location. Furthermore, in the case of Monts d'Ardèche, pricing strategies were only recently implemented, and so budget and practical questions seem to be hindering more extensive in-house management of data. The two Switzerland cases, namely Lucerne and Mount Rigi, are worth special mention. Among these cases, a deep-rooted cultural value system around participative democracy means that stakeholders of diverging interests and levels of power can find ways and mechanisms to come to solutions addressing unbalanced tourism at the destinations.

3.5.1. Laws and Regulations

Apart from a few destinations (Table 15), most destinations have implemented legally binding rules and regulations to address unbalanced tourism developments. In Florence, regulations govern the opening of new food and beverage stores, to control advertising in shop display windows in order to create a more harmonious and authentic feel of the commercial establishments in the city.

In Majorca, the *Plan de Intervención en Ámbitos Turísticos de Mallorca* (Plan of Intervention in Tourist Areas of Majorca, PIAT) regulates the accommodation offers on the island. It includes a maximum capacity of guest beds on the island of 430,000, and maximum tourism densities depending on the type of area. For the city of Palma individual regulations apply due to its special characteristic as the capital and a place of living for most of the island's inhabitants. This includes the limiting of new hotel buildings, the prohibition of Airbnb rentals in private apartments and the definition of a maximum touristic density for the city's territory set at 8 beds per hectare. Apart from this, in Palma and other parts of Mallorca, the sale and consumption of alcohol is regulated to better manage visitors who cause noise and other nuisance.

At Geirangerfjord, the Norwegian government adopted laws that will ban polluting cruise ships from entering the area. From 2026 onwards only zero-emission ships may enter the UNESCO World Heritage Fjords and from 2030 this law will apply to all Norwegian Fjords.

Iceland presently has a moratorium of new hotel development. In Reykjavik, private rentals via Airbnb are limited to a maximum of 90 days. Apart from this, the city has introduced a regulation of traffic by designating pickup spots for tourist buses to reduce bus traffic in residential streets. In addition, very recently a new legislation has been approved regulating the operation of private tour operators on public land.

3.5.2. Policies

Following legally binding regulations, additional specific tourism policies are implemented at destinations to address unbalanced developments. Such examples are highlighted below.

In Florence, opening hours of tourism attractions and shops are extended to avoid crowding and rushes around "common" closing times. Similar policies are also implemented at the Cliffs of Moher to disperse crowds.

In Lucerne, by the end of 2021, an official policy by the City will monitor short-term private rental developments (e.g., via Airbnb) to avoid touristification and to maintain a sound balance between resident and visitor numbers.

Adjusting the cost of attraction seems to be a common policy at some destinations. For example, at Geiranger Fjord, a pilot project to introduce a tourist tax is forthcoming to enable paying for more tourism facilities (the local community has a limited budget with just over 200 residents in the area). Also, dynamic transportation infrastructure pricing (tolls) on roads, and on waterways for ships, has been implemented. Dynamic pricing is also applied in the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, to disperse visitors around peak hours. Similar initiatives are observable in Vienna at the Chocolate Museum and Schönbrunn Palace.

In contrast, at Plitvice Lakes, the cost of visiting the park is threefold more during the summer peak visitor months as opposed to during the shoulder seasons. In the summer season, price increases have also been combined with an online entry reservation system, where daily entrance has been restricted to 1,000 entries per hour during peak visiting hours (11:00-14:00).

Policies that set limits to the number of visitor arrivals are also common at some destinations. For example, in the Bay of Lübeck police close full parking lots by ordinance to bar access to overcrowded beaches. Similarly, in hotspots of the Dolomites, capacity regulating policies are in place. For example, in high season the road to the popular Lake Braies is closed for private cars and a shuttle bus with prior reservation must be taken. Furthermore, parking spaces around natural attraction also fall under such a ticketing system. In Palma, cruise ships of certain large sizes must embark further away from the city (at Porto Pi) to avoid large crowd concentrations in Palma. It is also planned to limit the number of daily cruise ships in the corresponding ports.

The island of Mallorca has various environmental policies and actively promotes more public transport use to reduce private and rented car use. It has also adopted policies to increase renewable energy production.

At the Burren and Cliffs of Moher various policies have been implemented to manage unbalanced tourism. Policies are wide ranging and include mandatory overnight stays in the visitors' package in County Clare, withdrawal or conditional approval of licenses for day tour operator, as well as capping the number of visitors by setting capacity limits, amongst other measures.

In many destinations, the impact of unbalanced tourism growth was particularly evident in the area of traffic and transport. Especially in urban destinations, forward mobility planning is indispensable. This is where the sustainable urban mobility planning (SUMP) concept can help¹⁴. The following SUMP guidance documents can be helpful regarding managing the tourism flows in a sustainable manner:

- Mobility Plan for a polycentric region¹⁵:
- Planning for More Resilient and Robust Urban Mobility¹⁶:

3.5.3. Stakeholder Cooperation

At most destinations, key stakeholders, as documented in the individual cases, closely cooperate to strive towards solutions for unbalanced tourism. However, the process is vastly different between most destinations. In Switzerland, the cases of Lucerne and

¹⁴ Please see <https://www.eltis.org/mobility-plans/sump-concept>

¹⁵ Please see <https://www.eltis.org/sites/default/files/trainingmaterials/polysump-sump-guidelines-final.pdf>

¹⁶ Please see https://www.eltis.org/sites/default/files/sump_topic-guide_planning_for_more_resilient_and_robust_urban_mobility_online_version.pdf

Rigi both highlight the complexity of a participative democracy process in tourism planning and management amongst the stakeholders.

The regularity of exchange and the formality and nature of cooperation is also variable amongst the destinations. For example, in Florence monthly meetings occur of the steering board consisting of stakeholders from different levels of administration, organisations, chamber of commerce, research institutions, etc.

An interesting case, in this regard, is Bled, which reinvented the role and profile of the DMO enabling for clearer alignment between municipal and tourism development goals. A series of sustainable development action goals have been defined to preserve local environmental quality, as well as investments in public infrastructures (transport, waste management, and visitor facilities). Bled also invests in repositioning the destination (from “must see” to “must experience”) through more responsible marketing which includes a variety of specific goals such as increasing the length of stay

Destinations where UNESCO is a stakeholder appear to have interesting management structures in place as well, highlighting how stakeholders from private, public, and non-profit organisations can cooperate on specific projects where a clear common vision is shared. For example, at Geirangerfjord in Norway, stakeholders in the broader region of the UNESCO World Heritage adopted a “Green Fjord” Plan to proactively seek out sustainable outcomes for the area. The Fjord Ranger Programme seeks to increase and enhance communication in the area about various issues including tourism.

Several case destinations also cooperate with scientific institutions to establish data driven management policies. For example, in the Dolomites, UNESCO, Vodafone (a telecommunication company), TripAdvisor, ISTAT (Italian Statistics Office) and the Bank of Italy undertook a rigorous scientific study to assess visitor flow patterns to sites at the Dolomites under pressure. This resulted in the definition of various effective measures (vehicle restrictions, access limits and parking reservation) to some areas under pressure at the destination. Similar studies are observable in Lucerne, Vienna and elsewhere.

3.5.4. New tourism infrastructures as dispersion strategies

The creation of new facilities appears to be less common as a solution to disperse visitors than other measures (Table 15). Nonetheless, at some destinations transport and visitor infrastructure is addressed. For example, at the Burren and Cliffs of Moher a specific traffic management plan is underway while other measures implemented promote food tastings at local farms to diversify the tourism offering and disperse flows. Also, Bled has considerably upgraded infrastructure by constructing bypass roads and remote parking lots to remove pressures from the lake basin. In addition, the local sewage system was upgraded and efforts have been made towards achieving a zero-waste municipality. Elsewhere, in Vienna, specific new tourism spaces were created to disperse visitors (Belvedere, Sonnwendviertel) besides promoting all year around off-season cultural programmes.

The promotion of off-season events and attractions is also implemented at other destinations. For example, the City of Lucerne developed a light festival in winter, named LILU, to create more tourism activities in this low season.

3.5.5. Other Dispersion Strategies

Promoting areas that are at a distance from key attractions to disperse masses is a common measure at most destinations. For example, in the Bay Lübeck, the hinterland and more rural areas are promoted. In Florence, less known parts of the city are promoted to steer people elsewhere. The Monts d’Ardèche Regional Natural Parc developed an app gathering trekking routes to encourage visitors to explore less well-known parts of the mountains.

Another common dispersion strategy at some destinations is the off-season promotion of attractions. Geirangerfjord, Vienna, Lucerne, Mallorca, Bled, and Plitvice Lakes actively implement this as a component of their solutions to unbalanced tourism. In addition to marketing Iceland as a year-long destination, visitors are also encouraged to travel all around the island to disperse visitors from overcrowded spots in the Capital region and southern areas.

Additionally, in Palma the establishment of a new touristic route is planned, one further outside of the city centre. As one foreseen solution, *Fundació Turisme Palma 365* has planned a new project using touristic signage. In this plan, a splitting up of the city into 5 touristic routes is foreseen, which all start at public bus stops and do not overlap. The overall objective of the implementation of these routes is to incentivise arrival by public transport, a greater dispersal of the visitors outside of the city centre, and thus, an activation of the less touristic neighbourhoods of Palma.

3.5.6. Digital Solutions

All destinations have implemented some set of measures to address unbalanced tourism developments in recent years. However, not all destinations are applying the same approaches and technologies, and several are also in pilot phases.

The development of mobile phone applications appears to be a common solution to inform visitors about a destination and also to provide some helpful hints on where to go to experience areas in which less crowding may occur. In some destinations, the Apps are used to monitor visitor flows or assist in data gathering for crowd management. Specific examples of such Apps include the following:

- *FeelFlorence App* “pop up info” has been developed for when individuals approach within 200m of a crowded area. This App provides suggestions for other activities that are available in the meantime, as well as general suggestions for different groups of visitors and lengths of stay.
- Digital visitor card in Lucerne helps manage visitors in time and space (for over-nighting guests only) and an *iparking app*, available for coach buses, helps in the reservation of bus parking space in advance.
- *Ivie App* is a digital bus management system that is currently piloted in Vienna (limited contingent of entry tickets to the city during Advent Season), also available is a digital concierge for city explorers.
- Lübeck Bay has a *Beach Ticker App* that assembles data about visitor density at beaches and related parking lots to help visitors determine where space remains and has been recently amended to provide beach safety information. Similarly, first Palma and now the entire island of Majorca have introduced a Beach app during Covid-19 indicating the current level of congestion at popular beaches.
- The *Welcome Palma Web-App* targets visitors to help with flow management by recommending alternate attractions that are away from crowded hotspots in the city. Up until now, this was exclusively directed at cruise ship passengers. However, the app is currently being modified and a new version is due to be published in spring 2022 which will be targeted at all visitors.
- The Regional Natural Park of Monts d’Ardèche gathers data on visitor flows using sensors in cooperation with Orange (a telecommunication company and the regional Departmental tourism authority).

3.5.7. Other initiatives

Each of the 15 case destinations highlights a unique combination of solution approaches to address unbalanced tourism development. While none stand out as uniquely innovative per se, it is the combination and sets of approaches planned or implemented that provide important lessons learnt for other destinations that may be confronted with a form of overtourism or unbalanced tourism development.

In urban areas, such as Florence, the local resident population has partly deserted the core historic centre due to the touristification of the area. In Lucerne, this process is feared but not yet documented. Locals tend to resent coach tourists, who visibly crowd in and outside small local shops, block narrow streets in the old historic city, and arrive on buses that cause various traffic inefficiencies.

Majorca's sustainable tourism tax collects funds for investments in several ecological conservation, restoration, and social projects. For example, investments are concentrated in areas where the local environment has been degraded from tourism, and target not only environmental projects, but also social projects. Furthermore, tax revenue is used for promoting tourism product diversification and measures to reduce strong seasonal job fluctuations. Funds are also allocated to scientific research projects in tourism, as well as to initiatives that provide additional training opportunities to increase the employability of tourism workers.

The Iceland Academy is a website¹⁷ that informs and educates tourists on how to be more responsible on the island. The "Icelandic Pledge" is a voluntary code of conduct for tourists that can be signed online where a commitment can be made to behave responsibly in Iceland. This initiative also extends to work with journalists and influencers to achieve more responsible visitor behaviours. A similar initiative exists in the Dolomites Italy known as "Dolomeyes".

Elsewhere, in addition to some of the initiatives mentioned above, at the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, important investments are also made to educate both locals and visitors to the particularities and conservation needs of these sites. In several of the case destinations, there are also initiatives that target residents specifically, since resentment among the local population is common to some degree at all destinations (Table 14).

3.5.8. Monitoring unbalanced tourism

All 15 case studies systematically collect, analyse, and publish data on classic economic aspects of tourism although not at the same frequency, scale and quality that may relate to specific groups such as day visitor's in comparison to overnights. Classical visitor information mostly relates to arrivals, overnights and statistics gathered at specific attractions and embarkations at ports and airports. Some destinations have specific indicators as a sign to oversee crowding. In the Bay of Lübeck for example, seasonality is calculated based on standard official tourism statistics.

The monitoring of unbalanced tourism, however, is viable and highlights different approaches. It seems a lack of a comparable set of indicators for unbalanced tourism does not exist as each destination implements a very specific set of performance indicators to oversee tourism. They often tend to include some indicators regarding satisfaction, addressing resident sentiment or satisfaction surveys and as well as those related to the visitor experience.

Several destinations have tourism observatory or dashboards implemented (for example, Iceland) that aim to collect data about the broader socio-economic and sometimes environmental aspects of tourism. Some destinations such as Rigi and Lucerne are currently planning, or are in early phases of implementing, such systems.

Destinations such as Bled aim to reposition themselves as "sustainable and green". In Bled, in this context, a certification system is in place. Thanks to the Green Destinations Standards (GSTC accreditation) the destination is now also working towards establishing a monitoring framework to oversee tourism in a more holistic way. Initiatives in Majorca are in the process of implementing a Sustainable Tourism Observatory.

¹⁷ <https://visiticeland.com/iceland-academy>

Destinations that have UNESCO as a key stakeholder seem to have elaborate indicator sets compared to other destinations, as the organisation requires regular reports to guarantee appropriate management of listed areas. This is the case at Geirangerfjord and at the Dolomites. At the Burren and Cliffs of Moher, the destination additionally also adopted the Cape Town Declaration of Responsible Tourism in 2020 which additionally requires specific monitoring of tourism. At the Dolomites, the destination is also under the monitoring system of the "Sustainable Tourism Observatory of South Tyrol", which belongs to the UNWTO's International Network of Sustainable Tourism Observatories (INSTO). With this system in place, 29 specific indicators require monitoring, relating to visitors, residents, and the environment.

National Parks authorities at the case destinations also contribute to the management of important data on tourism. For example, at Plitvice Lakes National Park an elaborate set of visitor-use management indicators aim to oversee unbalanced tourism. At Monts d'Ardèche various stakeholders at different levels collect visitor statistics, which is increasingly generated from mobile phone devices, as it enables distinguishing between visitors and residents. The use of mobile phone sourced big data seems to be a new pathway coming forward at other destinations, such as Malta where it is applied to oversee tourism at destinations.

The regularity of information published is highly variable at the destinations. Classical tourism statistics are commonly aggregated monthly but more complex data about environmental indicators vary and may be less regular.

4. Task C: Establishing an annotated compendium of currently existing intelligence on overtourism

4.1. Methodological approach

The goal of this task is the aggregation of the information gathered through Task A, B, and D, into a comprehensive, annotated compendium. The output of Task C is targeted at stakeholders in destinations that are (potentially) impacted by unbalanced tourism growth. The focus is laid on policy makers, destination managers, public and private tourism entities.

The compendium provides scientific findings on the definition, background as well as root causes and impacts of overtourism (Task A). Furthermore, it presents relevant information on prevention and mitigation strategies and measures (Task B) and indicator frameworks that can be applied to understand, monitor, and manage overtourism (derived from Task A and Task D). Thus, the compendium enables and supports relevant stakeholders in the process of identifying and implementing appropriate solutions and mitigation measures for the prevention and alleviation of overtourism.

4.2. Collection of information basis

The information displayed in the compendium is based on the literature review of Task A as well as the outputs of Task B and D. An internal workshop consisting of the study core team members was held to discuss the information collected (from Task A, B and D) and to highlight the aspects and publications considered most important for the purpose of the compendium.

After these working steps took place, the structure of the compendium presented in the project inception report was slightly adjusted. The consortium came to the conclusion that the new structure is more appropriate as it provides a better basis for presenting the recommended publications and for developing a concise and user-oriented document. The introduced changes are set out and explained in detail in an explanatory note in Appendix 7.

4.3. Structure of the compendium and first draft

The structure of the compendium aims to ensure user-friendliness, target group appropriability and to be context-specific. In order to guide the reader and provide an overview on central aspects of unbalanced tourism growth, the compendium is divided into main chapters and subchapters.

Each (sub)chapter consists of an introductory text on the relevant outputs of the study (results of Tasks A, B, and D) and a comprehensive list of recommended publications for stakeholders (including scientific articles, books, book chapters, online resources and guidelines of relevant institutions). In addition, some chapters are complemented by references to the case studies of good practice conducted within this project.

The presentation of the selected publications contains the following information:

- Reference
- Short summary of the publication
- Key findings and most interesting aspects
- Keywords
- Online link to the publication
- Availability (open or restricted access)
- Destination focus

The final output consists of a compendium available online including links to important resources such as external tools, analyses and papers. The overall structure of the compendium is outlined in Box 1 below.

Box 1: Structure of the compendium

How to use this compendium	
1. Introduction into unbalanced tourism growth	
1.1	Background and definitions
1.2	Causes and impacts
1.3	Unbalanced tourism growth at heritage sites and in protected areas
2. Covid-19 and unbalanced tourism growth	
3. Measures and solution approaches for unbalanced tourism growth	
3.1	Strategies, guidelines and tools
3.2	Innovative approaches
3.3	ICT and social media
4. Indicators	
4.1	Coping with success
4.2	Impact and possible policy responses
4.3	Measuring overtourism
4.4	Carrying capacity
5. Glossary and concepts related to unbalanced tourism growth	
5.1	Overcrowding
5.2	Resilience
5.3	Degrowth
5.4	Tourismphobia
5.5	Carrying Capacity
5.6	Other theoretical concepts related with tourism impacts
6. Good practice, destination type specific case studies	
6.1	Urban Destinations
6.2	Rural Destinations
6.3	Coastal Destinations
6.4	Island Destinations
6.5	Mountain Destinations
References	

Source: Project team, 2022

4.4. Feedback loop and finalisation

The draft of the compendium underwent an in-depth quality control process by the project team. Furthermore, the dissemination of the compendium draft to the three experts involved throughout the project allowed for an additional assessment on the accessibility, user-friendliness and completeness of information provided in the document.

5. Task D: Proposing a set of overtourism indicators that would help tourism destinations to detect and measure risks of overtourism

5.1. Methodological approach

5.1.1. The three-tiered indicator system

The development of the indicator framework is based on the findings of the literature review of methodological approaches (Task A, particularly sections 2.4 and 2.5) and the findings of appropriate local indicator choices via the case studies (Task B).

Figure 13: Indicator framework

Source: Project team, 2022

One of the results of the analyses undertaken in the literature review (Task A), the case studies (Task B), as well as the stakeholder workshops (Task E), is the multi-dimensionality of the impacts of overtourism. As such, any overtourism monitoring framework needs to account for various impact fields. The main conclusion to be drawn from the literature on overtourism indicators (see section 2.4) is the importance of combining global indicators with regional territorial indicators, as well as with site- and problem-specific indicators. Apart from the theoretical desirability of certain indicators, data availability is a key challenge to consider when selecting core indicators.

As such, the indicator framework is composed of the three-tiered system, combining global trends and patterns, with regional, and local indicators.

1. Tier 1: Measuring global (demand) trends that act as driving forces for overtourism. These indicators cover driving forces and should be available at EU or national level.
2. Tier 2: Measuring tourism pressure on the regional level (NUTS2/3). These regional indicators enable a comparison of tourism developments along similar destinations (e.g. between island regions). This can provide insights into whether a particular region is more exposed to overtourism than its peers.
3. Tier 3: Measuring tourism pressure and actual impacts locally. A destination- or even site-specific approach is needed to assess the local risk or actual occurrence of overtourism.

The selection of tier one indicators (global demand trends) is based on the literature review and focuses on indicators which describe the changes in demand trends (such as growth in international arrivals, availability of low-cost airlines etc.). These indicators serve to measure a general risk of overtourism in sensitive destinations.

Tier 1: Measuring global (demand) trends that act as driving forces for overtourism, derived from the literature review (Task A). In detail, the tier one indicators should measure:

- Growth of international tourism in general, with a particular focus on the development of source markets from emerging economies. These demand segments contain many first-time travellers to a given destination, with a consequent focus on iconic sites, such as UNESCO World Heritage Sites.
- Passenger numbers of low-cost airlines and charter flights. These tend to focus on easily accessible destinations with airports and transport large numbers of tourists in relatively short periods of time.
- Passenger numbers of cruise companies. Even more than charter flights and low-cost airlines, the business model of most cruise companies is geared towards very high volumes of tourists. In addition, cruise ships can only call at ports of sufficient size, thus almost inevitably leading to high visitor concentrations.
- Indicating general risk of overtourism in sensitive destinations. This entails an overview of accommodation and attraction points of interest on selected territories.

The tier two indicators (regional indicators) are derived from the carrying capacity framework (please see Appendix 3 for the methodological approach) developed by Schuh et al (2021), as identified in the literature review and reported under Task A.3 (see section 2.4). These indicators (Figure 13) combine an exposure component (an indicator measuring tourism inflows, such as arrivals per inhabitant) and a territorial sensitivity component (an indicator measuring tourism impacts, such as employment in the tourism sector) into a **bivariate indicator**. The selection of exposure and sensitivity components is informed by the findings of the case studies in regards to observed impacts and the findings of the literature, particularly on overtourism indicators (see Table 6). The selection of indicators was, further, validated by the workshop series undertaken as part of Task E.

Figure 14: A theoretical concept of tourism impact

Source: Schuh et al, 2021

Tier 2: Measuring tourism pressure on the regional & local levels (NUTS2 and NUTS3), derived from the literature review (Task A), the case studies (Task B) and validated in the workshops (Task E). The tier two indicators combine "classical regional" tourist indicators with bivariate indicators developed within the carrying capacity framework of Schuh et al (2021).

- Importance of tourism for the local or regional economy (% of gross value added (GVA)¹⁸ and % of employment)
- Tourism intensity & density
- Growth in tourist arrivals/nights spent

¹⁸ Eurostat offers GVA and employment data for the NACE sectors G-I and G-J, however, not for the individual sub-sectors. This covers economic activities closely associated with tourism (such as accommodation). Sectors: wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication.

- Indicator pairs combining the tourism exposure and the territorial sensitivity based on the carrying capacity framework developed by Schuh et al (2021).

The tier three indicators (local indicators) are informed by the findings of the case studies. Indicators used in the case study regions as part of their tourism monitoring systems form a pool of potential indicators which can be used depending on the destination's specificities.

Tier 3: Measuring tourism pressure and actual impacts locally, derived from the case study findings (Task B). A destination – or even site – specific approach is needed to assess the local risk or actual occurrence of overtourism. This means that pressure indicators need to be refined and that state, and especially impact, indicators need to be added to the analysis. Based on the literature review and the case study analyses, the following key issues need to be taken into account and measured, where possible:

- Size of the actual "tourist" area in absolute figures and in relation to the overall destination area. Ideally, tourism density and intensity should then be calculated for those highly impacted areas.
- Seasonality is a key issue of overtourism. Tourism density and intensity should be measured separately for peak month(s) and the low season.
- Day visitors are an important driver of overtourism. Therefore, their numbers (in absolute terms and in relation to overnight tourists) should be added when calculating tourism intensity (called "Tourism Penetration Rate" by Peeters et al. 2018) and density. Furthermore, their spatial and temporal visitation patterns as well as their spending in relation to overnight tourists should be measured, if possible. Collecting data on day visitors may be one of the biggest challenges when monitoring overtourism. Using big data (e.g., tracking visitor movements through mobile phones) instead of, or in addition to, conducting surveys might open up new opportunities.
- The rising share of private accommodation offered on platforms such as Airbnb contributes to spreading overtourism into previously unaffected urban neighbourhoods. Their share of the overall accommodation offer and their spatial distribution should therefore be measured.
- The "sentiments" of both residents and tourists as an important impact of overtourism must be taken into account more systematically when managing an affected destination. This can be done either by direct surveys or by using data from online platforms such as TripAdvisor or Instagram.

Working with indicators generally implies a simplification of a more complex local situation. Therefore, it must be kept in mind that single indicators cannot cover the phenomenon of overtourism alone and that normally a combination of indicators is needed to get a realistic picture of the tourism development in a destination. For instance, passenger numbers of low-cost airlines and charter flights can be regarded as an indicator for the accessibility of a destination. However, the pax number of low-cost airlines and charter flights include non-touristic travel such as visiting families, business and commuting to work. Therefore, the destination's context must always be considered when interpreting such data.

5.1.2. Selection and validation of indicators

The selection of indicators was assessed along technical and content related principles. Particular attention was paid to the tier two indicators (i.e. the regional indicators) as this set is designed to be transferable across destinations. As such, the project team conducted in-depth research into the data sources available at EU level for all identified indicators. The robustness of the indicator pairs with sufficient data availability across EU-27 was tested via a correlation analysis between the exposure and sensitivity components.

The **technical principles** considered for the development of indicators were:

- Indicators are commonly accepted/well-justified by scientific literature and empirical studies (based on literature review)
- Indicators should be available at territorial resolution relevant to each tier
- Indicators are measurable and data is easily available

It is necessary that indicators appropriately cover the diverse backgrounds and starting points of the destinations, this includes consideration of territorial specificity and different socio-economic contexts, among others. In addition to this, providing adequately comprehensive insight on the various impacts of overtourism are considered. As such, the following set of **content-related principles** was applied:

- Indicators are relevant for all types of destinations and, at the same time, they capture the diversity of territorial specificities as well as specific socio-economic and tourism situations.
- Indicators should cover all three pillars of sustainability (economic, environmental and socio-cultural) in order to depict all facets of the impact of overtourism.
- The indicator list should be comprehensive enough to enable destinations to choose the most relevant indicators (following appropriate guidance).

Furthermore, the workshops undertaken in Task E featured practical application of the proposed tier two indicators to validate the overall selection. The approach to the validation process is presented in section 6.3. The focus on the validation of the tier two indicators via the workshop setting was undertaken due to their relatively higher complexity than the tier one and tier three indicators.

5.2. Development of overtourism indicators

This sub-task develops a concrete list of indicators to help stakeholders manage and monitor overtourism and its impacts along the three-tiered framework outlined in the methodological approach (section 5.1).

5.2.1. Tier one indicators: global demand trends

5.2.1.1. Selection of indicators

The tier one indicators measure global demand trends and may be measured at EU or Member State level. Of the indicators and themes highlighted in section 5.1, the project team analysed available data sources at Member State and EU level to assess their relevance and appropriateness. Based on general available data and the literature findings of section 2.4, the project team proposes the following set of tier one indicators:

- International arrivals, differentiated by country of origin to the extent possible in the country of analysis.
- Passenger numbers of (low-cost) airlines.
- Number of cruise ship tourist arrivals.

Depending on the type of destination, some of these indicators may be more or less relevant. For example, taking stock of the number of cruise ship tourists in Europe, or docking frequency at a specific Member State, is only relevant for destinations with some reliance on cruise ship tourism. However, the purpose of these indicators is to provide insights into developments at EU-27 or national level, which approximate large tourism demand-drivers.

5.2.1.2. Data sources and replicability

These indicators can be collected at national level from national statistical offices. This data is usually provided as part of the tourism statistics available from these sources.

However, depending on the specificities of the data collection of the national statistical offices, some of these indicators may not be available in the specified form. This primarily concerns airplane passengers. Potentially, the statistical office may not differentiate between “conventional” and “low-cost” carriers when counting airline passengers. In this case, it is advisable to take the number of airplane passengers as an approximation.

Conversely, when applying these indicators at EU-level to measure global trends potentially affecting a destination, several aspects should be considered. These aspects include limitations in terms of scope or data availability resulting from the higher level of analysis (EU-27 compared to national level). Potential data sources and their characteristics are presented in Table 16.

Table 16: Data sources tier one indicators

Name	Characteristics	Source
Arrivals at tourist accommodation establishments	Covers EU-27 and/or individual Member States. Available in monthly intervals, with recent data available. Can be differentiated by type of accommodation according to NACE Rev.2 Data can be differentiated into <i>domestic</i> and <i>foreign</i> tourists.	Eurostat [TOUR_OCC_ARM]
Number of trips by mode of transport	Covers EU-27 and/or individual Member States. Available in annual intervals. Data can be differentiated into <i>domestic, outbound, domestica and outbound, and all countries in the world.</i> Data can be differentiated into mode of transportation (<i>total, air, land – total, railways, and buses and coaches</i>)	Eurostat [TOUR_DEM_TTR]

Source: Project team, 2022

Additional, and more specific, indicators on EU-27 cruise passenger volumes as well as passenger volumes in low-cost airlines are available via paid statistical services. These indicators are usually collected from the reporting of the economic operators. As such, the indicators are usually available for relatively recent years.

5.2.2. Tier two indicators: measuring tourism pressure on the regional & local levels

5.2.2.1. Selection of indicators

The tier two indicators are composed of the classical overtourism regional indicators, as identified in Task A.3, and the exposure-sensitivity framework developed by Schuh et al (2021) to monitor overtourism impacts. In the exposure-sensitivity framework, bivariate indicators are constructed using an exposure component (measuring the tourism incidence in the region) and the sensitivity component (measuring potential impacts of overtourism).

The exposure indicators are available at NUTS2 level from Eurostat and feature high territorial coverage – i.e. they cover most EU regions (see Table 17). The selection of these exposure indicators stems from the literature review, focusing on available and robust options. Some of the territorial sensitivity components are available at NUTS3 level. As such, NUTS3 level exposure indicators are preferable to gain deeper insights into the comparative performance of regions. However, as tourism data is not available at NUTS3 level, the NUTS2 data was regionalised using the approach described in the

following section and Appendix 3. With the expected publication of NUTS3 level tourism data by Eurostat, this regionalisation approach may not be necessary in the future.

Table 17: Exposure indicators (Tier 2)

Indicator name	Methodology	Source	Territorial level
Tourism intensity (arrivals)	Number of arrivals/inhabitants	NUTS2: ÖIR, Eurostat NUTS3: ÖIR, based on Eurostat and Open Street Map (OSM)	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Tourism density (arrivals)	Number of arrivals/surface area	NUTS2: ÖIR, Eurostat NUTS3: ÖIR, based on Eurostat and OSM	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Tourism intensity (bed-nights)	Number of bed-nights/inhabitant	NUTS2: ÖIR, Eurostat NUTS3: ÖIR, based on Eurostat and OSM	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Tourism density (bed-nights)	Number of bed-nights/surface area	NUTS2: ÖIR, Eurostat NUTS3: ÖIR, based on Eurostat and OSM	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Growth in intensity (bed-nights or arrivals)	Percentage change between 2015 and 2019	NUTS2: ÖIR, Eurostat NUTS3: ÖIR, based on Eurostat and OSM	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Growth in density (bed-nights or arrivals)	Percentage change between 2015 and 2019	NUTS2: ÖIR, Eurostat NUTS3: ÖIR, based on Eurostat and OSM	NUTS2 and NUTS3

Source: Project team, 2022

The following sensitivity indicators can be matched with the exposure indicators at NUTS2 or NUTS3 level to form composite indicators. This “matching” can be undertaken using bivariate mapping or scatterplots to visualise patterns and highlight “outlier” regions.

The listed indicators are available as timeseries between the intervals, enabling a dynamic comparison with exposure indicators. These indicators are readily available from Eurostat. Some additional territorial components were identified as relevant, but lack data comprehensively at EU-27 level. This concerns particularly social and quality of life dimensions, as reported data is either significantly outdated (such as in Eurostat crime statistics) or not comprehensively available at regional level (such as poverty statistics). The findings of the case studies on the impacts of overtourism were used to provide a general assessment of the relevance of each tier two indicator. This selection was validated as part of the workshop series (see section 6.3) via a stakeholder driven systemic picture analysis.

Table 18: Sensitivity indicators (Tier 2)

Indicator name	Methodology	Source	Territorial level
Tourist capacity	Number of bed-places per inhabitant	Eurostat	NUTS2
Air travel intensity	Number of passengers at closest airport	Eurostat	NUTS2
Economic significance of tourism	Share of GVA of tourism-related sectors of total GVA	Eurostat	NUTS3
Labour market significance of tourism	Share of employment in tourist sector of total employment	Eurostat, DG AGRI	NUTS2
Net migration	Average net migration rate	Eurostat	NUTS3

Indicator name	Methodology	Source	Territorial level
Accessibility	Potential multimodal accessibility	Spiekermann & Wegener, Urban and Regional Research	NUTS3
Emissions	Emissions of CO ₂ per capita (tonnes)	JRC LUISA	NUTS2
Water consumption	Freshwater consumption litres/day/capita	JRC LUISA	NUTS2
Surface sealing	Surface area used for residential and commercial activities, as per ESTAT LUCAS data	Eurostat	NUTS2

Source: Project team, 2022

A correlation analysis between the selection of exposure and the sensitivity component of the NUTS2/3 data was undertaken to ensure the robustness of the proposed indicators. The results of this assessment are presented in Appendix 5.

The list of tier two overtourism indicators are presented below. All indicators are developed in both a static and a dynamic variant. In the case of the static variant, the exposure and the sensitivity components are measured at one point in time. In the case of the dynamic, the change of the two components over time (generally as a percentage change from 2015 to 2019) is compared.

Table 19: Tier two overtourism indicators

Indicator name	Methodology	Territorial level
Tourism intensity (tourism exposure)	Number of arrivals or bed-nights/inhabitants	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Tourism density (tourism exposure)	Number of arrivals or bed-nights/surface area	NUTS2 and NUTS3
Importance of tourism to regional economy	GVA of tourism-related activities as a percentage of total gross value added	NUTS3
Importance of tourism to regional employment	Tourism employment as a percentage of total employment	NUTS2
Bed places and tourism exposure	Number of available bed places <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS2
Economic importance of tourism	Tourism as a percentage of regional GVA <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS3
Labour market importance of tourism	Tourism jobs as a percentage of total employment <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS2
Net migration and tourism exposure	Average net migration (%) <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS3
Accessibility and tourism exposure	Potential multimodal accessibility <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS3
Water consumption and tourism exposure	Water consumption per capita <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS2
Surface sealing and tourism exposure	Change in artificial surfaces <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS2
Emissions and tourism exposure	CO ₂ emissions per capita <i>paired with</i> tourism exposure (arrivals or bed-nights)	NUTS2

Source: Project team, 2022

5.2.2.2. Data sources and replicability

The indicators presented in the preceding section are available at EU-27 level from sources such as Eurostat or the JRC. The data is available at NUTS2 and NUTS3 levels. For more detailed assessments between regions, this data can be exchanged with data from national and regional statistical offices. The advantage of using data from national or regional sources is the higher territorial resolution of these indicators, usually also covering municipal (i.e. LAU) level. However, this comes at the cost of comparability, since indicator definitions may vary between Member States.

As tourism data is not available at NUTS3 level from Eurostat data, the project team applied regionalisation techniques to approximate NUTS3 data from existing NUTS2 data. Most relevant data for the sensitivity indicators (see Table 18) is only available at NUTS2 level comprehensively for the EU-27. If sensitivity indicators were identified to be available at NUTS3, the project team regionalised the corresponding tourism exposure indicators (i.e. the tourism intensity) to NUTS3 level based on Eurostat and Open Street Map (OSM) data. OSM is an open-source mapping provider. It relies on user input, with users being able to tag locations (so-called "points of interest").

This regionalisation approach is detailed in Appendix 3. As part of this approach, the project team estimated the missing NUTS3 value of a given indicator (e.g. number of arrivals) by multiplying the NUTS2 value of the relevant indicator (e.g. number of arrivals) with the relative share of points of interest (e.g. hotels and other accommodations, as well as attractions such as museums etc.,) between the NUTS3 and associated NUTS2 region. This produces an estimate of the indicator at NUTS3 level.

The project team cautions against using OSM data as a sole means to approximate tourism inflows. Review of the data has shown that mapping, due to the open-nature characteristics of the platform, is heterogeneous across the Member States. Some Member States (e.g. Germany) see comprehensive coverage, whereas in other Member States (e.g. Italy or Greece), locations are not comprehensively tagged. Likely due to differences in knowledge and user behaviour. However, the platform was deemed relatively robust in an analysis by Bustamante et al (2021).

To limit any bias from these issues, the project team only used OSM data to regionalise existing Eurostat data from NUTS2 to NUTS3, using the approach detailed in Appendix 3. This approach accounts for differences between user behaviour between countries, as no comparisons between absolute number of points-of-interest were made between countries. With the expected publication of tourism indicators at NUTS3 level by Eurostat, the use of regionalisation techniques to obtain NUTS3 data from existing NUTS2 data may not be necessary in the future.

Table 20: Data sources tier two components

Name	Time period	Source
Number of inhabitants	2015-2019	Eurostat, population on 1 January by age group, sex and NUTS 2 region [demo_r_pjangroup]
Surface area	2015	Eurostat, area by NUTS 3 region [demo_r_d3area]
Number of bed-places	2015-2019	Eurostat, number of establishments and bed-places [TIN00181]
Number of passengers at closest airport	2015-2019	Eurostat, air transport of passengers by NUTS 2 regions [TRAN_R_AVPA_NM]
Share of GVA of tourism-related sectors of total GVA	2015-2019	Eurostat, gross value added at basic prices by NUTS 3 regions [nama_10r_3gva]; NACE sectors G-I and G-J (NUTS3)
Share of employment in tourist sector of total employment	2015-2019	DG AGRI & Eurostat

Name	Time period	Source
Net migration rate	2015-2019	Eurostat, population change – demographic balance and crude rates at regional level (NUTS 3) [DEMO_R_GIND3]; CNMIGRAT
Potential multimodal accessibility	2014	Spiekermann & Wegener, Urban and Regional Research
Emissions of CO ₂ per capita (tonnes)	2010-2020	Lavalle, Carlo; Trombetti, Marco; Pisoni, Enrico (2015): UI – Atmospheric emissions of CO ₂ (LUISA Platform REF2014). European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: http://data.europa.eu/89h/jrc-luisa-co2-atmospheric-emissions-ref-2014
Freshwater consumption litres/day/capita	2010-2020	Mari Rivero, Ines; Vandecasteele, Ine; Lavalle, Carlo (2015): LF311 – Water Consumption (LUISA Platform REF2014). European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: http://data.europa.eu/89h/jrc-luisa-lf311-water-consumption-ref-2014
Surface area used for residential and commercial activities	2015-2018	Eurostat, land covered by artificial surfaces by NUTS 2 regions [LAN_LCV_ART]
Number of arrivals	2010-2019	Eurostat, arrivals at tourist accommodation establishments by NUTS 2 regions [tour_occ_arn2]
Number of overnight stays	2010-2019	Eurostat, number of bed-nights [tour_cap_nuts2]

Source: Project team, 2022

5.2.3. Tier three indicators: measuring tourism pressure and actual impacts locally

5.2.3.1. Selection of indicators

The project team furthermore analysed the list of indicators used in the case study destinations, in terms of their frequency of use per destination type and their overall relevance to capture developments associated with overtourism. From the list of all indicators used, the project team shortlisted the most relevant and applicable across all destinations as core indicators. The full pool of good-practice indicators retrieved via the case study analysis is provided in Appendix 4. The selection of good practice core indicators is presented below (see Table 21). This selection of tier three indicators serves as a good practice pool for destinations from which to select local-level indicators.

Table 21: Tier three core indicators

Indicator	Theme
Number of overnight stays	General statistics
Arrivals by relevant mode of transportation (cruise, bus, car, plane etc.)	General statistics
Number of mobile phone network users	General statistics
Stays per accommodation type (hotels, hostels, private rentals, etc.)	General statistics
Seasonality of stays	General statistics
Number of bed-places and beds	General statistics
Employment in tourism sector	General statistics
Number of day visitors [at specific attractions]	General statistics
Visitors' satisfaction [survey]	Destination perception
Residents' satisfaction [survey]	Destination perception
Number of outreach events	Destination perception

Indicator	Theme
Visitor mobility statistics	Environment
Public transport accessibility	Environment
Waste generated/collected	Environment
Wastewater generated	Environment
Greenhouse gas emissions per capita	Environment
Monitoring of environmental quality (soil, water, air, biodiversity, etc.)	Environment
Share of renewable energy sources	Environment
Water consumption per capita	Environment

Source: Project team, 2022

5.2.3.2. Data sources and replicability

The assembled short-list was produced from the analysis of destinations in Task B (see section 2). The exact use of outlined short-list of best practice tier three indicators depends on the specificities and needs of the destination. Depending on the modes of tourism observed at the destination, some of the outlined indicators may be more relevant than others.

5.3. Visualisation of overtourism indicators

This section provides an overview of selected visualised tier one indicators, as well as visualised tier two indicators. The tier two indicators are mapped at EU-27 on NUTS2 or NUTS3 level. Additionally, the project team has visualised tier two indicator pairs in a scatterplot, combining tourism exposure and territorial sensitivity

5.3.1. Tier one indicators

From the **tier one indicators** measuring global demand trends, an indicative selection of indicators covering global trends at EU level was computed. This includes numbers of air passenger arrivals (EU-27 and international, i.e. extra-EU-27) and the risk assessment of potential tourism hotspots (indicatively undertaken for the region of Naples, below).

Figure 15: Monthly air passenger arrivals (EU-27)

Source: Eurostat, 2021, based on [AVIA_PAOC]

Figure 16: Monthly extra-EU-27 air passenger arrivals (EU-27)

Source: Eurostat, 2021, based on [AVIA_PAOC]

These two tier one indicators (see Figure 15 and Figure 16) illustrate the high-level pressures of growing air passenger numbers between 2008 and 2019. While the increase of arrivals from extra-EU-27 countries has remained relatively stable at around 40% of total arrivals (see Figure 16), the patterns mirror the movements observed among total arrivals (see Figure 15) which can be described as a stable growth between 2008 and 2019, with peaks during summer months and troughs during early spring months.

Additionally, the tier one indicator “general risk of overtourism” can be visualised via the mapping of tourist attractions and accommodations. The locations of tourist attractions can provide insights into the spatial distribution of potential tourist inflows and highlight vulnerable areas. Furthermore, the spatial distribution and concentration of tourist accommodations (hotels, holiday apartments etc.,) may provide complementary insights which can be used for tourist flow steering and may provide insights into (urban/rural) development and transport issues tied to tourism exposure.

The exposure of a particular region to tourist pressures can be mapped using POI data on tourist attractions and accommodations extracted from OSM (see section 5.2). The attractions and accommodations for greater Naples, Italy were mapped as an illustrative example. Attractions are highlighted in blue, accommodations in purple. A deeper shading represents a higher presence of attractions or accommodations, respectively.

Map 6: Heatmap of tourism exposure in the Naples area

Source: Project team, 2022, based on OSM data

In the case of the Naples area (see Map 6), accommodations are concentrated in the centre of Naples, as well as along other towns such as Sorrento and Vettica Maggiore. While these areas also feature a concentration of attractions, there are noticeable imbalances present throughout the area, most noticeably on the island of Capri, around Mount Vesuvius, and the regional park "Parco Regionale dei Monti Lattari".

5.3.2. Tier two indicators

An indicative selection of **tier two indicators** was computed, namely:

- Change in tourism intensity (arrivals) 2015-2019 (%) in Map 7.
- Change in tourism intensity (arrivals) 2015-2019 (%) and tourism intensity (arrivals) in 2019 in Figure 17.
- Change in labour market importance of tourism and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019) in Map 8.
- Change in economic importance of tourism and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019) in Map 9.
- Accessibility and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019) in Map 10.

These indicators follow the methodological design as outlined above and combine the tourism exposure component (*arrivals or bed-nights*) with a territorial sensitivity component. This pairing of components enables an assessment of the impacts of tourism in relation to a socio-economic, territorial, or environment context factor.

The change in tourism intensity (arrivals per inhabitant) between 2015 and 2019 is illustrated in Map 7 for the EU-27. Areas with an increasing tourism intensity are highlighted in yellow to red, with the blue to green shading corresponding to a declining intensity and a comparatively lower tourism growth rate, respectively. The majority of EU-27 NUTS3 regions saw increases in tourism intensity over that time period. However, the strongest increases can be observed across Portuguese, Croatian, and Slovenian regions. Additionally, many regions in the newer Member States have seen strong tourism intensity growth rates.

Map 7: Indicator: Change in tourism intensity (arrivals) 2015-2019

Source: Project team 2022, based on OSM and Eurostat data

These indicator pairs can also be “matched” for deeper insights into the territorial aspects of overtourism in scatterplots. In Figure 17, the tourism intensity (arrivals per inhabitant) in 2019 is compared with the change in tourism intensity (arrivals per inhabitant) between 2015 and 2019. Most regions across the EU-27 saw a substantial increase in tourism intensity over that period. Furthermore, mountain and island destinations are – generally – more likely to be associated with a tourism intensity than other types of regions.

Figure 17: Indicator: Change in tourism intensity (arrivals) 2015-2019 (%) and tourism intensity (arrivals) in 2019

Source: Project team 2022, based on Eurostat data

The labour market significance of tourism in comparison to the tourist exposure of NUTS3 regions is illustrated in Map 8. This bivariate map displays the two indicator components *change in tourism as a percentage of total employment* (2015-2019; the territorial sensitivity indicator) and the *change in tourism intensity* (arrivals; 2015-2019; the tourism exposure indicator). Each region is classified according to the region's relative score in each of the two components. In the case below, regions are colour-coded according to their relative performance in terms of the two indicator components representing their carrying capacity. This is visualised in the colour-coded matrix in the legend of the map.

A combination of a high and positive change in tourism intensity and a high change in relative tourism employment denotes regions in which the dependence on tourism in the labour market increased strongly between 2015 and 2019, paired with an increasing inflow of tourists. These dark blue or purple shaded regions include many regions across the newer Member States, particularly Pannonian Croatia, Cyprus and other island destinations in the Mediterranean. Conversely, green shaded regions have also seen growing importance of tourism as source of employment, but low growth rates in tourism intensity. Examples include French and Irish regions.

Map 8: Indicator: Change in labour market importance of tourism and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019)

Source: Project team 2022, based on OSM and Eurostat data

Conversely to the labour market significance of tourism, Map 9 illustrates the economic importance of tourism in comparison with tourism exposure. This bivariate map displays the regional performance along the territorial sensitivity indicator *change in tourism as a percentage of GVA*¹⁹ 2015-2019 and the exposure indicator *change in tourism intensity* (arrivals; 2015-2019). As in the case of the preceding map (Map 8), the shading of the regions corresponds to their carrying capacity performance along the colour-coded matrix in the legend of the map. The interpretation of the map follows the reasoning of the preceding map.

Regions with a growing economic specialisation and a (relatively) high increase in arrival intensity are highlighted in dark blue and brown. These regions include southern Portugal, regions along the Croatian and Slovenian Adriatic coast, regions in Lithuania, Bulgaria and Romania. Overspecialisation may be apparent in red-shaded regions, with a high growing economic significance of tourism but a comparatively small growth rate in

¹⁹ This NUTS3 indicator may capture economic activities of other sectors tangentially associated with tourism activities.

tourism intensity. Example regions include urban centres in Germany, western Ireland, and Western Macedonia (Greece).

Map 9: Indicator: Change in economic importance of tourism and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019)

Source: Project team 2022, based on OSM and Eurostat data

The indicator *accessibility and tourism* (Map 10, below) illustrates *change in tourism intensity* (arrivals; 2015-2019) in relation to the *multimodal accessibility* of the region (in 2014). As in the case of the preceding maps, the shading of the regions corresponds to their carrying capacity performance along the colour-coded matrix in the legend of the map.

This analysis highlights regions with the combination of high accessibility and an increase in tourism intensity in brown and dark green. These tend to include mostly urban destinations and highly urbanised regions with well-developed transport networks, such as Lisbon, Barcelona, Amsterdam, and Rome. Regions with a strong increase in tourism intensity but low accessibility are shaded in blue. This set of regions contains island destinations, such as Crete, and rural destinations across Central and Eastern Europe in which transport infrastructure may not be sufficient to account for large tourist inflows.

Map 10: Indicator: Accessibility and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019)

Source: Project team 2022, based on Eurostat, OSM and S&W Spiekermann & Wegener, Urban and Regional Research

6. Task E: Organising a series of stakeholder workshops on overtourism and outreach

6.1. Methodological approach

As part of this project, the project team has implemented a series of stakeholder workshops and has produced outreach materials. Five destination workshops and one concluding EU-level workshop were organised to promote peer learning, exchange, and networking among tourism actors. The following events were organised:

- Island destinations workshop hosted in Valletta, Malta, on 09.12.2021.
- Urban destinations virtual workshop hosted in Vienna, Austria, on 20.01.2022 and 21.01.2021.
- Coastal destinations virtual workshop hosted in Palma de Mallorca, Spain on 23.02.2022 and 24.02.2022.
- Rural destinations virtual workshop hosted at the Plitvice Lakes National Park, Croatia, 17.03.2022 and 18.03.2022.
- Mountain destinations workshop hosted in Munich, Germany, on 26.04.2022;
- EU-level workshop, hosted in Brussels, Belgium, on 20.05.2022.

The five destination workshops aimed to connect tourism stakeholders from destinations to foster peer-to-peer learning on the problems of, and solutions to, unbalanced tourism growth. Participants were invited to present solution approaches to unsustainable tourism growth and its environmental and socio-economic impacts on the regions. Moreover, challenges and bottlenecks hindering the mitigation of unbalanced tourism growth were examined. Importantly, the workshops focused on identifying concrete steps for destinations to move towards more sustainable practices and mitigate the impacts of unbalanced tourism growth. During the workshops, participants tested the practical application of proposed indicators for overtourism risk assessment.

The final EU workshop aimed to synthesise the destination workshops at EU level, with a strong focus on cross-destination analysis and EU stakeholder engagement. Further, this workshop aimed to foster exchange at EU level on unsustainable tourism growth in the context of the EU Transition Pathway for Tourism initiative, as well as to disseminate the project findings.

For each workshop the research team created a contact database (based on desk research) gathering a large array of tourism related actors of that destination type, including DMOs, stakeholders (such as local groups), and infrastructure providers. This contact database was created by assessing the inventory of identified regions with overtourism (Task A), researching alternative destinations (those at risk of overtourism and those not affected by overtourism), and subsequently identifying contact people at the destinations.

The research team¹¹⁰ reached out via social media and targeted invitations to the following stakeholder types as potential participants:

- Experts (high-level practitioners and academics).
- Representatives from the other case study destinations, as well as representatives from other destinations of the same type, who may want to take part in the peer-to-peer learning session.
- Thematically relevant representatives.
- Representatives from other interested destinations (destination management organisations, regional and local authorities, tourism industry representatives (associations, interest groups, etc.), residents' organisations of the destinations and infrastructure providers (transport, waste and other utilities etc.,).

6.2. Organisation and preparation of the dialogue platform

The organisation of each workshop entailed the delivery of a concept note approximately one month before each event. This concept note described the overall organisational and content approach to the workshop and outlined the following elements:

- An introduction, outlining context and summary of the project findings
- An outline of the aims of the workshop
- The workshop agenda, including a description of each session
- The approach to selecting and inviting participants
- Roles of the project team and external speakers

Prior to each workshop, the participants received a technical note outlining organisational details and the agenda, as well as technical aspects pertaining to the workshop. Due to the organisation of workshops in hybrid and virtual formats, this proved important to increase participation. The participants also received a background note summarising relevant information and project findings in preparation for the workshop.

External speakers and best practice examples were an important aspect in the workshops, particularly in the peer learning sessions. The project team asked representatives of the case study regions to present best practice solutions. In addition, the project team invited speakers from other destinations, as well as thematic experts to present in the workshops.

The destination workshops were organised as full-day events. The concluding EU workshop was organised as a half-day event.

6.2.1. Destination workshops

The project team implemented onsite and virtual workshops. The workshops were foreseen as full day events. However, in the case of fully virtual workshops (particularly the coastal and the rural destinations workshops), the events were organised as two half-day events. As such, the exact timing of the agenda items varied. A representative sample agenda of a two half-day workshop is presented below.

Box 2: Destination workshop day 1 agenda

Timing	Sessions
12:45	Opening of the meeting room for the online participants
13:00	Welcoming
13:15	Introduction of participants (position/background) Participants' expectations regarding the workshop <i>Format: round of introduction in plenary session</i>
13:45	Part 1: Presentation of the project findings (Tasks A to D) <i>Format: discussion in plenary session</i>
14:15	Break
14:25	Part 2: peer-to-peer learning Presentations of the challenges and problems faced as well as identified solution approaches from different perspectives (thematic experts, destination management organisations, infrastructure providers, local groups, etc.) <i>Format: participants presentations and open discussions in plenary session</i>
16:25	Break
16:40	Conclusions, summary of discussions and next steps <i>in plenary session</i>
16:50	End of the workshop

Source: Project team, 2022

Box 3: Destination workshop day 2 agenda

Timing	Sessions
08:45	Opening of the meeting room for the online participants
09:00	Welcoming and summary of Day 1
09:15	<p>Part 3: how to identify, assess, and address tourism growth imbalances: a structured approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the discussion format ▪ Group work: Assessment of overtourism impacts in rural areas via a systemic picture <p><i>Format: Interactive discussion</i></p>
10:00	Break
10:10	<p>Part 3 (cont.): how to identify, assess, and address tourism growth imbalances: a structured approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Selection of main overtourism impact indicators (as per systemic picture) ▪ Maps and illustrations of overtourism indicators ▪ Discussion of solution approaches <p><i>Format: Interactive discussion</i></p>
11:10	Break
11:20	<p>Part 4: Validation and key challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Group discussion 1: overtourism indicators, data availability and measurement ▪ Group discussion 2: solution approaches and governance ▪ Plenary discussion: Pathways to sustainable tourism destination and future developments <p><i>Format: Brainstorm and plenary – group work</i></p>
12:30	Conclusions, summary of findings and next steps <i>in plenary session</i>
12:40	End of the workshop Closing remarks

Source: Project team, 2022

During the **Introduction**, participants were asked to give a short overview of their background and stake in the overtourism debate.

During **Part 1**, members of the research team presented the assignment, its objectives, and main findings.

In **Part 2**, representatives of different destinations were invited to share the main issues and challenges they face, and the solutions (if any) that have been found to address the issues. The aim of this peer-to-peer session was to focus on problems which may be common to various destinations belonging to a given type, and to identify innovative ideas which may be transferable.

In **Part 3**, participants were introduced to a methodology which builds on existing knowledge and characteristics of a given destination type. During the session, participants were directly involved through an activity of drawing a systemic picture (either virtually or physically) identifying overtourism impacts. Building on this systemic picture, an analysis of the tourism impacts (relying on the indicators developed within the scope of the project) was presented by the research team and discussed with the participants.

Over the course of implementation of the workshop series, this section was adapted to improve the discussion flow. In general, two-to-three indicator pairs were presented, in addition to an EU-level map, as well as several (two to four) destination maps.

Finally, in **Part 4**, a brainstorming session was organised. Participants were free to choose their preferred topic among two group discussions:

- Group discussion 1: overtourism indicators, data availability and measurement
- Group discussion 2: solution approaches and governance

This was followed by a plenary session on development prospects for the tourism industry.

Over the course of the project, this session was adapted to improve flexibility and stimulate discussion. In the first workshops, this session included a world café session focused along four topics (validation and improvement, issues of data availability and appropriateness of the territorial degree of resolution, governance and role of EU institutions, and pathways towards sustainable tourism).

6.2.2. EU workshop

The concluding EU workshop followed a different format than the destination workshops, focusing on an EU level discussion on initiatives and a cross-comparison of drivers and impacts of overtourism across destination types.

Box 4: EU workshop agenda

Timing	Sessions
08:45	Arrival onsite, health and safety, and registration – coffee/tea
09:00	Welcoming and introduction
09:15	Introduction of participants
09:40	Part 1: Presentation of the project findings and recommendations <i>Format: Presentation of the key project findings followed by a Q&A session</i>
10:15	Part 2: Comparative analysis of overtourism per destination type Cross-analysis of causes, impacts and solution approaches found in island, rural, mountain, urban, and coastal destinations. This analysis highlights similarities and differences across the various types of destinations. <i>Format: Presentation and open discussions in plenary session</i>
11:00	Coffee/tea break
11:10	Part 3: Transition pathway for tourism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the Transition Pathway for Tourism ▪ Panel discussion: how more sustainable destinations can contribute to and benefit from the Transition Pathway for Tourism <i>Format: Brief presentation followed by panel discussion</i>
12:45	Conclusions and introduction to FUTURIUM
13:00	End of the workshop

Source: Project team, 2022

After a welcoming address by key speakers to set the frame of the project and workshop, all participants, on-site and online, were invited to provide a brief **introduction** of themselves and their destinations.

During **Part 1**, members of the research team presented the assignment, its objectives, and main findings. The aim of the presentation was to provide participants with a more detailed understanding of the objectives and results of the project. Participants were then invited to reflect on the presentation in a question-and-answer session.

In **Part 2**, the project team presented a cross-destination analysis of causes, impacts, and solution approaches found in island, rural, mountain, urban, and coastal destinations. This analysis highlighted differences and similarities along the destination types,

of the regional/destination system). An example of such a systemic picture from the urban destinations workshop is presented in Figure 18.

The aim of this approach was twofold:

- To identify the most relevant challenges and sensitive points where tourism intensity and unbalanced tourism growth would occur
 - Output 1: a list of the three to four most relevant issues, as identified by the stakeholders
- To identify in which way these causal links between tourism and context may be depicted. In other words, the aim was to identify indicators which may build the factual basis for depicting and learning how to overcome these challenges
 - Output 2: a list of indicators which may serve as basis for decision-making

Finally, the project team paired this information with respect to causes and effects. Exposure (in the form of various tourist intensity indicators) and sensitivity (in the form of various context indicators according to the challenges and needs identified in the first step) were combined in scatterplots. Thus, the resultant plot illustrated developments and potential interdependencies between tourism and the territorial context. This does not imply causality between the two factors, rather it visualises patterns. Using this approach, a visualisation of the root causes and associated territorial developments of tourism may be provided. This enabled the project team to identify outliers, i.e. destinations which form atypical patterns and may be at risk of overtourism.

Figure 19: Scatter plot change in arrivals (%) 2015-2019 and change in tourism employment (%) 2015-2019 in island NUTS2 regions²¹

Source: ÖIR GmbH, 2022, based on Eurostat data

The final step of this activity was a plenary discussion of the results. This was started by revisiting the list of the three to four most relevant issues as identified during the first step (output 1). In light of the information provided and the territorial evidence

²¹ These plots will be prepared for urban destinations.

available, the participants were encouraged to pin-down concrete ways to manage destinations, including pathways towards sustainable tourism. This discussion was targeted at the level of the types of destinations.

6.4. Outcomes of the dialogue platform

The findings of the workshop were used to develop conclusions and recommendations for this study. The workshops also produced valuable insights which supported the selection of bivariate indicator pairs as proposed in Task D. Furthermore, they supported key findings from the literature review (Task A) and the case studies (Task B). The resulting adjustments to the project conclusions and recommendations are detailed in section 7.1 and 7.2, respectively. The outcomes of the destination workshop series are detailed in report D.2.2 *Final workshop report* (please see Appendix 10).

The workshop discussions highlighted several indicator pair combinations as relevant across the destination types:

- *Change in tourism intensity* combined with the *average net migration rate*, especially for coastal and rural destinations: High burden from tourism and undesirable behaviour may reduce quality of life of residents in the hosting region. Additional burdens can come from increasing costs of living due to increasing housing prices.
- *Change in tourism intensity combined with the change in gross value added from tourism activities or with percentage of employment from tourism activities*: As tourism activities become increasingly favourable as an economic sector and attract more investments, it may displace other economic activities (in terms of relative share of the sector), leading to (over-)specialisation. This increases economic vulnerabilities in times of economic crises and other crises reducing the movement of people (e.g. pandemics), generally necessitating public support to the tourism sector.
- *Change in tourist intensity combined with multimodal accessibility*, especially for urban areas: In part due to their high levels of accessibility, are attractive to visitors, especially for short stays.
- *Tourism intensity combined with artificial surface area, water consumption per capita, etc.*, for destinations restricted in terms of local resources and reserves: The strain on local utilities and infrastructure due to high daytime population compared to a low permanent population was highlighted in the discussions. Particularly water consumption was mentioned in this context. The lack of local/regional (natural) resources places a burden on destinations, especially when encountering a large daytime or non-permanent population which places additional burdens on water consumption. When restricted in terms of local resources and reserves, be it in terms of surface area for construction, environmental reserves etc., planning decisions need to be taken with great care, so as to not exhaust the available reserves.
- *Change in tourist intensity combined with change in CO₂ emissions per capita*: With high numbers of incoming tourists come higher pollution levels in the region. This can be approximated by looking at the growth of CO₂ emissions per capita compared to the increases in tourism intensity over similar timeframes.

Issues with data access and data collection were discussed in the workshops. The main results of the discussions are highlighted below:

- Resident and tourist surveys gained importance in monitoring unbalanced tourism developments, shifting away from using traditional performance indicators and environmental assessments. However, the need for comparable indicators was stipulated.
- The lack of public sector access to big data poses a problem as this data is generally not shared by the companies which collect it. Data alliances (as is the case

in the Netherlands) may be used to create common data banks and improve access among destinations.

- Big data can provide many avenues to measuring (ideally in real time) tourism exposure in affected areas. A key issue is data access, costs and privacy rights. In addition, destinations tend to lack the capacities to apply big data solutions. As such, an EU-level platform could be useful.
- Often data is not interpreted sufficiently and lacks translation into policies and decision making. Often, there is a lack of skills for data management at DMOs.
- Especially topical for smaller destinations with lower technical capacities for the implementation of comprehensive indicator systems, the focus on fewer, less complex, indicators can be a way forward.

The discussion of solution approaches to mitigating the impacts of overtourism validated key findings from the literature review (Task A) and the case studies (Task B). The validated key findings are:

- Increasing housing prices are pressing issues in areas affected by overtourism, since they affect local residents (via out-pricing) as well as (seasonal) employees in the sector who may not find affordable accommodation due to price developments.
- In rural areas, de-concentration strategies and the redirection of visitor streams (e.g. via information campaigns) can not only help alleviate the burden on individual destinations and divert visitors to other areas, but also enable other areas to participate economically (as was the case in municipalities surrounding Plitvice Lakes National Park).
- Real-time and up-to-date information provision (crowd monitoring at destinations etc.,) and of use of services and amenities were highlighted multiple times as solution approaches in the workshops. Nevertheless, the urban workshop in particular showed that several challenges exist when working, for instance, with mobile phone data. The datasets need to be purchased from the providers and subsequently also the software/platforms to analyse the data. As such the city of Florence is using WIFI hubs to real-time measure density. The city is also working on using camera recordings (in conformity with GDPR requirements). The city of Vienna also prefers to rely on their own data collection efforts as it is more sustainable than using third-party big data solutions.
- Varying governance levels within a destination can be a challenge and have an impact on the management of tourism. This was shown in the coastal workshop. In the case of Mallorca, the airport policy is under the purview of the national government, limiting the possibilities for the regional government to restrict the number of incoming flights. In the case of Catalonia, tourism rarely affects one area alone, requiring a higher-level perspective for governance solutions.
- Unbalanced tourism monitoring is, in general, not very advanced. The importance of comprehensive impact measurement was confirmed in the coastal workshop as impacts may vary even within smaller regions (e.g. between municipalities).
- Visitors and residents are key stakeholders to consider in defining appropriate solutions to unbalanced tourism. This was also stressed in the island destinations workshop. Participation of residents in policy-making, as well as their consultation (e.g. via surveys) and means of residents to be financially compensated and take part in benefit-sharing were identified as success factors. While in the urban destination workshops the importance of the cross-sectoral cooperation between stakeholders was highlighted, as was that between economic sectors, such as upstream and downstream actors.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

7.1. Conclusions

7.1.1. Characteristics and occurrence of unbalanced tourism

The most frequently used term for unbalanced tourism is “overtourism”. Throughout the project, both terms have been used interchangeably. It is a complex, multidimensional phenomenon that implies exceeding the physical, ecological, economic, social and/or psychological carrying capacities of a destination through high numbers or densities of tourists and crowding. However, the precise point at which this happens is extremely difficult to determine. While it is possible to objectively determine the physical or ecological carrying capacities of a destination to a certain degree, the social aspects of overtourism are often subjective and dependent on stakeholder interests or even individual perceptions. Thus, it is not consistently possible to draw a clear line between overtourism and mass tourism, as the social perception of what constitutes overtourism can vary significantly.

Map 11: Destinations affected by overtourism

Source: Project team, 2022 (based on Task A findings)

Overtourism occurs in a variety of destinations, ranging from urban to rural and from mountain to coastal and island destinations. Destinations with important cultural or natural heritage sites or attractive protected areas are prone to be affected as well. Therefore, the inventory carried out by the project team has yielded a large number of destinations affected by overtourism throughout Europe. Prior to the outbreak of Covid-19 the majority of these were urban and coastal destinations. However, the pandemic changed this picture drastically, resulting in the occurrence of new overtourism “hotspots” in rural (mountain and coastal) areas caused by domestic tourism and day trips at the expense of urban tourism.

Another important finding is that overtourism rarely occurs in an entire destination or region. Instead, in two thirds of the inventoried cases only certain neighbourhoods, historic town centres, coastal strips or specific attractions were affected. Entire municipalities experience overtourism less frequently, mostly in rural areas or smaller towns. Furthermore, in many destinations overtourism is merely a seasonal phenomenon.

7.1.2. Root causes and impacts of overtourism

The root causes of overtourism are as complex and diverse as the phenomenon itself. For a systematic analysis, they can be divided into the following categories (see Figure 20):

- **External driving forces** consisting of general global developments (for instance, higher disposable incomes, technological advances) as well as tourism-specific developments (e.g. emergence of a global tourism industry, increased accessibility to air travel);
- More **recent tourism trends**, such as the occurrence of new source markets (especially from emerging economies) and the proliferation of information and communication technologies, enabling, among others, the emergence of peer-to-peer platforms and the widespread use of social media in relation to tourism;
- Sudden, **unpredictable events** such as terrorist attacks or the Covid-19 pandemic may lead to major disruptions causing a rapid **shift of visitor flows** and concurrently overtourism phenomena to other destinations.
- Such external driving forces lead to tangible effects, i.e. increasing **tourism-induced pressure** at the destination level, typically manifesting itself in high tourist densities, rapid growth or inappropriate visitor behaviour. Day visitors are often seen as particularly problematic in this regard since they tend to exacerbate pressure without contributing substantially to the local economy.
- **Internal factors**, also described as the state or **sensitivity** of a destination, may exacerbate or mitigate tourism pressure. These factors can be general or tourism-specific. Examples are the economic significance of tourism at local level, the fragility of natural ecosystems, the effectiveness of local governance (including destination management), or the degree to which social conflicts already exist.

The potential **impacts** of overtourism are likewise diverse, depending on the specific combination of driving forces, pressures and destination characteristics. Impacts can be physical, environmental, (socio-) economic or socio-cultural (including psychological). They can also be differentiated with respect to which stakeholder group is predominantly affected. Whether this is the local population, tourism- and non-tourism companies or the tourists themselves. To this end there are five main categories of impacts:

- The **degradation of the local infrastructure** – such as roads, port facilities, garbage collection or sewage treatment facilities – usually occurs through high numbers of tourists encountering limited local capacities.
- The **degradation of the natural environment** tends to be more pronounced in rural areas (including coasts and mountains) where ecosystems are often fragile and even relatively low visitor numbers may have negative effects, such as water and air pollution, soil erosion, or wildlife disturbance.

- **Imbalances in the local economy** can occur when tourism becomes predominant in certain areas (“touristification”), pushing out traditional stores or professions, and leading to rising prices for real estate or everyday consumer goods. Tourists may thus be seen by residents as competitors over scarce resources.
- **Impacts on the social environment** becomes an issue when residents feel psychologically, socially or culturally disturbed by the presence of too many tourists, especially if these tourists behave in an unacceptable way (e.g., by making noise or littering). Furthermore, tourism may also become a matter of conflict between local residents, depending upon whether or not they economically benefit from tourism.
- Finally, **tourists** themselves may be negatively affected by the presence of a large number of other visitors in the same area. This depends on the type of visitors and their expectations regarding their experience. For instance, cruise passengers may be more tolerant of crowding than nature tourists.

Figure 20: Causes and effects of overtourism

Source: Project team, 2022

The analysis of the 15 case studies and the workshop discussions have shown that unbalanced tourism is a process that evolves uniquely at each destination, despite some clear common mega-trends and drivers. International tourism growth is a key driver of unbalanced tourism development at most destinations. Secondly, the evolution of social media use contributes to overtourism at some specific sites resulting in them becoming hotspots without key management organisations in place with rapid and necessary controls.

Destination governance was shown to be a decisive factor for the emergence of overtourism. Varying governance levels within a destination can be a challenge and have an impact on the management of tourism. This was shown, for example, in the coastal workshop. In the case of Mallorca, the airport policy is under the purview of the national government, limiting the possibilities for the regional government to restrict the number of incoming flights. In the case of Catalonia, tourism rarely affects one area alone, requiring a higher-level perspective for governance solutions.

In terms of impacts, the most visible effects of overtourism include various types of congestion, such as the concentrated number of visitors or vehicles in a limited geographic space, including beaches, parking facilities, queues in front of museums, or

ports. The non-visible impacts of unbalanced tourism are more diffuse and include several socio-economic and socio-cultural impacts such as touristification, increased prices and biophysical impacts throughout the year. The issue of increasing housing prices was frequently discussed in the workshops, since they affect local residents (via out-pricing) as well as (seasonal) employees in the sector who are not able to find affordable accommodation. Yet, in many cases overtourism is subjectively perceived by local stakeholders, particularly by residents, and is season dependent. Summer is the most important season where unbalanced tourism is observable at the destinations, even if tourism is present during other times.

Therefore, how destinations experience unbalanced tourism significantly varies and partly relates to the destination type. Nevertheless, many commonalities are observable amongst cities, coasts and islands, rural areas and mountain destinations:

- **Urban destinations** (Florence, Lucerne, Vienna) appear to have more flexibility and local alternate tourism attractions and infrastructure available to implement physical dispersion strategies compared to rural destinations. The latter often have fewer resources and attractions as alternatives within an easily reachable geographic range, such as the cases of Geiranger Fjord, Cliffs of Moher, Plitvice Lakes and Monts d'Ardèche.
- **The rural areas** analysed (Plitvice Lakes, Regional Park of Monts d'Ardèche, Cliffs of Moher) demonstrate how regions depend on tourism flows and that the sudden appearance of large crowds at a few attraction points is not easy to manage. Furthermore, rural areas all seem to be confronted with the contradiction of capturing the economic benefits that tourism may bring, while offering idyllic rural landscapes and unique attractions. Unless rural destinations are able to develop an appropriate set of attractions and tourism infrastructure to disperse visitors, it may continue to be rather challenging to create less crowded hotspots around iconic "must-see" attractions. This applies particularly to destinations where protected area management goals to conserve ecological integrity do not always easily align with goals to provide more tourism infrastructure (attractions and accommodation, as well as parking and ancillary services).
- **The coastal and island destinations** all show biophysical fragility. This is especially true of beaches, dunes and places of biodiversity value. Collectively, island destinations have limited geographic space and share challenges with respect to further tourism growth. The absence of neighbouring land destinations makes them interesting since any management solution implemented can be set in a very specific scope suitable and adapted to a "closed" destination. As a result, island settings provide advantages in monitoring arrivals from outside, while the local movement and management of crowds remains equally comparable to all other destination types.
- **The mountain destinations** analysed highlight the fragility, both biophysical and socio-cultural, of such areas (Dolomites, Rigi, Bled). The destinations showcase how contemporary visitor masses can easily be channelled even to relatively remotely located places, as more and more visitors seek nature experiences at "instagrammeable" spots. Similarly to coastal areas, mountain destinations, particularly within protected areas, are suitable for management approaches aiming at stricter regulations and controls.

7.1.3. Indicators to measure overtourism

A large variety of indicators have been proposed in the literature to measure overtourism, or the risk of overtourism. Indicators are widely seen as an important tool to monitor and ultimately prevent or mitigate overtourism. The purpose of developing indicators can be three-fold:

- to detect risks or "early warning signs" before overtourism actually manifests itself, or is in its initial stages;

- to manage and counteract impacts that have already occurred (but may not be plainly visible, e.g., biodiversity loss);
- to monitor the effectiveness of mitigation measures.

Overtourism manifests itself through certain impacts that are caused by an unbalanced development of tourism. This may occur either quantitatively through too many tourists (and the infrastructure and supporting activities that are needed to make tourism happen) or qualitatively, for instance by tourists behaving inappropriately as perceived by local residents, which adds a subjective component to the issue. The obvious and direct approach to measure overtourism would be to measure its impacts. However, there are two conceptual challenges associated with this method:

- Can observed impacts, completely or partially, be attributed to tourism? For instance, water pollution in a coastal city may be caused by other economic activities or by the residents themselves.
- Negative impacts associated with overtourism typically occur incrementally. Tipping points, where a carrying capacity is exceeded, either do not exist or may be difficult to detect. Therefore, the value of an indicator does not necessarily indicate the existence, or non-existence, of overtourism.

Another fundamental weakness of using impact indicators is that they measure negative effects that have already occurred. For this reason, it may be appropriate to also measure driving forces, pressures and the sensitivity (or state) of a destination as a foresighted strategy to counteract overtourism before it manifests. This approach measures the *risk* of overtourism rather than the degree of overtourism itself. In the literature, such approaches have been suggested, including indicators measuring the extent of mitigation strategies (response indicators). There is a certain focus on driving forces and pressure indicators.

Some authors have proposed concise indicator sets that are to be universally applied while others have pointed out that destinations are too diverse to conceive a “one-size-fits-all” system of indicators. Furthermore, data availability and comparability between destinations are central challenges when striving to measure overtourism. The most frequently proposed indicators in the literature are:

- **Economic importance of tourism** (% of GDP and employment) in a destination (measuring a destination’s state or sensitivity).
- **Tourism intensity** (number of overnight tourists – arrivals or bed-nights – in relation to the number of local inhabitants) (measuring tourism pressure).
- **Tourism density** (number of overnight tourists – arrivals or bed-nights – in relation to the surface of the destination) (measuring tourism pressure).

With respect to the listed indicators, the corresponding data is readily available through Eurostat and other sources. The project team has, therefore, mapped these indicators on a European scale. It was decided to compute and depict indicators at NUTS 3 level, where available. If data was not available at NUTS-3 level, the NUTS-3 data was approximated or *regionalised* from available NUTS-2 data. This was done because overtourism tends to be a small-scale phenomenon rather than affecting a larger region. In the case of the economic importance of tourism activities, tourism-specific data are not uniformly available at EU level. Alternatively, a Eurostat indicator was chosen that covers sectors, such as accommodation or transport, that are part of or related to tourism. These maps were then overlapped with Map 1, depicting the occurrence of overtourism as derived from the literature in order to check the validity of the indicators.

Surprisingly, the correlation between the selected indicators alone and the actual occurrence of overtourism was rather weak. There are two predominant possible explanations for this:

- The authors that diagnosed overtourism in a certain destination may have used different criteria or thresholds for overtourism.

- Even the NUTS-3 level may still be too coarse to measure tourism pressure as a predictor for overtourism as it often occurs even below the municipal level, for instance in certain urban neighbourhoods or certain zones of protected areas.

Consequently, it would be appropriate to map overtourism indicators on LAU level. However, this would present serious challenges in data availability and comparability between destinations. A highly localised approach might also entail the risk of neglecting driving forces outside of the destination that might eventually manifest themselves as overtourism. The project team has therefore developed a three-tiered set of overtourism indicators that was presented and discussed in section 6 and, as an overview, in section 7.2.1.

Issues with data access and data collection were discussed in the workshops as well. The main results of the discussions are highlighted below:

- Resident and tourist surveys have gained importance in monitoring unbalanced tourism developments, shifting away from the use of traditional performance indicators and environmental assessments.
- The lack of public sector access to big data poses a problem as this data is generally not shared by the companies that collect it. A key issue, therefore, is data access, costs, and privacy rights. In addition, destinations tend to lack the capacities to apply big data solutions.
- Often data is not interpreted sufficiently and lacks translation into policies and decision-making. In addition, there is frequently a lack of skills for data management at DMOs.
- Especially for smaller destinations with lower technical capacities to implement comprehensive indicator systems, the focus on fewer, less complex indicators can be a way forward.

7.1.4. Solution approaches

This report has showcased 15 specific cases across Europe that illustrate how tourism can develop in an unbalanced way in destinations. These 15 cases highlight certain similarities and a lot of differences regarding unbalanced tourism patterns. However, most importantly, they are all cases of good practices and many of the specific initiatives and measures implemented can be applied to other destinations in Europe where tourism may already be, or may become, unbalanced. Although many destinations have implemented a complex set of solution approaches to overtourism, none represents a case where the issue is “solved for good”. It is rather that each case highlights a unique setting with a broad range of solution approaches that can partially be transferred to other destinations struggling with similar issues (see Table 15). No one single solution is suitable for all destinations, as geographic and socio-economic conditions vary. Furthermore, stakeholder values, beliefs and attitudes differ as well and are key aspects of successful management of overtourism. Whether a solution approach is appropriate must be decided by the local stakeholders. In any case, the solutions to manage unbalanced tourism need to be multidimensional as tourism is a complex and dynamic sector.

Table 22: Common approaches to address overtourism at destinations

	Destination	Laws and Policies	Key stakeholders cooperate	New Tourism Infrastructure Developments	Capacity Limits at some sites	Dispersion Strategies	Digital Solutions	Others
Urban	Florence	x	x			x	x	Enhanced reservation system to attractions
	Lucerne	x	x	x		x	x	
	Vienna	x	x	x	x	x		

Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level

	Destina- tion	Laws and Poli- cies	Key stake- holders cooperate	New Tour- ism Infra- structure Develop- ments	Capacity Limits at some sites	Dispersion Strategies	Digital Solu- tions	Others
Coastal	Bay of Lübeck	x	x	x	x	x	x	Create more space for pedestrians instead of cars
	Geirangerfjord	x	x			x	x	Green Shipping Programme, VR Experience of the area
	Palma	x	X	x	x	x	x	Online marketplace for tourism businesses, temporary prohibition of alcohol sale and consumption in public places
Island	Iceland	x	x	x	x	x	x	Iceland Academy and Pledge, Tourism start-up accelerator, Tourism Fund
	Mallorca	x	x	x	x	x	x	Sustainable Tourism Tax, Better Winter Strategy
	Malta		x					Malta Tourism Observatory planned, rebranding, focus towards different categories of tourists
Rural	Burren and Cliffs of Moher		x	x	x	x	x	Pricing strategies, encouraging longer stays
	Parc Naturel Régional des Monts d'Ardèche		x		x	x	x	"Flux Vision Tourism" Data gathering
	Plitvice Lake	x	x		x	x		Pricing strategies
Mountain	Bled	x	x	x				Encouraging longer stays
	Dolomites, Val Pusteria		x		x		x	Scientific assessment of flows
	Rigi		x	x				

Source: Project team, 2022

The solution approaches applied by the different destinations analysed in this project can be described as follows:

- Laws, regulations and policies:** Most destinations have implemented some manner of legally binding rules and regulations to address unbalanced tourism development. These include i.e., imposing limits to the construction of new hotels or the numbers of cruise passengers, the regulation of privately rented accommodation as well as pollution control measures for cruise ships. Interestingly, island destinations as "closed systems" appear to be more in a position to implement access controls and other limits rather than "open" destinations on the mainland. This is also true for protected areas which usually have a formal management structure and can rely on stricter conservation laws. This may include

imposing capacity limits for heavily visited sites. Less restrictive policies may create incentives to use public transport instead of an individual automobile, for instance.

- Nevertheless, **stakeholder cooperation**, including different interest groups, tourism companies and even the visitors themselves, has been implemented as a precondition to developing appropriate solutions to unbalanced tourism. Participation of residents in policy-making, as well as their consultation (e.g., via surveys) and means of residents to be financially compensated and to take part in benefit-sharing were identified as success factors.
- New and expanded **tourism infrastructure**, such as additional parking lots or increased waste collection capacities in the high season are obvious means to accommodate higher visitor numbers in an orderly manner. New infrastructure as well as new tourism offers or simply enhanced information campaigns have also been used to **disperse tourists** to other parts of a destination. Such “de-concentration” strategies and the redirection of visitor streams does not only help to alleviate the burden on areas with “must-see” attractions, but also enable other areas to participate economically – as has been the case in municipalities surrounding Plitvice Lakes National Park.
- **Digital solutions**, particularly the use of big data from mobile technologies and centralised tourism data observatories, seem to be key aspects of successful management of unbalanced tourism as they enable data-driven decision-making. Information provides a common ground for stakeholders of diverging interests and power levels to consider appropriate solutions from their own perspectives. Real-time and up-to-date information provision (crowd monitoring at destinations etc.,) and the use of services and amenities were highlighted multiple times as solution approaches in the workshops. Nevertheless, the urban workshop, in particular, demonstrated that several challenges exist when working for instance with mobile phone data. The datasets need to be purchased from the providers and subsequently also the software and platforms necessary to analyse the data. As such, the city of Florence is using WIFI hubs to measure density in real-time. The city is also working on using camera recordings (in conformity with GDPR requirements). The city of Vienna also prefers to rely on their own data collection efforts as it is more sustainable than using third-party big data solutions.

However, the systematic monitoring of unbalanced tourism with a key set of indicators is not well advanced among most studied destinations. This contributes to overtourism remaining a subjective phenomenon at some destinations. Systematic information collection and analysis, relevant to a destination, is key to managing unbalanced tourism. This information needs to be made accessible to all stakeholders, including residents of the destinations. The importance of impact measurement was also confirmed in the coastal workshop as impacts may vary even within smaller regions (e.g., between municipalities).

7.2. Recommendations

The recommendations presented in this report were developed based on the analyses undertaken in the literature review (Task A), the case studies (Task B), the development of overtourism indicators (Task D), and from the discussions in the stakeholder workshops (Task E). In terms of mitigation strategies, some general recommendations can already be derived from the previous chapter on solution approaches. A particular focus was directed on the development of an indicator system to measure the risk of unbalanced tourism and to inform its monitoring. Finally, recommendations are given to decision-makers on different levels, ranging from the EU to national, regional and local levels.

7.2.1. Proposed indicator system

An appropriate indicator system for the measurement of overtourism, or the risk of such a development, must fulfil four basic requirements:

- It must enable the monitoring, prevention and mitigation of overtourism.
- It must cover the cause-effect relationships leading to unbalanced tourism development, ranging from visitor pressure and actual impacts to the driving forces behind overtourism and the state, or characteristics, of a (potentially) affected destination.
- It must reflect the diversity of individual destinations while also taking into account comparability and replicability as well as the external driving forces behind overtourism, thus combining global with regional and local indicators.
- It must be feasible, meaning that data availability and the often-limited capacities of destination management organisations have to be taken into account.

With this in mind, a **three-tiered indicator system** was developed by the project team:

- Tier 1: Measuring **global trends** that act as driving forces for overtourism. These indicators should be available at global, EU or national level and indicate a *general risk* of overtourism.
- Tier 2: Measuring tourism pressure as well as internal factors (sensitivity) on the **regional level**. This type of indicator can provide insights into whether there is a more *specific risk* of overtourism in a given destination. These uniform indicators would also allow for comparisons of tourism developments between similar destinations (e.g., islands).
- Tier 3: Measuring tourism pressure, actual impacts and internal factors (sensitivity) **locally**. A destination – or even site – specific approach is needed to assess the local risk or actual occurrence of overtourism.

Tier 1 indicators are based on mega-trends, or root causes, that are known to have a strong influence on the occurrence of overtourism phenomena around the world. In more detail, the Tier 1 indicators should measure:

- Growth of international tourism in general, with a particular focus on the development of source markets from emerging economies. These demand segments contain many first-time travellers to a given destination, with a consequent focus on iconic sites, such as UNESCO World Heritage Sites.
- Passenger numbers of low-cost airlines and charter flights. These tend to focus on easily accessible destinations with airports and transport large numbers of tourists in relatively short periods of time.
- Passenger numbers of cruise companies. Even more than charter flights and low-cost airlines, the business model of most cruise companies is geared towards very high volumes of tourists. In addition, cruise ships can only call at ports of sufficient size, thus almost inevitably leading to high visitor concentrations in urban coastal areas.

The Tier 2 indicators (regional indicators) are derived from the carrying capacity framework developed by Schuh et al (2021) and other authors, as identified in the literature review. These indicators Figure 13 combine an exposure component (indicators measur-

ing tourism inflows, such as arrivals per inhabitant) and a territorial sensitivity component (indicators measuring regional tourism structures, such as employment in the tourism sector) into **bivariate indicators**:

- Importance of tourism for the local or regional economy (% of gross value added (GVA)²² and % of employment)
- Tourism intensity & density
- Growth in tourist arrivals/nights spent
- Indicator pairs combining the above

The Tier 3 indicators (local indicators) are informed by the literature review and the findings of the case studies. They form a “pool” of potential indicators which can be used depending on the destination’s specificities and particular needs. The following key issues need to be taken into account and measured, if possible, in almost every destination affected by overtourism:

- Size of the actual “**tourist**” area in absolute figures and in relation to the overall destination or municipal area. Ideally, tourism density and intensity should then be calculated separately for those highly impacted areas.
- **Seasonality** is a key issue of overtourism. Tourism density and intensity should be measured separately for peak month(s) and the low season.
- **Day visitors** (including cruise ship passengers in coastal or island destinations) are an important driver of overtourism. Therefore, their numbers (in absolute terms and in relation to overnight tourists) should be added when calculating tourism intensity and density. Furthermore, their spatial and temporal visitation patterns as well as their spending in relation to overnight tourists should be measured, if possible. However, collecting data on day visitors may be one of the biggest challenges when monitoring overtourism. Using big data (e.g. tracking visitor movements through mobile phones) instead of, or in addition to, conducting surveys might open up new opportunities.
- The rising share of **private accommodation** offered on platforms such as Airbnb contributes to spreading overtourism into previously unaffected urban neighbourhoods. Their share of the overall accommodation offer and their spatial distribution should therefore be measured.
- The “**sentiments**” of both **residents** and **tourists** as an important impact of overtourism must be taken into account more systematically when managing an affected destination. This can be done either by direct surveys or by using data from online platforms such as TripAdvisor or Instagram (for tourists).

In addition, the workshop discussions highlighted several indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure and territorial sensitivity) as relevant across all destination types:

- *Change in tourism intensity combined with the average net migration rate, especially for coastal and rural destinations. A high burden from tourism and undesirable behaviour may reduce the quality of life of residents in the hosting region. Additional burdens can come from increasing costs of living due to increasing housing prices. This may lead to stronger pressures to emigrate as it becomes increasingly unattractive to reside in a tourism hotspot.*
- *Change in tourism intensity combined with the change in gross value added from tourism activities or with percentage of employment from tourism activities. As tourism activities become increasingly attractive as an economic sector and attract more investments, it may displace other economic activities (in terms of relative share of the sector), leading to (over-)specialisation. This increases economic vulnerability in times of economic crises and other crises reducing the movement of people (e.g., pandemics), generally necessitating public support to the tourism sector.*

²² Eurostat offers GVA and employment data for the NACE sectors G-I and G-J, however, not for the individual sub-sectors. This covers economic activities closely associated with tourism (such as accommodation). Sectors: wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities, information and communication.

- *Change in tourist intensity combined with multimodal accessibility*, especially for urban areas. In part due to their high levels of accessibility, cities are attractive to visitors, especially for short stays.
- *Tourism intensity combined with artificial surface area, water consumption per capita, etc.*, for destinations restricted in terms of local resources and reserves. The strain on local utilities and infrastructure due to a high day-time population compared to a low permanent population was highlighted in the discussions. Particularly water consumption was mentioned in this context. The lack of local/regional (natural) resources places a burden on destinations, particularly when encountering a large daytime or non-permanent population. When restricted in terms of local resources and reserves, be it with respect to surface area for construction, environmental reserves etc., planning decisions need to be taken with great care, as to not exhaust the available reserves.
- *Change in tourist intensity combined with change in CO₂ emissions per capita*. With high numbers of incoming tourists come higher pollution levels in the region. This can be approximated by looking at the growth of CO₂ emissions per capita compared to the increases in tourism intensity over similar timeframes.

7.2.2. Recommendations at EU level

Even though overtourism is largely a regional or local phenomenon that should consequently be managed at those levels, external driving forces are better managed, or at least informed on, at EU or national level. In particular, EU institutions could do the following:

- Support destinations potentially affected by overtourism by regularly providing **Tier 1** and particularly **Tier 2 indicators** to help them assess their general risk of unbalanced tourism development.
- Provide guidelines for **multi-level cross-regional cooperation** in order to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism (see following chapter).
- Develop a **common data space for tourism** and fair data sharing. This was one of the core requests of the destinations in the workshop discussions. This common data space should further be connected to other sectors' data spaces, consistent with the Data Act²³. Stakeholders such as the tourism industry, SMEs and destination management organisations should collaborate and agree on common practices (Code of Conduct) to actively share tourism-related data in a European Tourism Data Space. A first draft of the Code of Conduct on tourism data sharing was just released and should be agreed upon by stakeholders in the course of 2022.
- **Short-term rentals (STRs)** have been addressed as drivers for overtourism, in particular in urban destinations. The discussions in the workshops called for more transparency and fair market conditions for STRs. The Commission launched the STR initiative, undertaking a public consultation²⁴ in 2021 to support the development of a framework for STRs as well as to increase transparency and improve the market access for hosts. Together with the Digital Services Act²⁵, the Digital Markets Act²⁶ and other relevant legislation it will support the regulatory environment of STRs.

7.2.3. Recommendations at national level

The following recommendations are directed at stakeholders in charge of national tourism policies, in particular governments, and national tourism bodies such as industry

²³ [Data Act: Businesses and citizens in favour of a fair data economy | Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁴ [Tourist services – short-term rental initiative \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁵ [The Digital Services Act package - Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁶ [The Digital Markets Act: ensuring fair and open digital markets - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

federations and tourism boards. They may also apply to federal states in countries such as Germany.

- **Multi-level cross-regional cooperation** is necessary to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism. This also applies to the coordination along the supply chain in affected regions, including non-tourism actors. This level of stakeholder cooperation can be difficult and resource intensive. National or EU guidelines on stakeholder involvement in sustainable tourism development may mitigate this issue.
- National organisations may also provide **country-specific data** for Tier 1 and Tier 2 indicators and inform stakeholders about new trends (such as increasing demand from overseas markets) that may affect tourism destinations.
- **Big data solutions** (such as mobile phone network data) provide accurate monitoring of tourism inflows and hotspots and may be used to provide time-sensitive information in steering systems. However, these systems are generally expensive and technically complex and DMOs lack capacities or financial resources to implement these systems. As such, national (and possibly EU) support and provision of these data services can alleviate this gap.
- Where the implementation of **capacity restrictions**, especially at ports and airports, is under the jurisdiction of national governments, care should be taken to consider the needs of regional and local governments and citizen groups.

7.2.4. Recommendations at regional and local levels

The following recommendations are directed at tourism- and non-tourism stakeholders in charge of regional and municipal policies, planning, and management, in particular local governments, destination management organisations and local tourism industry associations.

- Destinations need to adopt an **appropriate definition** of overtourism to enable an objective understanding of the phenomenon in their local context in order to avoid subjective perceptions by various stakeholder groups, particularly residents. The definition of what constitutes overtourism should be developed in a participatory process.
- Destinations should define ways to explore what medium- and long-term balance of tourism means for their destination in order to avoid overtourism in their **general planning and management framework** and to acknowledge this phenomenon as an existing aspect of contemporary tourism development.
- Destinations may want to adopt a framework to **oversee overtourism** as a phenomenon beyond classical economic key performance indicators to enable a more data-driven and systematic analysis of the sector in a holistic way.
- In order to achieve this, the **collection and analysis of data** at a relevant scale, frequency and reliability on the economic, social and environmental facets of tourism in a systematic and continuous fashion is recommended. Ideally, this complements existing data collection frameworks, and not duplicates them.
- Including residents and **stakeholder participation** in policymaking, as well as their consultation (e.g., via surveys) reveals “pain-points” and increases tourism acceptance in the destinations. This is particularly crucial in areas with a high reliance on tourism as an economic sector and in vulnerable areas with low absorption capacities, such as in rural areas.
- The social dimension needs to be captured to monitor overtourism. This can be done via **resident and visitor surveys**, preferably at the local and regional level. However, not all DMOs are able or allowed to conduct such surveys.
- **Steering systems** (e.g., awareness campaigns, dynamic pricing and pre-booking) may be used to mitigate the burdens of visitors. This can be done in conjunction with big-data solutions to pin-point tourist hotspots.
- **Visitor management** systems should rely on real-time and up-to-date information provision. They can be exercised in different ways, ranging from crowd monitoring to improving infrastructure in heavily visited areas to **dispersal**

strategies by creating additional infrastructure and alternative tourism offers in less visited parts of a destination.

- **Demarketing** may be a solution to discourage certain undesirable tourist groups from visiting a destination.
- Systematic **capacity building** in the context of indicator systems and monitoring is necessary at DMOs to enable the use of comprehensive monitoring systems. Many DMOs lack capacities and dedicated personnel to develop and implement indicator systems. In the case of persisting capacities or low resources, the DMO may wish to implement reduced sets of indicators, focusing on easy-to-collect data.
- Effective planning to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism is recommended. This may have to include various **regulatory provisions** (e.g., on short-term rentals, time limits on hotel permits) or **taxes** levied on harmful tourist activities. In particular, it is necessary to curtail individual automobile traffic, one of the most noxious sources of negative overtourism impacts, and shift traffic flows more to **public transportation** options.

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Appendix 1: Destinations affected by overtourism

The maps below present a finer view on the regions identified (in Task A.4) as affected by overtourism. The regions are characterised according to their typology (urban, rural, coastal, island, and mountainous).

Map A.1: Coastal destinations

Source: Project team, 2022

Map A.3: Mountain destinations

Source: Project team, 2022

Map A.4: Rural destinations

Source: Project team, 2022

Map A.5: Urban destinations

Source: Project team, 2021

Appendix 2: Data sources

Table A.1: Data sources

Indicator	Data source	Year
Map 1, Destinations affected by overtourism	Differentiated by type: Based on literature review Task A.1	2021
Map 2, Gross value added from tourism activities as a share of total gross value added	Eurostat: nama_10r_3gva; NACE sectors G-I and G-J (NUTS3)	2018
Map 3, Employment from tourism activities as a share of total employment	Eurostat: nama_10r_3empers; NACE sectors G-I and G-J (NUTS3)	2018
Map 4, Tourism density (2018)	ÖIR, based on Eurostat: number of bed-nights (NUTS2; tour_cap_nuts2) and area by NUTS 3 region (reg_area3) Regionalisation via population data: Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region [demo_r_d2jan] and NUTS3 region [demo_r_gind3]	2018
Map 5, Tourism intensity (2018)	ÖIR based on Eurostat: Eurostat: number of bed-nights (NUTS2; tour_cap_nuts2) and Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS3 region [demo_r_gind3] Regionalisation via population data: Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region [demo_r_d2jan] and NUTS3 region [demo_r_gind3]	2018
Map 6, Heatmap of tourism exposure in the Naples area	ÖIR, based locations in Open Street Map with the tag <i>tourism attractions</i> [various] and <i>accommodations</i> [various]	2021
Map 7, Indicator: Change in tourism intensity (arrivals) 2015-2019	ÖIR, based on Open Street Map and Eurostat	2021, 2015-2019
Map 8, Indicator: Change in labour market importance of tourism and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019)	Tourism exposure indicator: ÖIR, based on Open Street Map and Eurostat Territorial sensitivity indicator: DG AGRI, Eurostat	2021, 2015-2019
Map 9, Indicator: Change in economic importance of tourism and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019)	Tourism exposure indicator: ÖIR, based on Open Street Map and Eurostat Territorial sensitivity indicator: Eurostat	2021, 2015-2019
Map 10, Indicator: Accessibility and change in tourism intensity (arrivals; 2015-2019)	Tourism exposure indicator: ÖIR, based on Open Street Map and Eurostat Territorial sensitivity indicator: Multimodal accessibility, S&W Spiekermann & Wegener, Urban and Regional Research	2021, 2015-2019, 2014
Figure 15, Monthly air passenger arrivals (EU-27)	Eurostat	2008-2019
Figure 16, Monthly extra-EU-27 air passenger arrivals (EU-27)	Eurostat	2008-2019
Figure 17, Indicator: Change in tourism intensity (arrivals) 2015-2019 (%) and tourism intensity (arrivals) in 2019	ÖIR, based on Open Street Map and Eurostat	2021, 2015-2019

Source: Project team, 2022

Appendix 3: Methodological approach Tier 2 indicators

Methodological approach Tier 2 indicators

The **technical principles** to be considered for the development of tier two indicators are:

- Indicators are commonly accepted/well-justified by scientific literature and empirical studies (based on literature review)
- Indicators should be available at relevant territorial resolution as NUTS2/3
- Indicators are measurable and data is easily available

It is necessary that indicators appropriately cover the diverse backgrounds and starting points of the destinations, this includes consideration of territorial specificity and different socio-economic contexts, to name a few. In addition to this, providing adequately comprehensive insight on the various impacts of overtourism will be considered. As such, the following set of **content-related principles** is proposed:

- Indicators are relevant for all types of destinations and, at the same time, they capture the diversity of territorial specificities as well as specific socio-economic and tourism situations
- Indicators should cover all three pillars of sustainability (economic, environmental and socio-cultural) in order to depict all facets of the impact of overtourism.
- The indicator list should be comprehensive enough to enable destinations to choose the most relevant indicators (following appropriate guidance).

Figure A.1: A theoretical concept of tourism impact

Source: ESPON TOURISM, 2022.

Based on the principles outlined above, an important aspect of the indicator framework is that it should be able to capture diverse impacts of overtourism within a region. This requires one to refer not only to purely tourism-related indicators but also socio-economic indicators. Thus, the most appropriate framework to measure overtourism bases itself on the exposure-sensitivity model. This refers to the tourism exposure on the region, **measured by tourism indicators**, and territorial sensitivity of the region, **measured by territorial/socio-economic context indicators** (see Figure A.1). The product of combining the two types of indicators reflects the (over)tourism impact in a specific field, depending on the type and theme of paired indicators. Nevertheless, to interpret the value of such a combination of indicators, one needs to place it in the context of various destinations, i.e., by benchmarking.

The developed indicator pairs combining socio-economic and tourism data are assessed to analyse thresholds in carrying capacity. The definition of clear thresholds indicating

whether a region is burdened by overtourism or not is related to a series of challenges, as identified by consortium members in ESPON Tourism (ESPON, 2021):

- Carrying capacity itself is an “optimisation problem” – assuming that there is a “border situation” of the territorial context, where one additional unit of input (in our case tourism intensity) will result in a crossing of the capacity threshold.
- At the same time, there is no strict threshold which can be established but territorially specific situations or target corridors defining the carrying capacity.

The indicator computation activity will involve two main steps:

- Combining pairs of indicators: the approach to measuring the risk of overtourism involves combining indicators from both sets of data, socio-economic/territorial and tourism, according to the tourism exposure-territorial sensitivity framework described in Task D.1.
- Interpretation of indicator pairs: the values of two indicators have to be interpreted and benchmarked in order to be interpreted in terms of risk of overtourism.

The performance of the developed indicator pairs will have to be assessed in relation with another observation: i.e., the degree of tourism performance (exposure indicator) will be compared to the associated territorial performance (territorial sensitivity indicator). An overview of the relative assessment of a given indicator pair is provided in Figure A.2, below. The developed indicators will be validated in stakeholder workshops at a later stage of this project.

Figure A.2: Carrying capacity assessment

Source: ESPON TOURISM, 2022

Regionalisation using OSM data

To arrive at an estimate of the number of bed-nights or arrivals at NUTS3 level in a given region, the NUTS2 value of the indicator has been multiplied by the *share* of attractions and accommodations points of interest from Open Street Map (OSM) between the given NUTS3 region and the associated NUTS2 region.

$$ValueN3_i = share\ of\ N3\ attractions\ and\ accommodations_i * ValueN2_i$$

OSM²⁷ is a collaborative mapping service which provides a geodatabase of the world. The extraction and analysis approach are illustrated in Figure A.3 and in the text below. OSM was assessed to be relatively reliable as a source for tourism data in countries with high ICT levels (Bustamante et al 2021). However, a limitation is that while many locations are mapped, but the information tied to each location may not necessarily be complete (ibid.)

Figure A.3: Open Street Map extraction and analysis approach

Source: Project team, 2022

In a first step, the project team took an inventory of all potential types of points of interest (POI) relevant to tourist activities. POIs are locations on the map which are tied to specific features of the area, buildings, or sites. These POIs are tagged according to their function and type in OSM, enabling a categorisation of landmarks, locations, etc. A full overview of these tags is available online and was analysed by the project team along their potential use. From the selection of relevant tags for tourism, the project team selected tags tied to tourist attractions (such as museums, natural features and other elements which have a touristic function) and accommodations (such as hotels, hostels etc.). The number of POI are subsequently cleaned and aggregated per NUTS2 and NUTS3 region.

As this approach only features a regional application of points of interest data within a given NUTS2 region with no comparison between individual NUTS2 regions or countries, it limits the bias which can be introduced due to differences in knowledge of the OSM platform between individual regions or countries. This mitigates issues encountered with OSM data, such as the under- and overrepresentation of countries due to the inhabitants' knowledge of the mapping platform.

²⁷ See: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>

Appendix 4: Case study indicators

The Tier 3 indicators are fed from the case study results (Task B). These indicators represent a pool of good practice indicators which can be chosen from, depending on the destination's specificities.

Table A.2: Tier 3 indicator pool

Indicator name	Theme
Overnights	General
Bus arrivals	General
Cruise ships and passenger arrivals	General
Mobile phone user info	General
Accommodation type	General
Length of stay	General
Group size	General
Visitor loyalty	General
Direct/Indirect economic impacts	General
Net revenue overnight stays	General
Stays in private accommodation	General
Tax collected from private accommodation (Airbnb)	General
Seasonality	General
Temporal concentration of visitors	General
Accommodation capacities	General
Tourism employment (e.g., nr of employees, productivity)	General
Percent of female enterprises	General
Percent of employees in the accommodation and food service sector/by citizenship	General
Flight movements	General
Number of day visitors	General
Number of visitors at tourist attractions	General
Number of visitor entrances to the park	General
Waiting time due to crowds at park entrance	General
Overnights	General
Number of beachgoers	General
Vehicle numbers in carparks	General
Number of ecolabelled tourism businesses	General
innovation	General
Production & sustainable consumption	General
Use and regional planning, tourism development supervision	General
Cultural heritage & traditions	General
Sports tourism	General
Safety, security, health	General
Governance	General
Condition of infrastructure	General
Eco counters on strategic entry points, trails	General
Share of local products	General
Renovation according to highest architectural and environmental criteria	General

Indicator name	Theme
Total number of participants of educational programs	General
Support of visitors to the conservation of park values	General
Number of operators with sustainability certification	General
Governance	General
Investment-free areas	General
Number of sustainable offers	General
Visitor Sentiments/Satisfaction/Experience Quality	Visitor Destination Perception
Resident perceptions, quality of life/satisfaction	Visitor Destination Perception
Inclusivity and accessibility	Visitor Destination Perception
Health	Visitor Destination Perception
Number and diversity of information services/projects for stakeholders	Visitor Destination Perception
Number of projects that examine the form of knowledge transfer during planning	Visitor Destination Perception
Number of events, actions and specific information to stakeholders	Visitor Destination Perception
Number of projects that include a participation process	Visitor Destination Perception
Share of environmental visitor transport	Environment
General visitor mobility	Environment
Quality of public transport accessibility at off-peak times (changes)	Environment
Solid waste management	Environment
Waste quantities (weight)	Environment
Water management	Environment
Wastewater management	Environment
Energy management	Environment
Climate change & destination capacity	Environment
Long-Term Air Quality Monitoring Program (carbon-dioxide, sulphur dioxide, nitrogen oxide and water vapor etc.)	Environment
Environmental Assessment Tool/Environmental Impact Assessment	Environment
Biodiversity	Environment
Soil quality	Environment
Water and air quality	Environment
Land use	Environment
Landscape Diversity	Environment
Landscape perception (LABES survey)	Environment
Change in the plant world (Pro Rigi observations)	Environment
Breeding bird population	Environment
Biodiversity Promotion Areas	Environment
Share of renewable energies	Environment
Greenhouse gas emissions	Environment
Drinking water consumption per capita	Environment

Source: Project team, 2022, based on case study findings

Appendix 5: Correlation analysis outputs Tier 2 indicators

The project team undertook a correlation analysis calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient using complete observations for the NUTS2 and the NUTS3 components respectively. The results are printed below.

Table A.3: Correlation analysis outputs (NUTS2 components)

	Arrival intensity (Change 15-19, %)		Bed nights (Change 15-19, %)		Bed night intensity (Change 15-19, %)	
	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value
Change in tourism employment (15-19, %)	0.10	0.14	0.15	0.02	0.16	0.02
Change in capacity (15-19, %)	0.58	<0.01	0.60	<0.01	0.62	<0.01
Change in occupancy rate (15-19, %)	0.05	0.48	0.05	0.40	0.02	0.81
Change in air passengers (15-19, %)	0.37	<0.01	0.29	<0.01	0.29	<0.01
Change in artificial surface (15-18, %)	0.05	0.48	0.08	0.24	0.07	0.27
CO ₂ per capita growth (10-20, %)	0.25	<0.01	0.21	<0.01	0.32	<0.01
CO ₂ per capita (2020)	-0.12	0.06	-0.13	0.05	-0.13	0.04
Water per capita per day growth (10-20, %)	0.40	<0.01	0.34	0.00	0.44	<0.01
Water per capita per day growth (2020)	0.07	0.30	0.07	0.30	0.12	0.08
Change in the unemployment rate (15-19, %)	-0.31	<0.01	-0.28	<0.01	-0.29	<0.01

Source: Project team, 2022

Table A.4: Correlation analysis outputs (NUTS3 components)

	Arrival intensity (Change 15-19, %)		Bed nights (Change 15-19, %)		Arrivals (Change 15-19, %)		Arrival density (Change 15-19, %)	
	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value
GVA in tourism related sectors (Change 15-19, %)	0.04	0.15	0.04	0.16	0.04	0.23	0.04	0.19
Average net migration (15-19, %)	-0.44	<0.01	-0.40	<0.01	-0.02	0.58	-0.26	<0.01
Employment in tourism related sectors (Change 15-19, %)	0.15	<0.01	0.17	<0.01	0.14	<0.01	0.14	<0.01
Multimodal accessibility (2014)	-0.36	<0.01	-0.31	<0.01	-0.03	0.33	-0.25	<0.01

Source: Project team, 2022

Appendix 6: Annotated compendium of currently existing literature on overtourism [separately]

Appendix 7: Explanatory note on the adjustments to the compendium structure (Task C)

After completing the comprehensive literature review on unbalanced tourism growth at destination level (Task A) and the case studies of good practices (Task B), as well as conducting an internal, task related workshop, the structure of the compendium presented in the project inception report was slightly adjusted. The consortium came to the conclusion that the new structure is more appropriate as it provides a better basis for presenting the recommended publications and for developing a concise and handy document.

With the objective of structuring the central publications on unbalanced tourism growth as clearly as possible and making them easily accessible to the interested stakeholder groups, the following changes were introduced:

- **Some (sub)chapters were merged, respectively restructured.** This applies for example to the chapter on the causes and impacts of overtourism. The majority of the publications analyse both, the causes and the impacts of the phenomenon. Consequently, it is considered the most reasonable to merge these sub-topics to one chapter. The topic of Covid-19 and unbalanced tourism growth is due to its currency and an increasing amount of literature presented in a separate main chapter.
- Furthermore, **some further (sub)chapters were added.** For example, due to their increasing importance, sub-chapters on ICT and social media as well as other innovative approaches were introduced. Also, in coherence with the project report, a sub-chapter focusing on unbalanced tourism growth at heritage sites and in protected areas was added.
- Besides, **some originally proposed chapters were omitted.** This applies to the chapter focusing on the outputs of Task E (the workshop series). Instead, the workshops will be used to verify the compendium and, if deemed necessary, complement the final document with further publications on the topic of unbalanced tourism growth. Also, the originally proposed chapter "Identified EU destinations and destination types potentially facing overtourism" was omitted, respectively restructured. The special characteristics of the different types of destinations assessed throughout the study are outlined within the chapter "Good practice, destination specific case studies" (chapter 6). Publications about Covid-19 and unbalanced tourism growth are presented in a separate chapter (see above).
- Furthermore, the **originally proposed appendices** (the case study reports) **conducted throughout the project were omitted**, since they will be part of the final project report. Including them as well in the compendium might exceed the capacity of the already extensive document, and make it less clearly structured and handy for the reader.
- Finally, **references to the case studies of good practice** were integrated throughout the document in order to illustrate the (sub)topics further and establish a stronger link to the destination examples analysed within Task B.

As formerly mentioned, these adjustments were introduced in order to ensure that the main purpose of Task C is fulfilled, namely to create a comprehensive, easily accessible array of evidence behind the phenomenon of unbalanced tourism growth affecting destinations in the EU and elsewhere.

Appendix 8: Task B Destination-level case studies [separately]

- Florence
- Lucerne
- Vienna
- Bay of Lübeck
- Geirangerfjord
- Iceland
- Palma
- Mallorca
- Malta
- Burren and Cliffs of Moher
- Monts d'Ardèche
- Plitvice Lakes
- Bled
- Dolomites Region
- Rigi

Appendix 9: Consulted organisations

Table A.5: Case study interviewees

List of consulted organisations	Destination
Economic Activities and Tourism Directorate of Florence (Promozione Economica e Turistica Direzione Attività Economiche e Turismo; Servizio Promozione Economica Turistica e Lavoro)	Florence
Commissioner for economic issues of the City of Lucerne	Lucerne
Vienna Tourist Board Academic expert	Vienna
Director of the Tourism Agency of Lübeck Bay – TALB	Bay of Lübeck
Visit Iceland Department of Tourism and Innovation, Icelandic Ministry of Industries and Innovation Icelandic Tourism Cluster	Iceland
Fundació Turisme Palma 365 Palma XXI Consell de Mallorca, Tourism Department Sustainable Tourism Observatory of Majorca, Fundació Mallorca Turisme	Palma
Consell de Mallorca Sustainable Tourism Observatory of Majorca, Fundació Mallorca Turisme	Mallorca
Malta Tourism Authority	Malta
Burren Ecotourism Network Burren and Cliffs of Moher UNESCO Global Geopark Cliffs of Moher Visitor Experience	Ireland
Monts d'Ardèche Regional Natural Park Development Manager of Ardèche Tourism Development Agency Bénédicte Observatory of the tourism economy for Ardèche Tourism Development Agency	Monts d'Ardèche
Touristic group of the Plitvice Lake Municipality.	Plitvice Lakes
RBAG RigiPlus AG	Rigi

Source: Project team, 2022

Table A.6: Consulted EU experts

List of consulted EU organisations
Europarc Federation (Barcelona Office)
Palacký University (Olomouc, Czech Republic) on (Central-) Eastern Europe
CIPRA

Source: Project team, 2022

Appendix 10: D.2.2 – Final workshop report

A10.1. Introduction

A10.1.1. Context and objectives of the assignment

The Executive European Innovation Council and SMEs (EISMEA), under the powers delegated by the European Commission, Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROW), commissioned the study “Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level – root causes, impacts, existing solutions and good practices.

The study was carried out by Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development and its consortium partner, ÖIR GmbH – the Austrian Institute for Regional Studies, together with Institute of Tourism and Mobility (ITW) at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts – Business.

The objective of the study was first, to build solid evidence on the phenomenon of overtourism, in particular by focusing on multiple the root causes and effects of overtourism at the destination level. An additional objective was the gathering of concrete best practice solutions (preventive and mitigating actions) that have been successfully applied by tourism destinations in the EU and globally.

It also aimed to gather evidence on whether and in what ways the COVID-19 crisis has led to the changes in strategies and actions of the tourism destinations when addressing overtourism phenomenon. This study provided new data and fill knowledge gaps, in particular by focusing on the complexity of less addressed causes of overtourism, such as social media, digital platforms and peer-to-peer platforms. Second, the study further proposed a set of overtourism indicators that can serve tourism destinations in establishing their risk analysis frameworks, allowing them to detect the potential risk of overtourism and address the associated challenges in a timely manner.

Finally, the study aimed to contribute to the dialogue among the EU tourism stakeholders on sustainable tourism. This was done by organising a series of workshops for tourism destinations in order to exchange best practice solutions, identifying common problems, assess and validating the proposed indicators. Five workshops were therefore organised in locations, each, representing one of the five types of destinations examined within the framework of this study, namely urban, rural, mountain, island and coastal destinations. A concluding sixth workshop was organised in Brussels.

A10.1.2. Overview and aims of the workshops

The study “Unbalanced tourism growth at destination level – root causes, impacts, existing solutions and good practices”, as a follow up of Task A (gathering evidence on overtourism), Task B (case studies), and Task D (overtourism indicators), had one of the key tasks the organisation of five destination-specific workshops and one concluding workshop at EU-level. Each workshop intended to shed light on the specificities of the type of destination in regards to the issues linked to overtourism to better comprehend the linkages between tourism and territorial settings. The concluding workshop in Brussels also aimed at linking the findings and conclusions to the EU transition pathway for tourism and green transition in particular. The following workshops were organised:

- Island destinations workshop hosted in Valletta, Malta, on 9 December 2021,
- Urban destinations virtual workshop on 20 and 21 January 2022,
- Coastal destinations virtual workshop on 23 and 24 February 2022,
- Rural destinations virtual workshop on 17 and 18 March 2022,
- Mountain destinations workshop hosted in Munich, Germany, on 26 April 2022,
- EU-level workshop, hosted in Brussels, Belgium, on 20 May 2022.

The workshops aimed to connect tourism stakeholders from destinations to foster peer-to-peer learning on problems and solutions to unbalanced tourism growth. Participants were invited to present solution approaches to unsustainable tourism growth and its environmental and socio-economic impacts on the regions. Moreover, challenges and bottlenecks hindering the mitigation of unbalanced tourism growth were examined. Importantly, the workshops focussed on identifying concrete steps for destinations to move towards more sustainable practices and mitigate the impacts of unbalanced tourism growth. During the workshops, participants tested the practical application of proposed indicators for overtourism risk assessment.

A10.1.3. Content and organisation of the destination workshops

A10.1.3.1. Approach to the destination workshops

The project team implemented onsite and virtual destination workshops. The destination workshops were foreseen as full day events. However, in the case of fully virtual workshops (particularly the coastal and the rural destinations workshops), the events were organised as two half-day events. As such, the exact timing of the agenda items varied. Please see a representative sample agenda of a two-day workshop below.

Box A.1: Day 1 agenda

Timing	Sessions
12:45	Opening of the meeting room for the online participants
13:00	Welcoming
13:15	Introduction of participants (position/background) Participants' expectations regarding the workshop <i>Format: round of introduction in plenary session</i>
13:45	Part 1: Presentation of the project findings (Tasks A to D) <i>Format: discussion in plenary session</i>
14:15	Break
14:25	Part 2: peer-to-peer learning Presentations of the challenges and problems faced as well as identified solution approaches from different perspectives (heritage site experts, destination management organisations, infrastructure providers, residence groups, etc.) <i>Format: participants presentations and open discussions in plenary session</i>
16:25	Break
16:40	Conclusions, summary of discussions and next steps <i>in plenary session</i>
16:50	End of the workshop

Box A.2: Day 2 agenda

Timing	Sessions
08:45	Opening of the meeting room for the online participants
09:00	Welcoming and summary of Day 1
09:15	Part 3: how to identify, assess, and address tourism growth imbalances: a structured approach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the discussion format ▪ Group work: Assessment of overtourism impacts in rural areas via a systemic picture <i>Format: Interactive discussion</i>
10:00	Break

Timing	Sessions
10:10	<p>Part 3 (cont.): how to identify, assess, and address tourism growth imbalances: a structured approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Selection of main overtourism impact indicators (as per systemic picture) ▪ Maps and illustrations of overtourism indicators ▪ Discussion of solution approaches <p><i>Format: Interactive discussion</i></p>
11:10	Break
11:20	<p>Part 4: Validation and key challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Group discussion 1: overtourism indicators, data availability and measurement ▪ Group discussion 2: solution approaches and governance ▪ Plenary discussion: Pathways to sustainable tourism destination and future developments <p><i>Format: Brainstorm and plenary – group work</i></p>
12:30	Conclusions, summary of findings and next steps <i>in plenary session</i>
12:40	End of the workshop Closing remarks

Welcoming and participants' introduction

During the introduction of the workshop, participants were asked to give a short overview of their background and stake in the overtourism debate.

During **Part 1**, members of the research team presented the assignment, its objectives, and main findings.

In **Part 2**, representatives of different destinations were invited to share the main issues and challenges they face and which solutions (if any) have been found to address the issues. The aim of this peer-to-peer session was to focus on problems which may be common across various destinations belonging to a given type and identify innovative ideas which may be transferable.

In **Part 3**, participants were introduced to a methodology which builds on existing knowledge and characteristics of a given destination type. During the session, participants simulated the application of the methodology to the type of destination they represent. Concretely, participants were directly involved, drawing a systemic picture (either virtually or physically). Building on an indicator brainstorming exercise, an analysis of the tourism impacts (relying on the indicators developed with the scope of the project) was provided by the research team and discussed with the participants.

Over the course of implementation of the workshop series, this section was adapted to improve the discussion flow. In general, two or three indicator pairs were presented, in addition to an EU-level map, as well as several (two-to-four) destination maps.

Finally, in **Part 4**, a brainstorming session was organised with the participants. Participants were free to choose their preferred topic among two group discussions:

- Group discussion 1: overtourism indicators, data availability and measurement
- Group discussion 2: solution approaches and governance

This was followed by a plenary session on development prospects for the tourism industry.

Over the course of the project, this session was adapted to improve flexibility and stimulate discussion. Initially this session included a world café session focussed along four topics (validation & improvement, issues of data availability and appropriateness of the territorial degree of resolution, governance and role of EU institutions, and pathways towards sustainable tourism).

A10.1.3.2. Workshop participants

For each workshop the research team created a contact database (based on internet research) gathering a large array of tourism related actors of that destination type, including DMOs, stakeholders, such as local groups, as well as infrastructure providers. This contact database was created by assessing the inventory of identified regions with overtourism (Task A), researching alternative destinations (at risk of overtourism and not affected by overtourism), and subsequently, identifying contact people at the destinations.

The research team reached out via social media and targeted invitations to the following stakeholder types as potential participants:

- Several experts (high-level practitioners and academics),
- Representatives from the other case study destinations, as well as representatives of other destinations of that type who may want to take part in the peer-to-peer learning session.
- Thematically relevant representatives/experts.
- Representatives from other interested destinations (destination management organisations, regional and local authorities, tourism industry representatives (associations, interest groups), residents' organisations of the destinations and infrastructure providers (transport, waste and other utilities etc).

A10.1.4. Content and organisation of the EU-level workshop

A10.1.4.1. Approach to the EU-level workshop

The EU-level workshop was planned as a half-day event in Brussel at the premises of the European Commission. The workshop foresaw the possibility of virtual participation.

Box A.3: Agenda EU-level workshop

Timing	Sessions
08:45	Arrival onsite, health and safety, and registration – coffee/tea
09:00	Welcoming and introduction:
09:15	Introduction of participants
09:40	Part 1: Presentation of the project findings and recommendations <i>Format: Presentation of the key project findings followed by a Q&A session</i>
10:15	Part 2: Comparative analysis of overtourism per destination type Cross-analysis of causes, impacts and solution approaches found in island, rural, mountain, urban, and coastal destinations. This analysis highlights similarities and differences across the various types of destinations. <i>Format: Presentation and open discussions in plenary session</i>
11:00	Coffee/tea break
11:10	Part 3: Transition pathway for tourism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the Transition Pathway for Tourism – policy context ▪ Panel discussion: How more sustainable destinations can contribute to and benefit from the Transition Pathway for Tourism <i>Format: Brief presentation followed by panel discussion</i>
12:45	Conclusions and introduction to FUTURIUM
13:00	End of the workshop

After a welcoming by key speakers to set the frame of the project and workshop, all participants, on site and online, were invited to provide a brief introduction.

During **Part 1**, members of the research team presented the assignment, its objectives, main findings, and key recommendations. Participants were invited to reflect on the presentation in a question-and-answers session.

In **Part 2**, the project team presented a cross-destination analysis of causes, impacts, and solution approaches found in island, rural, mountain, urban, and coastal destinations. This analysis highlighted differences and similarities along the destination types, as identified in the destinations workshop series and the case studies. This was followed by an open discussion with the participants.

Part 3 was organised as a panel discussion on the EU Transition Pathway for Tourism. The panel was composed of representatives from EU, national, regional, and destination level. The topic of the panel was how more sustainable destinations can contribute to and benefit from the Transition Pathway for Tourism.

The focus of this panel session was on the identification of concrete actions that would lead to more sustainable and responsible tourism destinations, therefore contributing to the transition of EU tourism ecosystem. The panel discussion was structured along the following points:

- What challenges are you encountering in your destination when building a more sustainable tourism model?
- You have heard the overview of the EU Transition Pathway for Tourism. What initiatives or strategies have you implemented (or intend to implement) in order to increase the sustainability of your destination, which in your view may contribute to the implementation of this Transition Pathway?
- How could EU further support you in building a more sustainable and more responsible tourism destination?

The moderator then concluded the workshop deriving conclusions from the discussions. The moderator also highlighted the Futurium platform, the resources available for the destinations, and invited the participants to join the discussions there.

A10.1.4.2. Workshop participants

The research team contacted and invited all participants from the previous five destination workshops to take part in this event. These invitees include:

- Experts (high-level practitioners and academics),
- Representatives from the case study destinations,
- Representatives from other interested destinations (destination management organisations, regional and local authorities, tourism industry representatives (associations, interest groups), residents' organisations, service and infrastructure providers etc.).

A10.2. Outcomes of the dialogue platform

This section presents the shortened content findings of the five destination workshops (sections A10.2.1 through A10.2.5), the EU-level workshop (section A10.2.6), and an overarching evaluation of the workshop series (section A10.2.7).

A10.2.1. Island destinations

A10.2.1.1. Peer-to-peer discussion

The issues of overtourism impacts, causes, and mitigation practices in island destinations were discussed in the peer-to-peer session. The following key points were raised by the participants:

- Island destinations seem to be affected by significant path dependency, as illustrated in the cases of Malta, Mallorca, and Cyprus. Economic re-specialisation can be difficult due to the high economic importance of the sector which causes conflicts among stakeholders.
- Soft tourism management solutions are easier to implement. Implementation of hard measures (such as taxing accommodations) can be difficult due to tax evasion. As such, taxing undesired behaviour is easier to implement. The motive of taxation can also be important, whether it is implemented to steer or to gather additional resources (as is in Cyprus).
- In the case of Cyprus, overspecialisation led to high accommodation concentration along the coast line and high seasonality. Soft steering measures include marketing as an all-year destination.
- Tourists are looking for more customised and unique experiences, providing real-time information on overcrowding can help steer tourist volumes along sites. This is also undertaken by the City of Lübeck which steers tourists to empty parking lots.
- With grow of tourist arrivals, authenticity declines (in Iceland, the English language becomes more important; international hotels enter).
- Tourist arrivals can impact (food) prices: local foodstuffs can become in-demand, pushing the price up for everyone else.

A10.2.1.2. Causes and impacts of overtourism

The outcomes of the discussion of the causes and impacts of overtourism were captured in the systemic picture below.

This discussion produced three core hypotheses between tourism impacts and socio-environmental and economic developments. These hypotheses serve as indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure component and territorial sensitivity component):

- Lack of local/regional (natural) resources leading to narrow leeway to commit mistakes. As islands are restricted in terms of local resources and reserves, be it in terms of surface area for construction, environmental reserves etc., planning decisions need to be taken with great care, as to not exhaust the available reserves. Relevant territorial sensitivity component: artificial surface area, water consumption per capita, CO₂ emissions per capita etc.
- Economic dependence on tourism activities leading to a path dependency for regional development. As tourism activities become increasingly attractive as an economic sector and attracts more investments, it may displace other economic activities (in terms of relative share of the sector) as was the case in Mallorca and Malta, leading to (over-)specialisation. This increases economic vulnerabilities in times of economic crises and other crises reducing the movement of people (e.g. pandemics), generally necessitating public support to the tourism sector. Relevant territorial sensitivity component: percentage of GVA or employment from tourism activities.
- Island destinations tend to not experience linear growth, when it comes to the development of arrivals, as tourists arrive predominantly via air transport. Due to the fixed number of seats per plane, incremental increases in transported passengers are not possible. Increases in demand exceeding current transport capacities lead to the scheduling of more flights which open additional new capacities for more tourists coming in. As such, the number of arriving tourists

grow in steps by the number of available flights. Relevant territorial sensitivity component: arrivals at nearest airport, number of bed-places, accessibility etc.

Figure A.4: Systemic picture of causes and impacts of overtourism in island destinations

A10.2.1.3. Validation session

Key outputs of the discussion of Topic 1 validation & improvement – solution approaches and expectations:

- Solution approaches: Real-time and up-to-date information provision (crowd monitoring at destinations etc.) and of use of services and amenities were highlighted multiple times as solution approaches. Additional contributions include: improving infrastructure and implementing visitor management strategies, de-marketing.
- Citizen participation: Participation of residents in policy-making, as well as their consultation (e.g. via surveys) and means of residents to be financially compensated/take part in benefit-sharing were highlighted.

- Planning solutions: Highlighted points include regulatory changes (e.g. on short-term rentals, time limits on hotel permits), taxes levied on harmful tourist activities, as well as attraction-specific points, such as dynamic pricing and booking slots.
- Monitoring and role of indicators: resident and tourist surveys to gather data, shifting away from using traditional performance indicators, environmental assessments, and the need for comparable indicators.

Key outputs of the discussion of Topic 2: "issues of data availability and appropriateness of the territorial degree of resolution":

- Data access: lack of public sector access to big data (this data is generally not shared by the companies which collect it), data alliances (as is the case in NL) may be used to create common data banks and access among destinations
- Data use: lack of interpretation of data and translation into policies and decision-making, lack of skills for data management at DMOs
- Data collection: big data sources (mobile phone data), satellite data, resident surveys
- Spatial granulation: some indicators are used at local level combined with higher level indicators (regional) was highlighted (e.g. in Barcelona).

Key outputs of the discussion of Topic 3: "governance and role of EU institutions":

- Role of EU: participants highlight the EU's role in providing common standards and guidance/direction
- Main tourism players: DMOs are the main players, ministries and national tourism authorities provide the overall vision/framework. Additionally, economic actors sometimes may have outsized influence on decision making due to lobbying. Municipalities are important for the implementation of related policies; however, they tend to lack resources to manage tourism.
- Implementing bodies (of tourism policies): private sector actors, public actors (national, regional, and local governments)
- Necessary governance actions: participative approaches involving residents are important; regulation of peer-to-peer accommodation; prime tourism locations could be limited by national government intervention (support of special tourism zones)

Key outputs of the discussion of Topic 4: "pathways towards sustainable tourism":

- Sustainability as a concept: taking the carrying capacity of the destination into account; balancing utilisation and regeneration; shift to regenerative tourism (i.e. tourism which provides a net benefit to the destination)
- Tourism strategies and potentials for further improvements: more data driven decisions and policies, transversal work among managing (city) departments, inclusion of residents
- Important trends to be addressed: digitalisation (skills, services, and marketing etc.) and decarbonation of transport. Further points include: Effects of climate change (e.g. flight shaming, demand for cooler destinations in summer, demand for low carbon tourism, energy exchange in transport, circular economy), the implications of demographic change (ageing, disabilities) and emerging market on tourism.

A10.2.2. Urban destinations

A10.2.2.1. Peer-to-peer discussion

The following points were raised by the participants in the peer-to-peer session:

- Social dimension of tourism needs to be captured, this can be done via resident and visitor surveys at, preferably local and regional level. However, not all DMOs/organisations are able/allowed to conduct such surveys.
- Cross-regional cooperation is necessary in the context of urban tourism, particularly in terms of transport interlinkages (e.g. tickets and transfers between airport and city, especially if located in different regions).
- COVID-19 and the acceleration of pre-existing trends: tourists are increasingly looking for unique experiences, away from the masses. Cities can capitalise on this with dedicated tours, as in Vienna, but this targets mainly repeat tourists.
- Spreading tourists via new points of interest does not necessarily spread demand, but rather may lead to an increase of demand as you widen the tourism offer. There may be social advantages to restricting tourist areas as you allow residents to “keep” their areas.
- Role of social media in shifting focus to new points of interest within a destination: you need the necessary infrastructure (public transportation, English-speaking residents, local willingness to interact with tourists).
- Governance measures (Florence): direct cooperation with city districts on potential attractions and relevant thematic focus, subsequent development of tailored/thematically-focussed itineraries to steer tourists. Districts and municipalities are provided with materials and guidance to manage visitors. The city also cooperates with private tourism stakeholder (guides, etc.) in regular meetings.
- Mobile phone data is expensive when used in monitoring solutions: it is necessary to purchase the datasets from the providers and subsequently use their software/platforms to analyse the data. As such the city of Florence is using WIFI hubs to real-time measure density. The city is also working on using camera recordings (in conformity with GDPR requirements). The city of Vienna also prefers to rely on their own data collection efforts as it is more sustainable than using third-party big data solutions.

A10.2.2.2. Causes and impacts of overtourism

The outcomes of the discussion of the causes and impacts of overtourism were captured in the systemic picture below.

In a following step, the participants identified core hypotheses on the relationship between overtourism and socio-economic developments in the affected areas. These hypotheses serve as indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure component and territorial sensitivity component). The most important hypotheses, in the context of urban destinations, were:

- Accessibility and tourism exposure in urban areas: Urban areas, in part due to their high levels of accessibility, are attractive to visitors, especially for short stays. Relevant indicator: Tourism exposure and multimodal accessibility.
- Pollution and tourism exposure in urban areas: With high numbers of incoming tourists come higher pollution levels in the region. This can be approximated by looking at the growth of CO₂ emissions per capita compared to the increases in tourism intensity over similar timeframes. Relevant indicator: Tourism exposure and change in CO₂ emissions per capita.
- Land competition and tourism exposure in urban areas: Economic gains from tourism activities can lead to increased regional specialisation into tourism. This puts the sector into competition with other economic and non-economic uses of land in urban areas and increases incentives to construct dedicated buildings and areas. Relevant indicator: Tourism exposure and change in surface sealing.

Figure A.5: Systemic picture of causes and impacts of overtourism in urban destinations

A10.2.2.3. Validation session

The validation session on governance and sustainability was conducted in plenary form. Presented below are the key points of the discussion:

- Tipping points in overtourism: These can occur in visitor perception (e.g. if certain im-pressions of undesirable behaviour go viral in media) and long-term skew the perception of the destination. Further tipping points are related to negative changes in quality of life as experienced by residents.
- Data should not only be looked as in an isolated manner: comprehensive indicator sets, shifting away from traditional "key performance indicators" are important in monitoring impacts. These should also be actively involved in tourism planning.
- Perception of tourists as "temporary residents": as tourists are not politically active, there is a lower incentive for governments to specifically target their needs. Generally, these impacts of overtourism are known within the region, but the political will lacks to address them. However, a resident-based perspective of the impacts can help overcome this barrier and motivate political action.

- Necessary EU-level support: Access to big data and on transport modes can help inform decision-making at destination level; support in training and bottom-up approaches; more tailored support within existing EU funding schemes; guidance and benchmarking on what the thresholds of overtourism are across regions. Overview of EU funding sources should be more accessible for potential beneficiaries as well as application cases (good practices).
- With the return to economic and social normality, a re-thinking of the modes and types of tourism is necessary, as opposed to returning to conventional pre-COVID-19 tourism.
- Cross-sectoral cooperation between stakeholders is important, also between the economic sectors, such as upstream and downstream actors.
- Comprehensive multi-actor approaches to governance are important in addressing overtourism impacts. It requires horizontal and vertical cooperation and sufficient competences to address challenges.
- Organisational change: incentivise organisations to only book in sustainable manners (travel, accommodations) can improve the sustainability of tourism activities.
- Awareness-building is necessary to shift to more sustainable tourism development.

A10.2.3. Coastal destinations

A10.2.3.1. Peer-to-peer discussion

In the peer-to-peer discussion among the participants, the following points were raised by the participants on coastal overtourism:

- On measuring the impacts of overtourism: Data collection for the 700 key performance indicators (KPIs) used to assess overtourism in Mallorca is based on a well-sampled set of 140 companies and utility providers. In addition, hotels are obliged to provide data on water and energy usage by law. Municipalities are also obliged to provide data. For municipal data, comparisons between on- and off-season data values are made to isolate the influence of tourism.
- Impact measurement is important as impacts may vary even within smaller regions (e.g. between municipalities). In the case of municipalities in Zeeland, the satisfaction of tourism varies with little observable relation with the tourism intensity. Other and more specific factors (e.g. incidence of traffic problems) may be more important than tourism intensity alone.
- On seasonality: Some destinations are highly seasonal (in this case Zeeland) and spreading the tourist inflows over more months is better in terms of economic outcomes. However, residents seem to prefer tourism inflows to be concentrated into shorter periods of time. Over the past years, the season has extended narrowing the period of time for residents in which there are fewer incoming tourists. Additionally, the accommodation type has been shifting from camping to resorts.
- On the spatial phenomena leading to overtourism: In the Bay of Lübeck, the concentration of tourists occurs due to spatial factors. The motorway (from Hamburg) is close to the beach area and tourists tend to leave at the first possible exit, overcrowding the beaches close to this exit.
- Spatial concentration of tourism into well-managed areas is not necessarily an option for all destinations: in some destinations, residents prefer tourists to integrate as opposed to staying in "tourist factories". However, this depends on the destination and residents may not always want to interact with tourists (Zeeland). In Mallorca, tourism was originally concentrated into few areas ('50s, '60s) which led to uneven economic gains from tourism.
- The varying governance levels can have an impact on the management of tourism: in the case of Mallorca, the airport policy is under the purview of the national government, limiting the possibilities for the regional government to restrict the number of incoming flights. In the case of Catalonia, tourism rarely affects only one area, requiring a higher-level perspective for governance solutions.

- Escapist tourism causes unwanted behaviour which residents may not want to see. Education (e.g., on waste disposal) and other means (e.g., limits on alcohol sales) can be important to limit this.

A10.2.3.2. Causes and impacts of overtourism

Figure A.6: Overview of challenges and solution approaches in coastal areas

In a following step, the participants identified core hypotheses on the relationship between overtourism and socio-economic developments in the affected areas. These hypotheses serve as indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure component and territorial sensitivity component). The most important hypotheses, in the context of coastal destinations, were:

- High burden from tourism and undesirable behaviour may reduce quality of life of residents. Additional burdens can come from increasing costs of living due to increasing housing prices. As such, residents may be prone to leaving the area, as it becomes increasingly unattractive to reside in. Relevant indicator: increase in tourism intensity and average net migration rate.
- Economic dependence on tourism activities leading to a path dependency for regional development. This increases economic vulnerabilities in times of economic crises and other crises reducing the movement of people (e.g. pandemics). Relevant indicator: increase in tourism intensity and percentage of employment from tourism activities.
- Lack of local/regional (natural) resources place a burden on coastal destinations, particularly when encountering a large daytime or non-permanent population which places additional burdens on water consumption. Relevant indicator: increase in tourism intensity and water consumption per capita.

A10.2.3.3. Validation session

The discussion was held in plenary format, focussing on the challenges tied to governance and overtourism management. The key points were:

- Intergovernmental cooperation is challenging. Within the context of overtourism and its wide range of impacts, intersectoral cooperation is needed. Vertical cooperation across governance levels is also important.
- It is essential to gather sufficient data as a basis for policy action. This enables appropriate targeting via public measures.

- Planning decisions, even at municipal level, can make a difference in terms of mitigating overtourism. In the case of Palma, limiting construction and renovation grants for the airport limited its expansion. Furthermore, limits were imposed on hotels and other accommodations to limit available bed places. However, the possibilities of economic development from tourism for municipalities places incentives for commercial development which does not always account for environmental damages. As such, this rests on the prioritisation of the individual municipalities.

A10.2.4. Rural destinations

A10.2.4.1. Peer-to-peer discussion

In the peer-to-peer discussion among the participants, the following points were raised by the participants on rural overtourism:

- The importance of stakeholder coordination was highlighted in the discussion of the case of the Plitvice National Park: the park implemented a pre-booking system for tour providers (who represent a major source of day visitors coming from the coastal areas). This system requires the tour providers to pre-purchase tickets they intend to sell in advance, thus limiting the uncontrolled in-flow of visitors.
- The booking and dynamic pricing system implemented by the Plitvice National Park was highlighted as being effective in managing visitor inflows and temporally deconcentrating visitors.
- Redirection of visitor streams via information campaigns can help alleviate the burden on individual destinations and divert visitors to other areas. Overtourism tends to affect only a small area within a broader rural region. As such, deconcentration strategies can help mitigate broader impacts. Further, this can enable other settlements/areas to participate economically
- Another identified issue is the impact of overtourism on housing prices. This was mentioned as affecting local residents (via out-pricing) and (seasonal) employees in the sector who could not find affordable accommodation. Additionally, individuals with second homes within the destination (with the home standing empty for the majority of the year) can further restrict the supply of affordable housing. In this context, the potential for increased emigration was mentioned.
- It was mentioned that reaching small entities (e.g. micro-SMEs) can be difficult, as they lack capacities to access funding or take part in consultation processes. In this context, LEADER²⁸ was mentioned as a potential pathway out of this issue, as many local development strategies feature a strong emphasis on tourism support and involvement of small economic actors.
- Isolated settlements cannot absorb incoming visitors easily, leaving them more exposed to impacts of overtourism. Rural tourism tends to be very localised, with strong inflows in small areas. This does not necessarily spill-over to other rural areas in the vicinity.
- Overreliance on tourism as a source of income can leave regions vulnerable to sudden changes in tourist inflows (e.g. with the pandemic limiting incoming tourists). Particularly small settlements in rural regions without significant other economic sectors are exposed to these macro-shocks.
- The overall tourism inflows are concerning if the situation is evolving rapidly, i.e. when the inflows pick up quickly over a timespan. This may require support from municipalities.

²⁸ LEADER "Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale", meaning 'Links between the rural economy and development actions' is a bottom-up initiative funded by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development. It empowers local actors via Local Action Groups to target needs in the area by selecting and funding relevant projects aimed at promoting territorial development, including environmental and social issues.

A10.2.4.2. Causes and impacts of overtourism

Figure A.7: Overview of challenges and solution approaches in rural areas

In a following step, the participants identified core hypotheses on the relationship between overtourism and socio-economic developments in the affected areas. These hypotheses serve as indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure component and territorial sensitivity component). The most important hypotheses, in the context of rural destinations, were:

- A key issue highlighted across the discussions was the declining affordability of housing for local residents (particularly younger individuals and families). This may lead to stronger pressures to emigrate. As such, one identified indicator pairing is the combination of change in tourism intensity (exposure) and average net migration (context).
- Overspecialisation into tourism, with the resulting economic imbalances and increased regional vulnerability, was also a reoccurring topic in the workshop sessions. Rural areas may have little economic alternatives to tourism and initial specialisation may lead to relatively set pathway dependencies in terms of regional development. A relevant indicator pairing is the change in tourism intensity (exposure) combined with the change in gross value added from tourism activities (context).
- The strain on local utilities and infrastructure due to high day-time population compared to a low permanent population was highlighted in the discussions. Particularly water consumption was mentioned in this context. Relevant indicator: the combination of change in tourism intensity (exposure) and change in water consumption per capita (context).

A10.2.4.3. Validation session

Keys discussion points on the topic indicators, data availability, and measurement: were:

- The importance of integrating the perspective of various stakeholder groups into indicator systems as the perception of overtourism impacts varies depending on the group.
- The scope of the monitoring and the territorial focus: to which extent it only includes the destination and whether it captures the wider region can be an important factor in monitoring overtourism comprehensively. Furthermore, com-

comparisons between similar destinations can be made, but it is important to take specificities into account.

- Focussing on fewer, less complex indicators can be a way forward especially for smaller destinations with lower technical capacities to implement comprehensive indicator systems.
- Big data can provide many avenues to measuring (ideally in real time) tourism exposure in affected areas. A key issue is data access and privacy rights. In addition, destinations tend to lack the capacities to apply big data solutions. As such, an EU-level platform could be useful.

Key discussion points on the topic solution Approaches and Governance were:

- There is a need to educate and create awareness among tourism and local community stakeholders on the impacts of overtourism.
- Integrated solutions, involving broad ranges of relevant stakeholders are important avenues to mitigating the negative impacts of overtourism ("horizontal coordination"). This also applies to economic coordination along the supply chain, including non-tourism actors, in affected regions.
- Vertical coordination between various governance levels is also important to address issues, as competences may vary between the individual levels.

Key discussion points in the plenary session "Pathways to sustainable tourism destination and future developments" were:

- There can be difficulties to stakeholder cooperation: innovative approaches may be resisted by incumbents. Further, these cooperation approaches can be resource-intensive.
- Comprehensive stakeholder cooperation approaches are implemented in Local Development Strategies via LEADER/CLLD (which tend to have a strong tourism focus) and via Smart Specialisation Strategies.
- The strengths of steering systems (e.g. awareness campaigns, dynamic pricing and pre-booking) in mitigating the burdens of visitors.

A10.2.5. Mountain destinations

A10.2.5.1. Peer-to-peer discussion

In the peer-to-peer discussion among the participants, the following points were raised by the participants on mountain overtourism:

- Mountain destinations are very specific. They are often in set path dependencies, as the key types of tourism (in particular skiing) are very investment intensive (requiring dedicated infrastructure such as ski lifts). These investments need to be paid off over long periods of time, making diversification difficult.
- Diversification is difficult: summer tourism requires different (and more expensive) lifts than winter tourism. In addition, with climate change and the associated declining snow levels, more investments are needed to sustain the winter season (e.g. snow cannons).
- Mountain destinations see specific sport day-time tourism (such as tied to sport events) which may not leave an "economic footprint" as little is consumed locally and the tourists may not stay overnight, as is the case of selected Spanish mountain destinations.
- Visitor monitoring and management strategies play a role in identifying tourist hotspots. In the Allgäu (DE) the DMO implemented monitoring systems based on mobile phone data to identify hotspots. Further, using GPS data the DMO identified that the destination became more attractive to regional tourists during COVID-19 as compared to other tourists.
- Land-use conflicts can occur between different actors, particularly in the case of areas with high specialisation on tourism. This can have an implication on the affordability of housing, which may push people to migrate to other regions.

- Conflicts between tourists and local inhabitants and authorities may occur on the actual use of land, such as hiking or biking on private property or accessing land which is not meant for touristic activities (e.g. fire protection forest aisles).
- Despite the economic specialisation of tourism, it may not make up the majority of employment sources (such as in the German Alps). However, employment in the tourism sector is often highly seasonal and not always attractive to the local population.
- Certification of tourist businesses was discussed as a means to safeguard visitor and service quality. In the case of the Alpine region, an initiative seeks to promote networking, branding, and the provision of high-quality experiences in the so-called "Bergsteigerdörfer" (mountaineering villages).
- The influx of tourism may promote or sustain the production of regionally-distinct products and services, which may otherwise not exist. Furthermore, tourism may lead to increased appreciation of the environment in mountain destinations.
- Reaching out to digital drivers of overtourism, in particular Instagram influencers, is difficult for DMOs. Many DMOs may not be aware of their existence.
- The issue of the transportation modes is prominent in mountain destinations: tourists tend to come by car and need to park at dedicated parking spots. This can lead to congestion, causing a deterioration of the quality of life.
- Increases in tourism inflows may subject the existing governance arrangements within a region to additional pressure, as tourism activities gain in relative importance and related actors gain in influence.

A10.2.5.2. Causes and impacts of overtourism

Figure A.8: Overview of challenges and solution approaches in mountain areas

In a following step, the participants identified core hypotheses on the relationship between overtourism and socio-economic developments in the affected areas. These hypotheses serve as indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure component and territorial sensitivity component). The most important hypotheses, in the context of mountain destinations, were:

- Economic dependence on tourism activities leading to a path dependency for regional development, in part due to the heavy investment load necessary to sustain mountain tourism. Relevant indicator: increase in tourism intensity and percentage of employment from tourism activities.

As part of the discussion of the project findings and conclusions, as well as the comparative analysis across destination types, the following points were raised by the participants:

- The definition and understanding of what a tourist constitutes is generally unclear. Temporary residents, such as second-home owners, tele-workers etc., while generally not classified as tourists, can create similar issues in regions as tourists (burden on infrastructure, overcrowding etc.). However, they also tend to create stronger links with the region than “conventional” tourists.
- Alienation due to the influx of tourists can affect locals: mass tourism can lead to a loss of local culture, with local residents perceiving themselves as alienated from the area.
- Implementing and sustaining participation (particularly of residents) in sustainability approaches is difficult. Regions (such as the Azores) implement multi-actor working groups based on annual data monitoring on sustainable tourism.
- Path dependency and loss of income for SMEs are factors to consider in the context of a sustainable transformation of the tourism sector. Approaches to mitigate this is by actively including these actors and their needs in strategies or by moving up the value chain.

A10.2.6.2. EU Transition Pathway for Tourism

The panel discussion of the EU Transition Pathway for Tourism discussed the initiative and sustainable tourism along the questions specified in section A10.1.4.1²⁹. The main contributions and discussion points from the destination representatives were:

- The speaker from Spain indicated that it is difficult to change patterns and behaviours among tourists and businesses since economic interests are involved. Authorities sometimes lack the experience to reach out to specialised stakeholders (such as the transportation sector or agricultural representatives). As such, education and mainstreaming of sustainability is important in the overall transition to more sustainable tourism.
- The speaker from the Netherlands highlighted that the rethinking around the sustainability of tourism started already in 2014 in Amsterdam. A goal of the 2030 tourism strategy (published in 2018) is the co-sharing of benefits between residents and the tourism sector by 2030.
- The speaker from the Azores, Portugal, underlined the importance of the EU Transition Pathway for Tourism as the overarching strategic framework for their sustainability actions. The Azores’ strategy features strong degrees of stakeholder participation and is data-driven. As part of the strategy, stakeholders need to commit and show progress. Further, as part of the sustainability charter of the Azores, there are guidelines for companies to prepare for the transition. The regional airline is also part of a decarbonisation programme.
- The speaker from the European Commission highlighted the COVID-19 pandemic as an accelerator of trends in the tourism sector: The Eurobarometer surveys indicate an increased willingness to commit to higher prices in return for a more sustainable tourism experience among tourists. The EU Transition Pathway Initiative seeks to foster a multi-actor process for an improved degree of social and environmental resilience.

Further key points raised in the discussion were:

- EU sustainability certification schemes for destinations was discussed, highlighting the overall added value in terms of easier recognition, but also in terms of heterogeneous willingness of uptake across destinations. The Joint Research Centre is conducting a project on the assessing the existing certification schemes.

²⁹ Due to time restrictions, the third question was not discussed.

- The lack of ability of small-scale actors was discussed in transitioning to a more sustainable form of tourism.
- Tourism data access is important: it is essential for more communication between data scientists and stakeholders to provide qualitative context information to the quantitative data trends.
- Overtourism varies significantly between destinations and regions. However, economic factors drive tourism. As such, a debate among tourism actors is needed on the future of the sector (i.e. what type of product is to be developed or how the tourism value chains should look like). Approaches can include incentivising change, such as requiring business-to-business travellers to remain in certified hotels.
- The role of the EU includes providing guidance and functioning as a process facilitator in the context of the overall transition. Awareness raising around the issue of sustainable tourism is important.

A10.2.7. Evaluation of workshop implementation

This section presents the overall evaluation of the destination workshop series.

A10.2.7.1. Number of participants

The project team invited participants via the following avenues:

- Invitation via case study contacts;
- Social media and newsletter outreach;
- Consortium networks;
- Circulation of information within hosting destination's networks.
- Circulation of information within EC networks;
- Direct invitation via internet research.

Potential participants were contacted with accompanying documents (leaflet advertising the project and agenda); confirmed participants received preparatory documents ahead of the workshop.

Direct invitation of destinations via internet research proved to be very resource intensive and was conducted for every destination workshop in the preparation process. The inventory of destinations affected by overtourism produced in Task A had to be significantly extended to include other destinations not affected by overtourism and destinations at-risk of overtourism. Furthermore, contact information of relevant actors in these areas had to be identified and aggregated into a database. These actors included: tourism industry associations and interest groups, residents' organisations, service and infrastructure providers.

Table A.7: Number of participants per workshop

Workshop	Number of participants
Island destinations, 9 December 2021	33 (thereof 10 onsite)
Urban destinations, 20/21 January 2022	Day 1: 33 Day 2: 19
Coastal destinations, 23/24 February 2022	Day 1: 18 Day 2: 12
Rural destinations, 17/18 March 2022	Day 1: 27 Day 2: 19
Mountain destinations, 26 April 2022	16 (thereof 14 onsite)
EU-level workshop, 20 May 2022	31 (thereof 13 onsite)

DMOs and regional authorities directly involved with matters of overtourism were the most interested and frequent participants in the workshops. Tourism-related actors (in particular infrastructure providers, planners etc.) were very difficult to reach and activate despite targeted and extensive outreach (via internet research and via destination networks), as interest from these groups remained low throughout the entire workshop series. Further, many destinations were affected by undertourism as a consequence of travel restrictions. This issue was raised in the workshops and may explain lack of interest among certain destination types and tourism actors.

A10.2.7.2. Quality of discussion and stakeholder input

Throughout the entire workshop series, contributions by participants were frequent and valuable. This was especially noted in the peer-learning sessions (Part 2) and in the systemic picture session (Part 3). In virtual and hybrid settings, the active use of moderation techniques was necessary to entice participation in the sessions. A total of 11 best practices were presented throughout the course of the workshop series (see Table A.8Table).

Table A.8: Number of best practices presented

Workshop	Number of best practices presented
Island destinations, 9 December 2021	Four best practices: Iceland, Tenerife, Azores, Malta
Urban destinations, 20/21 January 2022	Two best practices (Vienna, Florence), one thematic presentation
Coastal destinations, 23/24 February 2022	Three best practices: Bay of Lübeck, Mallorca, Catalonia
Rural destinations, 17/18 March 2022	One best practice (Plitvice), two thematic presentations
Mountain destinations, 26 April 2022	One best practice (Bergsteigerdörfer), one thematic presentation

The EU-level workshop featured four panel speakers, providing their input on sustainable tourism and the Transition Pathway for Tourism initiative. The quality of contribution was high, followed by an active discussion among the participants.

A10.2.7.3. Stakeholder feedback

The project team collected feedback in structured and unstructured approaches. Structured approaches included surveys (LimeSurvey and mentimeter.com), unstructured approaches included the collection of verbal and written feedback throughout and after the workshops.

While the collected feedback was positive, the feedback received was not necessarily very detailed throughout the workshops. When using a more structured assessments (via LimeSurvey in the urban and the rural destinations workshop or via mentimeter in the urban and coastal workshops) low response rates limited the insights drawn, providing generally a very positive perception.

However, the project team implemented several changes to the approach to increase stakeholder satisfaction:

- In the case of virtual workshops, two half-day events instead of one full-day event were implemented to improve the quality of the participants' experience and reduce fatigue.
- Changes to Part 3 and Part 4 accounting for differences in virtual workshop moderation techniques as compared to physical workshops and to reduce fatigue among participants.

- Stakeholder feedback on the EU-level workshop was positive and indicated a high level of satisfaction. Participants indicated a high degree of willingness to continue exchange and discourse on the matter of sustainable tourism in comparable forums

A10.3. Conclusions and recommendations

The workshops enabled the project team to validate significant aspects of the project findings, as identified in the literature review (Task A) and the case studies (Task B). In addition, the workshops confirmed the selection of Tier 2 indicators in the systemic picture sessions. The findings of the workshops were used to refine the conclusions (see sections A10.3.1 and A10.3.2) and recommendations (see section A10.3.3). This section also highlights the similarities and differences between the destination types as identified in the workshop series.

A10.3.1. Main observations and solution approaches

The final report showcased 15 specific cases across Europe that illustrate how unbalanced tourism growth can develop. The 15 cases highlight certain similarities and a lot of differences about unbalanced tourism patterns. They are all cases of good practices and many of the specific initiatives and measures implemented that can be transferred to other destinations elsewhere in Europe where tourism may be or become unbalanced. Although many destinations have a complex set of solution approaches to unbalanced tourism, none represent a case where the issue is “solved for good”. It is rather that each case highlights a unique setting with broad solution approaches that can be transferred to other destinations struggling with similar issues.

In summary the cases collectively contribute to the following key lessons, which were fundamentally validated and refined in the five destination workshops and the EU-level workshop:

- **Unbalanced tourism is a process** that evolves uniquely at each destination, despite some clear common mega trends and drivers.
- **International tourism growth is a key driver** of unbalanced tourism developments at most destinations.
- **Unbalanced tourism is mostly subjectively perceived by local stakeholders** as a fact of reality, particularly by residents, and depends on seasons. Summer is the most important season where unbalanced tourism is observable at the destinations, even if tourism may be present during other times, and even spreads across seasons.
- **The evolution of social media use contributes to unbalanced tourism** some specific sites becoming hotspots without key management organizations having a rapid and necessary control in place.
- **The most visible impact of unbalanced tourism includes various congestion** such as the concentrated number of visitors or vehicles in a limited geographic space, including beaches, parking facilities, lines in front of museums, or ports.
- **The non-visible impacts of unbalanced tourism are more** diffuse and include several socio-economic impacts such as touristification, increased prices and biophysical impacts throughout the year. The issue of increasing housing prices was also discussed in the workshops, since they affect local residents (via out-pricing) as well as (seasonal) employees in the sector who may not find affordable accommodation due to price developments. Cultural alienation is another factor affecting local residents: residents may lose a sense of belonging with increased touristic transformation of their area.
- **How destinations experience unbalanced tourism significantly varies** and partly relates to destination type. Many commonalities are observable amongst cities, coasts, rural areas and mountains.

- **Urban destinations** (Florence, Lucerne, Vienna) appear to have more flexibility and local alternate tourism attractions and infrastructures available to implement physical dispersion strategies compared to rural destinations. These destinations often have fewer resources and attractions as alternatives within an easily reachable geographic range nearby, such as the case of Geiranger Fjord, Cliffs of Moher, Plitvice Lakes and Monts d’Ardèche. However, urban destinations can face challenges related to cross-regional impacts and related governance issues: cross-regional cooperation is often necessary to navigate challenges stemming from transport infrastructure (such as when the airport is outside of the city’s boundaries).
- **The rural areas** analysed (Plitvice Lakes, Regional Park of Monts d’Ardèche, Cliffs of Moher) demonstrate how regions depend on tourism flows and deal with sudden large crowds at a few attraction points. Rural overtourism is often concentrated on very specific areas. Rural areas all seem to be confronted with the contradiction of capturing the economic benefits that tourism may bring, while offering idyllic rural landscapes and unique attractions. Unless rural areas are able to develop an appropriate set of attractions and tourism infrastructures to disperse visitors, it may continue to be rather challenging to create less crowded hotspots around iconic must-see attractions. This applies particularly to destinations where protected area management goals to conserve ecological integrity does not always easily align with goals to provide more tourism infrastructures (attractions and accommodation, as well as parking and ancillary services). De-concentration strategies and the redirection of visitor streams (e.g. via information campaigns) can not only help alleviate the burden on individual destinations and divert visitors to other areas, but also enable other areas to participate economically (as was the case in municipalities surrounding Plitvice National Park). Small scale actors in rural areas may be constrained in terms of their ability to respond to challenges arising from overtourism due to low personnel availability.
- **The coastal and island destinations** all show biophysical fragility. This is especially true of beaches, dunes and places of biodiversity values. Collectively island destinations have limited geographic space and share challenges with respect to further tourism growth. The absence of neighbouring land destinations makes them interesting, as any management solution implemented can be set in a very specific scope suitable and adapted to a “closed” destination. As a result, island settings provide advantages in monitoring arrivals from outside, while the movement and management of crowds locally remains equally comparable to all other destination types. It appears that solutions relying on strict control, access limits and regulations are easier to implement than in “open destination systems”.
- **The mountain destinations** analysed highlight the fragility of such areas, including biophysically or socially (Dolomites, Rigi, Bled). The destinations showcase how contemporary visitor masses can easily be channelled even to relatively remotely located places, as more and more visitors seek nature experiences at “instagrammeable” spots. Like in coastal areas, mountain destinations, particularly within protected areas, are suitable for management according to stricter controls and regulations and appropriate infrastructures.
- **The solutions to manage unbalanced tourism need to be multidimensional** as tourism is a complex and dynamic sector. No one single solution is suitable for all destinations, as stakeholder values, beliefs and attitudes are key aspects of successful management of unbalanced tourism. Each case offers transferable lessons for other destinations, regardless of the destination type or classification. However, whether a solution approach is appropriate must be decided by the local stakeholders.
- **Digital technologies**, particularly the use of big data from mobile technologies and centralized tourism data observatories, seem to be key aspects of successful management of unbalanced tourism, as they enable data driven decision making. Information provides a common ground for stakeholders of diverging interests

and power levels to consider appropriate solutions from their own perspectives. Real-time and up-to-date information provision (crowd monitoring at destinations etc.) and use of services and amenities were highlighted multiple times as solution approaches in the workshops. Nevertheless, the urban workshop in particular showed that several challenges exist when working for instance with mobile phone data. The datasets need to be purchased from the providers and subsequently the software/platforms to analyse the data. As such the city of Florence is using WIFI hubs to real-time measure density. The city is also working on using camera recordings (in conformity with GDPR requirements). The city of Vienna also prefers to rely on their own data collection efforts as it is more sustainable than using third-party big data solutions. Access to big data and recent tourism data can be challenging for destinations due to the costs associated with purchasing and managing these data.

- **Varying governance levels within a destination can be a challenge** and have an impact on the management of tourism. This was shown in the coastal workshop: in the case of Mallorca, the airport policy is under the purview of the national government, limiting the possibilities for the regional government to restrict the number of incoming flights. In the case of Catalonia, tourism rarely affects only one area, requiring a higher-level perspective for governance solutions. This can also be the case for urban destinations, where the main transport modes of incoming tourists (such as airports) may not necessarily be in the destination region. This can require complex governance arrangements.
- **The monitoring of unbalanced tourism is not well advanced** with a key set of indicators that allows cross destination comparison or an objective understanding of the issues at destinations. This contributes to unbalanced tourism remaining a subjective concept at some destinations. Systematic information collection and analysis, relevant to a destination, is key to managing unbalanced tourism. This information needs to be made accessible to all stakeholders, including residents of the destinations. The importance of impact measurement was also confirmed in the coastal workshop as impacts may vary even within smaller regions (e.g. between municipalities).
- **Visitors and residents are key stakeholders** to consider in defining appropriate solutions to unbalanced tourism. This was also stressed in the workshop on island destinations. Participation of residents in policy-making, as well as their consultation (e.g. via surveys) and means of residents to be financially compensated/take part in benefit-sharing were identified as success factors. While in the urban destination workshops the importance of the cross-sectoral cooperation between stakeholders was highlighted, also between the economic sectors, such as upstream and downstream actors.
- **Tourism intensity and density are important indicators** that need to be a part of the data collection framework in tourism observatories. The case studies have highlighted clear challenges in defining tourism intensity and density due to a lack of statistical frameworks for data collection, ones including information on day visitors, cruise ships or coach bus passengers. Furthermore, destinations need to clearly identify the spatial boundaries for managing tourism, otherwise unbalanced tourism risks continuing to be a subjective matter, and one difficult to define among local stakeholders. It is unlikely that specific intensity or density levels can be defined at cross-destinations. It is more a matter, that each destination should define a spectrum of acceptable levels for their tourism destination.

A10.3.2. Overtourism indicators

There are three mega-trends that have contributed to overtourism appearing in various destinations in Europe and other parts of the world (at least in pre-Covid times). These driving forces should be easily measurable through globally available indicators:

- Growth of international tourism in general, with a particular focus on the development of source markets from emerging economies. These demand segments contain many first-time travellers to a given destination, with a consequent focus

on iconic sites, such as UNESCO World Heritage Sites. Culturally, there may be less aversion against crowding, thus increasing the risk of overtourism.

- Passenger numbers of low-cost airlines and charter flights: These tend to focus on easily accessible destinations with (large) airports and transport high numbers of tourists in relatively short periods of time. This applies in particular to urban and island destinations.
- Passenger numbers of cruise companies: Even more than charter flights and low-cost airlines the business model of most cruise companies is geared towards very high volumes of tourists. In addition, cruise ships can only call at ports of sufficient size, thus almost inevitably leading to high visitor concentrations.

On the regional and local levels, the most commonly proposed indicators for overtourism are:

- Economic importance of tourism (% of GDP and employment)
- Tourism intensity (number of overnight tourists – arrivals or bed-nights – in relation to the number of local inhabitants)
- Tourism density (number of overnight tourists – arrivals or bed-nights – in relation to the surface of the destination)
- Dynamic bivariate indicators composed of a tourism exposure component (e.g. change in tourism intensity) and a territorial sensitivity component illustrating associated impacts of overtourism (e.g. change in the tourism employment as a share of total employment).

These are widely used indicators for measuring driving forces and pressures in relation to overtourism. The corresponding data are easily available through Eurostat and other sources. However, it is not precise enough to apply these indicators to the NUTS-2 level, as Peeters et al. (2018) have done. As several authors have pointed out, overtourism usually occurs in relatively confined spaces, for instance urban neighbourhoods or certain zones of protected areas, i.e. often even below the municipal level. Consequently, it would be appropriate to map these overtourism indicators on LAU level. However, this would present serious challenges in data availability. As such, these indicators need to be complemented with destination-specific indicators. For some destinations, especially rural and urban destinations mentioned this issue, the scope of the territorial focus might be extended to capture the wider region in monitoring overtourism comprehensively.

Thirdly, a destination- or even site-specific approach is needed to assess the local risk or actual occurrence of overtourism. This means that pressure indicators need to be refined and that state and especially impact indicators need to be added to the analysis. Based on the literature review, the following key issues need to be taken into account and measured, where possible:

- Size of the actual “tourist” area in absolute figures and in relation to the overall destination area. Ideally, tourism density and intensity should then be calculated for those highly impacted areas.
- Seasonality is a key issue of overtourism. Tourism density and intensity should be measured separately for peak month(s) and the low season. In the workshop on island destinations, it was discussed that tackling seasonality can be tricky. As pressure is eased along the peak, the peak is extended. This extends the duration during which the impacts of overtourism are observed.
- Day visitors are an important driver of overtourism. Therefore, their numbers (in absolute terms and in relation to overnight tourists) should be added when calculating tourism intensity (called “Tourism Penetration Rate” by Peeters et al. 2018) and density. Furthermore, their spatial and temporal visitation patterns as well as their spending in relation to overnight tourists should be measured, if possible. Collecting data on day visitors may be one of the biggest challenges when monitoring overtourism. Using big data (e.g. tracking visitor movements through mobile phones) instead of, or in addition to, conducting surveys might

open up new opportunities. Another possibility may be to collect postal codes of paying visitors at points of interest.

- The rising share of private accommodation offered on platforms such as Airbnb contributes to spreading overtourism into previously unaffected urban neighbourhoods. Their share of the overall accommodation offer and their spatial distribution should therefore be measured.
- The “sentiments” of both residents and tourists as an important impact of overtourism must be taken into account more systematically when managing an affected destination. This can be done either by direct surveys or by using data from peer-to-peer platforms such as TripAdvisor. The discussion in the workshops confirmed the importance of impact measurement. Dissatisfaction due to overtourism might not always be related to tourism intensity. Other and more specific factors (e.g. incidences of traffic problems) may be more important than tourism intensity alone.
- Access to data is an issue for many destinations. Reliable tourism data from big data sources is attractive to destination in principle, as it provides time-relevant data, usually available at very high territorial resolution. Good example are mobile phone data used to monitor tourist inflows and concentration. However, this data is very expensive to procure and destinations often lack capacities to manage and analyse this data.

The workshop discussions highlighted several indicator pair combinations (tourism exposure and territorial sensitivity) as relevant across the destination types:

- *Change in tourism intensity combined with the average net migration rate*, especially for coastal and rural destinations: High burden from tourism and undesirable behaviour may reduce quality of life of residents in the hosting regions. Additional burdens can come from increasing costs of living due to increasing housing prices. This may lead to stronger pressures to emigrate as it becomes increasingly unattractive to reside in.
- *Change in tourism intensity combined with the change in gross value added from tourism activities or with percentage of employment from tourism activities*: As tourism activities become increasingly attractive as an economic sector and attracts more investments, it may displace other economic activities (in terms of relative share of the sector), leading to (over-)specialisation. This increases economic vulnerabilities in times of economic crises and other crises reducing the movement of people (e.g. pandemics), generally necessitating public support to the tourism sector.
- *Change in tourist intensity combined with multimodal accessibility*, especially for urban areas: in part due to their high levels of accessibility, are attractive to visitors, especially for short stays.
- *Tourism intensity combined with artificial surface area, water consumption per capita, etc.* for destinations restricted in terms of local resources and reserves: The strain on local utilities and infrastructure due to high day-time population compared to a low permanent population was highlighted in the discussions. Particularly water consumption was mentioned in this context. The lack of local/regional (natural) resources places a burden on destinations, particularly when encountering a large daytime or non-permanent population which places additional burdens on water consumption. When restricted in terms of local resources and reserves, be it in terms of surface area for construction, environmental reserves etc., planning decisions need to be taken with great care, as to not exhaust the available reserves.
- *Change in tourist intensity combined with change in CO₂ emissions per capita*: With high numbers of incoming tourists come higher pollution levels in the region. This can be approximated by looking at the growth of CO₂ emissions per capita compared to the increases in tourism intensity over similar timeframes.

Whilst previously discussed indicators have focused on urban (or more generally, inhabited) areas and therefore on socio-economic and socio-cultural impacts, indicators

measuring environmental impacts such as water quality, groundwater regeneration/depletion, species richness, surfaces affected by trampling or volumes of waste found in the landscape etc. were more prevalent in rural, coastal or mountain destinations. The discussions in the workshops pointed out, that socio-economic, socio-cultural and environmental impacts of overtourism may be relevant for all types of destinations.

Issues with data access and data collection were also discussed in the workshops. The main results of the discussions are highlighted here:

- Resident and tourist surveys gained importance in monitoring unbalanced tourism developments, shifting away from using traditional performance indicators and environmental assessments. However, the need for comparable indicators was stipulated.
- The lack of public sector access to big data poses a problem as this data is generally not shared by the companies which collect it. Data alliances (as is the case in the Netherlands) may be used to create common data banks and access among destinations.
- Big data can provide many avenues to measuring (ideally in real time) tourism exposure in affected areas. A key issue is data access, costs and privacy rights. In addition, destinations tend to lack the capacities to apply big data solutions. As such, an EU-level platform could be useful.
- Often data is not interpreted sufficiently and lacks translation into policies and decision-making. Often, there is a lack of skills for data management at DMOs.
- Especially for smaller destinations with lower technical capacities to implement comprehensive indicator systems, the focus on fewer, less complex indicators can be a way forward.

A10.3.3. Recommendations related to mitigation measures

The main recommendations arising from the destination workshops are presented below. These were validated as part of the EU-level workshop. A final set of recommendations is presented in the main report, differentiated by governance level.

- Destinations should define ways to explore what medium and long-term balance of tourism means for their destination in order to avoid overtourism in their general planning and management framework and to acknowledge this phenomenon as an existing aspect of contemporary tourism development.
- Destinations need to adopt a definition of overtourism to enable an objective understanding of the phenomenon in their local context to avoid subjective perceptions by various stakeholder groups, particularly residents. The definition of what constitutes overtourism should be developed in a participatory process.
- Destinations may want to adopt a framework to oversee overtourism as a phenomenon beyond classical economic key performance indicators to enable a more data driven and systematic analysis of the sector in a holistic way.
- To oversee overtourism as a holistic process at a destination, the collection and analysis of data at a relevant scale, frequency and reliability on the economic, social and environmental facets of tourism in a systematic and continuous fashion is recommended. Ideally, this complements existing data collection frameworks, and not duplicates them.
- Including residents and stakeholder participation in policy-making, as well as their consultation (e.g. via surveys) reveals “pain-points” and increases tourism acceptance in the destinations. This is particularly crucial in areas with a high reliance on tourism as an economic sector and in vulnerable areas with low absorption capacities (such as in rural areas, in which overtourism occurs at very localised areas).
- Multi-level cross-regional cooperation is necessary to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism. This also applies to the coordination along the supply chain, including non-tourism actors, in affected regions. This stakeholder cooperation can

be difficult and resource-intensive. EU guidelines on stakeholder involvement in sustainable tourism development may mitigate this issue.

- The social dimension needs to be captured to monitor overtourism. This can be done via resident and visitor surveys at, preferably at the local and regional level. However, not all DMOs/organisations are able/allowed to conduct such surveys.
- Big data solutions (such as mobile phone network data) provide accurate monitoring of tourism inflows and hotspots and may be used to provide time-sensitive information in steering systems. However, these systems are generally expensive and technically complex and DMOs lack capacities or financial resources to implement these systems. As such, EU support and provision of these data services can augment this gap.
- Steering systems (e.g. awareness campaigns, dynamic pricing and pre-booking) may be used to mitigating the burdens of visitors. This can be done in conjunction with big-data solutions to pin-point tourist hotspots.
- Real-time and up-to-date information provision (crowd monitoring at destinations etc.) and the use of services and amenities were highlighted multiple times as solution approaches. Additional contributions include: improving infrastructure and implementing visitor management strategies, demarketing.
- Systematic capacity building in the context of indicator systems and monitoring is necessary at DMOs to enable the use of comprehensive monitoring systems. Many DMOs lack capacities and dedicated personnel to develop and implement indicator systems. In the case of persisting capacities or low resources, the DMO may wish to implement reduced sets of indicators, focusing on easy-to-collect data.
- Effective planning to mitigate negative impacts of overtourism including regulatory changes (e.g. on short-term rentals, time limits on hotel permits), taxes levied on harmful tourist activities, attraction-specific points, such as dynamic pricing and booking slots, as well as improvements in infrastructure.

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